

THE ROLE OF THE ORNAMENTAL HORTICULTURE SECTOR IN PLANT INVASIONS ACROSS SOUTHERN AFRICA

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Certificate of Ethical Approval

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[BordersKillKnowledge](#) in the [HostileEnvironment](#)
[I am demanding a BetterDeal](#)
[PGRsAsStaff](#)

STOP FINANCING GENOCIDES, FREE PALESTINE

ABSTRACT

Biological invasions are increasingly gaining attention due to their rising impacts, often combined with other drivers of biodiversity change. Historically, ornamental horticulture worldwide has significantly influenced plant invasions, and Southern Africa is no exception. A significant proportion of introduced ornamental plants have become invasive across the sub-region. However, documentation and research of plant invasions, including inventories and their management, are scattered and often focused on a single country. South Africa stands out as a hotspot in research and management of plant invasions. Studies in South Africa and elsewhere in the sub-region indicate that perceptions of invasive plants are complex, dynamic, and nuanced. In addition, studies show that stakeholder conflicts can jeopardise invasion management success, often reflecting societal injustices. Hence, it is essential to unpack the human dimensions of biological invasions in the sub-region.

This thesis examines the role of the ornamental horticulture sector in plant invasions in Southern Africa. It focuses on the human dimensions shaping this interplay, given the significant number of species introduced through the ornamental trade and the conflicts in managing invasive ornamental plants reported in South Africa. To achieve this, I have: i) identified which invasive plants are currently used within the ornamental horticulture sector; ii) identified the supply chain's structure and dynamics and the practices within the ornamental horticulture sector; iii) assessed the perceptions of alien and invasive ornamental plants from the stakeholders involved; and iv) provided recommendations for an integrated governance approach to ornamental-related biological invasions.

The research integrated quantitative and qualitative methods using a patchwork ethnographic approach with critical realism as the philosophical underpinning. Methods included plant surveys with descriptive statistics, semi-structured interviews, questionnaires, participant observations, focus groups, workshops, and thematic analysis. Participants included environmental specialists, ornamental industry staff, and gardeners (or end users). Data were generated and analysed from 191 participants from Botswana, Namibia, Zimbabwe, South Africa, Zambia, the Democratic Republic of Congo, and Eswatini, with visits to 66 sites across Botswana, Namibia, and Zimbabwe. Key findings include:

i) At least 22% (289) of the 1,211 plants on sale in 11 nurseries of Botswana, Namibia, and Zimbabwe have established alien populations in the sub-region, with 82 of these being invasive in at least one continental country of Southern Africa. Given the popularity and establishment

of many of these plants in the global market, this high invasion debt might create conflicts if management efforts are taken.

ii) South Africa (and Zimbabwe to a lesser extent) plays a hegemonic role within the sub-regional ornamental sector, having the colonial legacy of the British and Dutch ornamental industry and being the leading supplier and model to follow in the sub-region. The sector increasingly provides ‘formal’ and ‘informal’ livelihoods in urban areas, especially for women. It reflects a deep cultural mixing that typifies postcolonial African societies. Alien plants and foreign styles usually symbolise higher social status. Still, modern trends toward more geographically contextualised gardening practices and native plants are also in fashion.

iii) There are commonalities and differences in perceptions and understandings amongst participants that might affect the management of ornamental-related invasions. Although people’s perceptions of invasive species and particular ornamental plants vary due to different interests, socio-economic, cultural contexts, and personal experiences with the plants, the overall understanding of the key concepts of biological invasion does not differ substantially across environmental specialists, ornamental industry staff, and ornamental gardeners or end users in Southern Africa.

iv) Practical recommendations are provided to facilitate conflict management and decision-making in managing ornamental-related invasions, mainly in Botswana, Namibia, and Zimbabwe. Recommendations emphasise the need to consider power imbalances in the sub-region at individual, group, societal, and regional levels.

This thesis conveys that complex processes, termed “products of history,” influence the likelihood of plants becoming invasive through interactions with the ornamental sector and related practices. For invasion management to be feasible and sustainable, environmental specialists must practice environmental management that does not neglect social and geopolitical realities, counteracts power concentration and marginalisation, and incorporates sensitivity, care, and justice.

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1. Introduction

Biological invasions are increasingly gaining attention due to their rising impacts, often combined with other drivers of biodiversity change. One of the most influential frameworks for the study and understanding of biological invasions (*i.e.*, invasion science) is the Unified Framework for Biological Invasions by Blackburn et al. (2011) (Wilson, Datta et al., 2020). This framework describes biological invasions as a complex process where species' introduction and naturalisation (I used establishment hereafter) are core to undergoing invasion (Blackburn et al., 2011). According to this framework, alien species are those that have been introduced to an area they could not have reached without human agency. The chain of effects that leads to the establishment of self-sustainable populations in the 'new' area and eventually (or not) to prolific spread and range expansion is part of the introduction-naturalisation-invasion continuum (see Figure 1 in Blackburn et al., 2011 for the stages within the continuum). This continuum describes the biogeographical, reproductive, and dispersal barriers that invasive species overcome, spreading along considerable long distances and across vast areas (Blackburn et al., 2011; Richardson et al., 2000; Richardson & Pyšek, 2006).

The Unified Framework is not exempt from critiques around terminology and philosophical underpinnings (see [chapter 2](#) for a brief discussion about conceptual and philosophical issues and [chapter 4](#) for an empirical example of the conceptualisation of invasion and invasive species). Nonetheless, this thesis uses it as the conceptual backbone for my interpretation of biological invasions. Hence, I use the terms alien, native, and invasive species to refer to species in these categories as per the Unified Framework. I recognise, though, that these terms could be conflictual and/or meaningless in other languages and epistemological frameworks (Soto et al., 2024; Wehi et al., 2023). However, I chose to utilise them because these terms and the Unified Framework are widely used in invasion science (Soto et al., 2024; Wilson, Datta, et al., 2020), especially in South Africa, one of the countries within the sub-region this thesis focuses on and a hotspot in invasion research (Zengeya & Wilson, 2023; IPBES, 2023).

According to the Unified Framework, species' abilities to become invasive (*i.e.*, invasiveness) depend on multiple factors, including the biogeographical context, the species' evolutionary capability of acclimation and adaptation, the human agency, and the environmental history of the place (Wilson et al., 2007; 2009). Although species invasiveness does not necessarily directly correlate with impact (Ricciardi & Cohen, 2007), overall, invasive species have come to be considered one of the five direct drivers of global biodiversity change because of their

33 negative impacts on nature, nature's contributions to people and good quality of life (Díaz et
34 al., 2019; IPBES, 2019; Bacher et al., 2023). According to the first global assessment on alien
35 species and their control (IPBES, 2023), at least 39,215 alien species, 37,215 established alien
36 species, and 5,256 invasive alien species have been recorded globally (Seebens et al., 2023).
37 Furthermore, established alien species have been reported from all countries and all ecosystems
38 globally (Seebens et al., 2023). Their number is predicted to rise by 36% globally by 2050,
39 albeit with a significant variation per region and type of organism (Seebens et al., 2023).

40 According to Bacher et al. (2023), 67% (3,515) of the recorded invasive alien species have
41 documented cases of impacts, with negative impacts surpassing the positive impacts across
42 geographical regions and types of organisms (Figure 4.2 in Bacher et al., 2023). Although the
43 documentation of positive impacts has grown in the published academic literature over the last
44 two decades (Figure 4.3 in Bacher et al., 2023), academics from other fields argue that there is
45 an over-reporting of negative impacts and neglect of invasive species' benefits by invasion
46 scientists (e.g., Lidström et al., 2015; Wehi et al., 2023; but also see [chapter 2](#) for further
47 analysis of this debate). In addition, as can also be observed in other areas of science (Guibrunet
48 et al., 2024), invasion science is geographically, epistemologically, and linguistically
49 concentrated in Global North's western epistemologies in English, Indigenous and local
50 people's perspectives elsewhere are not fully considered and understood (Pyšek et al., 2008;
51 Seebens et al., 2023; see further discussion in [sub-chapter 2.2](#)).

52 Nonetheless, the IPBES report itself is based on an exhaustive review and analysis of the
53 currently available literature, stating that "invasive species are a major threat to nature, nature's
54 contributions to people and good quality of life" (IPBES, 2023; Roy et al., 2024). This
55 assessment aligns with the twenty so-called Aichi targets and goals that the UN Convention on
56 Biological Diversity set in 2011 to curb the global biodiversity crisis (CBD Secretariat, n.d.).
57 The ninth Aichi Target called for the urgent need to i) identify invasive species and their
58 pathways of introduction, ii) control or eradicate priority invasive species, and iii) manage
59 pathways to prevent invasive species' introduction and establishment (CBD Secretariat, 2012).
60 As a follow-up, in December 2022, the member states at the UN Conference of the Parties
61 (COP15) adopted the Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework (KMGBF), which
62 updated the Aichi Targets. Here, target 6 of the KMGBF aims to "reduce the introduction of
63 invasive alien species by 50% and minimise their impact" by 2030 (CBD Secretariat, 2022).

64 Impacts from invasive species exist across all sectors of the nature-society space (Angulo et
 65 al., 2021; Bacher et al., 2023). The IPBES assessment reports that biological invasion costs
 66 have increased fourfold every decade between 1970 and 2020, amounting to US\$1,738 billion
 67 in 2020 (Bacher et al., 2023). Furthermore, their analysis documents that invasive species have
 68 contributed—alone or alongside other drivers of global biodiversity change—to 60% of the
 69 recorded global extinctions, negatively impacting good quality of life in 85% of the recorded
 70 cases (Bacher et al., 2023). About 5% (175) of the recorded invasive alien species with
 71 documentation of impacts have been found to exert negative impacts on all the three categories
 72 that the IPBES framework outlines: nature, nature's contributions to people, and good quality
 73 of life (see Bacher et al., 2023 for a thorough description of these impacts).

74 As an example of an invasive species of concern globally, *Pontederia crassipes* (water
 75 hyacinth) (see Figure 1.1) stands out as one of the top 10 most widespread invasive species
 76 globally (Seebens et al., 2023) and as an example of how multiple drivers of biodiversity
 77 change can act in synergy, worsening the negative impacts from biological invasions (Hulme
 78 et al., 2023). Water hyacinth populations have exponentially grown across African water
 79 bodies, facilitated by the eutrophication caused by the overuse of fertilisers, environmental
 80 degradation, and the increase in extreme weather phenomena (e.g., floods) (Hulme et al., 2023).

81
 82 **Figure 1.1: A brief outline of water hyacinth’s invasion effects in African water bodies.**
 83 **See more in Kitunda (2018) and Bacher et al. (2023). This image was used in an article**

84 **published in the May issue of the SC Gardens Botswana magazine (Rodríguez-Cala et al.,**
85 **2023).**

86 Water hyacinth is also an example of how ornamental use is one of the main reasons why
87 current invasive plants were intentionally introduced across many geographies historically (see
88 Box 3.5 in Hulme et al., 2023 and [sub-chapter 2.4](#) for more details) (Banerjee et al., 2021;
89 Dehnen-Schmutz & Touza, 2008; Rojas-Sandoval & Ackerman, 2021; van Kleunen et al.,
90 2018; Zenni, 2014). Approximately 94% of the plants considered established alien species have
91 been cultivated initially in botanical and/or domestic gardens for mostly ornamental purposes
92 (van Kleunen et al., 2018).

93 The human agency plays a pivotal role in biological invasions, not only through direct actions
94 like species transportation and reproduction but also indirectly through other drivers of global
95 biodiversity change, such as land use and pollution. This is evident in the case of water hyacinth
96 (Hulme et al., 2023). Furthermore, human values and behaviors, identified as part of the
97 indirect drivers of global biodiversity change by IPBES, 2019, and their interactions with the
98 more-than-human entities ultimately shape biological invasions and the other drivers of global
99 environmental change.

100 Unlike the other direct drivers, which represent human actions on Earth's components (e.g.,
101 converting a forest into a monoculture of oil palms, overfishing a marine species, or polluting
102 aquifers with black water from the urban sewage), invasive species as drivers of change
103 uniquely refer to the impacts and dynamics of change created by living organisms. This
104 fundamental fact adds complexity when addressing and judging their impacts and the ethical
105 controversies that can arise from their management (Fitzgerald et al., 2007; Latombe et al.,
106 2022; Novoa et al., 2016; Shackleton et al., 2020; Shackleton & Shackleton, 2018; Selge,
107 2011). In that sense, invasive species' characteristics and impacts are contextual and change
108 over time and space (IPBES, 2023), as well as the human perceptions of them and their impacts.
109 These perceptions are influenced by historical and geographical circumstances and socio-
110 economic and cultural aspects, often varying between different stakeholders (Pfeiffer & Voeks,
111 2008; Novoa et al., 2018; Shackleton, Richardson et al., 2019).

112 For instance, Uusitalo et al. (2024) document the dynamic and nuanced public perceptions of
113 *Rosa rugosa* in Finland. The species, introduced from Asia to Europe in the late eighteenth
114 century, was known in Finland a century later. According to Uusitalo et al. (2024), discourse
115 analysis of Finnish newspapers revealed that during the twentieth century, the species was
116 highly appreciated not only for its beauty and long blooms but for its tolerance to salt, drought,

117 and low-nutrient soils, up to a point to being named “Shrub of the Year” in 1997. However, a
118 significant shift in the plant’s public meaning from being valuable and resistant to harmful
119 happened in the 2000s with the launch of the Finnish National Strategy on Invasive Alien
120 Species in line with the international biodiversity targets. The analysis of a popular Finnish
121 online discussion forum showcased mixed feelings about the species amongst the public, with
122 some showing positive attitudes towards the plant and others not (Uusitalo et al., 2024).
123 Similarly, ornamental plants like *Rhododendron ponticum* have been the subject of a shift in
124 public discourses from an expensive garden beauty to a widely planted species in woodlands
125 to a problem species in the moorlands and woodlands across Britain and Ireland (Dehnen-
126 Schmutz & Williamson, 2006). The time it takes for alien species populations to spread
127 profusely and cause noticeable impacts on their surroundings and how people become aware
128 of and receive such impacts shape these shifts in public perceptions. Considering and
129 incorporating such different views and their likely dynamic nature during the design of species-
130 specific management approaches supports decisions that are not only likely to be fairer and to
131 attract more support from various stakeholders but are also more likely to be implemented
132 successfully, being, hence, more effective.

133 A management approach to biological invasions that prevents and reduces their negative
134 impacts while ensuring their positive effects on nature, nature’s contributions to people, and a
135 good quality of life can only be achieved if we comprehend how human groups perceive
136 invasive species and how these species relate to people’s lives and livelihoods. Such
137 understanding and consideration are essential if the targets that international bodies and nation-
138 states have set up are to be reached while guaranteeing social, epistemic, and environmental
139 justice. While there is a growing body of published studies assessing people’s awareness of
140 biological invasions and invasive species and unpacking people’s perceptions of these species
141 and their impacts, there is still much more to be done to deepen our understanding and apply it
142 in the management of biological invasions (IPBES, 2023; Shackleton, Adriaens, et al., 2019,
143 see also [sub-chapter 2.3](#) for more details).

144 Considering the importance of addressing the human dimensions of biological invasions for an
145 effective, context-specific, and just management approach, this thesis addresses three
146 interconnected areas that are key to further our understanding of the interactions between
147 people and plant invasions: i) plant invasions in Southern Africa, ii) the ornamental horticulture
148 sector, and iii) stakeholders’ perceptions of plant invasions. My thesis investigates the links
149 between the ornamental horticulture sector and plant invasions in Southern Africa by looking

150 into the perceptions and attitudes towards ornamental-related plant invasions from the distinct
151 stakeholder groups involved in the interplay between the ornamental sector and environmental
152 management in the sub-region.

153 1.1 A brief introduction to a rainbow sub-region, Southern Africa

154 As the reader might have noticed from the previous paragraph, I have capitalised Southern
155 Africa. Southern Africa has at least two internationally agreed definitions. The United Nations'
156 geographical scheme comprises Eswatini, Lesotho, Botswana, Namibia, and South Africa. On
157 the other hand, the Southern African Development Community (SADC) integrates historical,
158 socio-cultural, economic, migratory, environmental, biogeographical, and geopolitical aspects
159 to its definition. According to SADC, continental and island state members comprise Southern
160 Africa ([SADC](#), n.d.). In this thesis, however, I use the Southern Africa Development
161 Community's (SADC) definition limited to the continental member states because it represents
162 a geopolitical unit of 12 continental member states sharing tight historical, economic, socio-
163 cultural, migratory, environmental, and political relations (Angola, Democratic Republic of
164 Congo, Botswana, Eswatini, Lesotho, Malawi, Mozambique, Namibia, South Africa, Tanzania,
165 Zambia and Zimbabwe). Commonalities in geographical-physical features (e.g., rivers,
166 mountains), economy (e.g., trade routes, policies), politics (e.g., political boundaries, political
167 systems), and culture (e.g., languages, religions) define geopolitical regions. By capitalising
168 "Southern Africa," I highlight that Southern Africa is a geopolitical sub-region, further
169 demonstrating the relevance of geopolitics in the empirical chapters of this thesis. My
170 definition serves as the right fit-for-purpose concept of a geopolitical region that accounts for
171 the transboundary nature of plant invasions and ornamental-related trade and exchange while
172 balancing my research capacity to cover a vast area.

173 Southern Africa harbours a highly diverse human population with strategically relevant
174 resources (e.g., rare-earth minerals in the Democratic Republic of Congo¹, diamonds in
175 Botswana) and important ecosystems (e.g., the second largest rainforest in the world, the
176 Okavango delta). There are historically nomadic hunter-gatherer tribes, like the Khoe-San
177 groups (which have multiple ethnicities) and the Hadza people (du Plessis, 2020; Shriner et al.,

¹ Although not related to this thesis, I think that the recent case that the Democratic Republic of Congo's government filed against Appel over the use of conflict minerals (<https://www.business-humanrights.org/en/latest-news/drc-complaint-against-apple-brings-new-hope-in-conflict-minerals-crisis/>) exemplifies the global relevance of the mineral resources in the sub-region, as well as the serious consequences for the local people.

178 2018). There are sedentary tribes that came from the central-west part of Africa (see Currie et
179 al., 2013 and Shriner et al., 2018, for a discussion on origins). These tribes, collectively and
180 contentedly called Bantu, give way to the Southern African kingdoms that comprise most of
181 the sub-region's population. There are also colonial-settler descendants from the former
182 colonial Arabian, Dutch, British, German, Portuguese, and Belgian empires and colonial
183 servants from other colonies like Southeast Asians (e.g., Indians, Sri Lankans, Malays). More
184 recent waves of migration (e.g., Chinese, Eastern Europeans, West Asians, and North
185 Americans) also populate Southern Africa.

186 The colonial rules—along with the genocides committed across (see Kiernan, 2023 for detailed
187 discussions of examples)—the Apartheid rule in South Africa, Namibia, and Zimbabwe, and
188 the anti-colonial and anti-Apartheid liberation movements shape the "mix" and dynamics of
189 power relations between these ethnicities (Becker, 2020; Funada-Classen, 2013; Limb et al.,
190 2010; Lissoni, 2023; Melber, 2019; Ndulu et al., 2019; Shillington, 1989). Colonisation,
191 Apartheid, capitalism, and liberation wars have hugely influenced personal and collective
192 identities, languages, cultures, and human relations with nature in Southern Africa (Baracchini,
193 2021; Ramutsindela et al., 2016; Shackleton & Gwedla, 2021; Thondhlana & Shackleton,
194 2015; van Sittert, 2003). Skin colour, ethnicity, class, and natural resources, hence, entangle
195 intimately shaping the power relations and conflicts at individual, societal, and regional levels
196 (Cloete, 2022; Funada-Classen, 2013; Hino et al., 2019; Johanson Botha, 2009; Melber, 2019;
197 Molosi-France, 2019; Ndulu et al., 2019; Pellicer & Ranchhod, 2023; Rasch, 2018).

198 1.2 Why is it important to study the links between the ornamental sector and plant 199 invasions in Southern Africa?

200 Considering the ornamental horticultural sector in Southern Africa, countries like South Africa
201 and Zimbabwe have a globally renown ornamental sector related to the British and Dutch
202 colonial legacies (Hinsley et al., 2025; Matthee et al., 2006; Mrema & Sauriri, 2014; Netnou-
203 Nkoana & Eloff, 2012) (see further discussion in [chapter 5](#)). Also, in the Democratic Republic
204 of Congo, the sector's contribution to people's livelihoods in the capital is significant (Mukubu
205 Pika et al., 2024).

206 The sector has had a significant role in intentional plant introductions and cultivation in the
207 sub-region. For South Africa, Henderson (2006) detailed that approximately 84% of major
208 invasive plants whose control, propagation, and trade were subject to the Conservation of
209 Agricultural Resources Act 43 of 1983 (CARA) and its amendments in 2001 were cultivated

210 as ornamental initially. Similarly, Kobisi et al. (2019) reported that almost 30% of the declared
211 invasive plants in Lesotho are used as ornamental. In Zimbabwe, Maroyi (2017) documented
212 that 39% of the alien naturalised plants registered in the National Herbarium were introduced
213 as ornamental. According to Faulkner et al. (2020; 2023), the number of introductions for
214 ornamental purposes has consistently grown in South Africa, with no expectation of a decrease
215 soon. Given the interconnection between mainland countries in Southern Africa and the fact
216 that South Africa has the most significant ornamental sector and is the most geopolitically
217 powerful country in the area (Gumedé, 2014), I hypothesise that the sub-region as a whole has
218 experienced this increase. Likewise, this sub-regional increase would reflect the global trend
219 (Hinsley et al., 2025).

220 Moreover, the majority (57%) of the species that had exhibited the highest increase in range
221 from 2000 to 2016 in South Africa, based on records from the Southern African Plant Invaders
222 Atlas, were introduced as ornamentals many years ago (Henderson & Wilson, 2017). Some of
223 these fast-expanding ornamental plant species in South Africa (e.g., *Tecoma stans*) are also
224 dominating urban areas in other countries, like Gaborone in Botswana (Mafokate et al., 2013).
225 These data highlight the long-term nature of biological invasions, pointing at a high potential
226 for their future increase (i.e., invasion debt). In that sense, Rouget et al. (2016) estimated a high
227 invasion debt for South Africa, using the case of invasive species of *Acacia*. Given the evidence
228 in the abovementioned studies and the transboundary nature of plant dispersal and ornamental-
229 related trade and exchange, I hypothesise that this high invasion debt extrapolates to the sub-
230 region.

231 In summary, this thesis focuses on Southern Africa to investigate the links between the
232 ornamental sector and plant invasions because of the relevant roles that the sector has had in
233 the economy and the introduction-naturalisation-invasion continuum in different countries of
234 the sub-region. However, as I have attempted to showcase in the previous paragraphs, data and
235 analyses are scattered and patchy, focused on single countries. In that sense, South Africa is a
236 sub-regional, continental, and global leader in invasion research, management, and policy
237 (IPBES, 2023; Zengeya & Wilson, 2023). This thesis aims to provide a sub-regional picture of
238 the role of the ornamental sector in plant invasions in Southern Africa. A sub-regional
239 perspective is essential when approaching biological invasions because species naturally
240 disperse across political and administrative borders. Borders in Southern Africa have split
241 socioecological units (e.g., the international border between South Africa and Namibia cuts
242 through the Nama Karoo, splitting this biome and its inhabitants into two different countries;

243 more details about the dynamics along that border can be found in Lenggenhager et al., 2023).
244 For example, as mentioned earlier, *Tecoma stans* ' populations are quickly spreading across the
245 urban areas within the savanna biome that stretches between South Africa (Northwest and
246 Limpopo provinces) and Botswana (South-East and Central districts). In addition, approaching
247 ornamental-related biological invasions requires a sub-regional lens because trade and
248 exchange are transboundary by their very nature (Hinsley et al., 2025).

249 [1.3 Why is it important to study the stakeholders' perspectives about the role of the](#) 250 [ornamental sector in plant invasions in Southern Africa?](#)

251 Research in South Africa has documented divergent views and conflicts between stakeholders
252 linked to the ornamental sector and its practices. For instance, the management of cacti has had
253 complications due to the opposing attitudes between the stakeholders who are negatively
254 impacted by cacti invasion (e.g., land managers in protected areas) and those who receive
255 benefits from their presence (e.g., plant sellers) (Shackleton et al., 2011; Novoa et al., 2016;
256 Kaplan et al., 2017; Novoa et al., 2018). Other studies have highlighted issues linked to the
257 implementation of South Africa's Alien and Invasive Species Regulations, first promulgated in
258 2014 (Cronin et al., 2017; Wilson & Kumschick, 2024) and to the wide sale and use of alien
259 plants as ornamental (Cronin et al., 2017; Shackleton & Shackleton, 2016). For instance,
260 Cronin et al. (2017) documented that 73% of the invasive plants in stock in 41 nurseries in
261 Cape Town, South Africa, may not be owned, imported, grown, moved, sold, given as a gift or
262 dumped in a waterway under the South African law.

263 Beyond South Africa, Mukubu Pika et al. (2024) documented that most (91%) of the
264 ornamental plants on sale in the streets of Kinshasa, the Democratic Republic of Congo, are
265 alien. In other Southern African countries, as my research demonstrates (see [chapter 4](#) and
266 [chapter 5](#)), the posts on social media gardening groups (e.g., Gabs Gardener [n.d.] in Botswana,
267 Gardening and Plant Lovers [n.d.] in Zimbabwe, Flower Gardening in Malawi and around
268 Malawi [n.d.], Gardening in and around Zambia [n.d.]) show the broad interest in alien plants
269 for gardening and ornamentation. In other countries of the region, less published research has
270 focused on the human dimensions of alien and invasive plants compared to South Africa (Table
271 1.1). Ornamental plants have not received much attention despite the significant number of
272 plants introduced into the region for that purpose and transiting the naturalisation-invasion
273 continuum, as mentioned earlier (further details in [sub-chapter 2.4](#) and [chapter 4](#)). Nonetheless,
274 the existing studies that were identified (Table 1.1, see also chapter 2) point to the need to

275 consider the perceptions of distinct groups of stakeholders, first, to elucidate the history of the
 276 species in the areas and second, to facilitate mutual understanding that prevents and reduces
 277 conflicts of interest. All that contributes to developing a contextual and mindful management
 278 approach that minimises costs while maximising benefits from these plant invasions.
 279 Furthermore, the studies reflect that a just and ethical management approach can only be
 280 achieved if the influences that macro-socio-ecological dynamics (e.g., unemployment,
 281 historical political processes, biocultural practices, and traditions) have on how distinct
 282 stakeholder groups interact with and understand these plants in the sub-region are
 283 comprehended as contextualised in time and space.

284 **Table 1.1: Publicly available research addressing the human dimensions of plant**
 285 **invasions in countries of Southern Africa, excluding South Africa (for details on how I**
 286 **searched for these articles, refer to [sub-chapter 2.5](#)).**

Country	Species	Topic	Authors
Botswana	<i>Prosopis glandulosa</i>	Perceptions of the species and management options in rural communities	Mosweu et al. (2013)
Lesotho	<i>Rosa rubiginosa</i>	Perceptions of the species and its contribution to rural communities	Makhorole (2021)
Malawi	<i>Prosopis glandulosa</i>	Social effects of the species	Chikuni et al. (2004)
Tanzania	Agricultural weeds	Knowledge and perceptions of weed management	Laizer et al. (2019)
Tanzania	<i>Parthenium hysterophorus</i>	Pastoralists' awareness of the species	Musese et al. (2020)
Zambia	<i>Tithonia diversifolia</i>	Effects on rural livelihoods	Witt et al. (2019)
Zimbabwe	<i>Vernonanthura polyanthes</i>	Social-ecological impacts of the species	Kachena & Shackleton (2024)

287

288 For example, Mosweu et al. (2013) document how the general attitudes and perceptions of the
 289 communities in the Southern Kalahari that belongs to Botswana about *Prosopis* (now *Neltuma*
 290 sp.) have been changing from the time it was introduced for its benefits—and plant density was
 291 low—to decades after—when the density skyrocketed in the area. The dramatic increase in
 292 range and density made its negative impacts noticeable for most within the community; hence,
 293 the community management approach in the study. Makhorole (2021) shows the relevance of
 294 *Rosa rubiginosa* harvesting for the livelihoods of the poorer households of the rural
 295 communities of Leribe District in Lesotho and as a supplementary income for the local

296 population in general. Therefore, the local benefits of invasive plants these results demonstrate
297 should be considered by the environmental managers if planning a management strategy in the
298 area. Likewise, Kachena & Shackleton (2024) unpacked how different stakeholders living in
299 Chimanimani mountains in Zimbabwe perceive *Vernonanthura polyanthes*, pointing at
300 conflicts of interest in the management between the people who are embracing the plant's
301 benefits for apiculture, firewood, and medicine and those who see its expansion and ecological
302 effects as a threat to tourism, pastoralism, and farming. People are aware of the plants' benefits
303 and adverse effects. For example, most households in Swang'oma in Malawi depend on
304 *Prosopis glandulosa*'s (now *Neltuma glandulosa*) provision of firewood (Chikuni et al., 2004).
305 Therefore, they cannot afford the removal of the species, despite recognising that its spines are
306 a regular physical hazard and the loss of grazing area to its expansion (Chikuni et al., 2004).

307 The above-mentioned studies show that the perceptions of invasive plants in Southern Africa
308 are complex, nuanced, and dynamic. Management approaches not based on unpacking and
309 understanding those perceptions, as well as engaging stakeholders involved, often lead to
310 conflicts and injustices (Shackleton et al., 2020; Shackleton, Shackleton et al., 2019),
311 compromising the effectiveness, utility, and sustainability of any chosen management
312 approach. Although existing documentation of complications in the management of invasive
313 plants related to the ornamental sector focused on South Africa, the apparent wide use of alien
314 plants in the sector across the sub-region (see also [chapter 4](#)) suggests that unpacking people's
315 perceptions of these plants as well as the factors influencing their use within the sector and
316 beyond is needed to prevent or likely reduce complications in their management.

317 This thesis provides the space for addressing these issues from the stakeholders' perspectives
318 involved in the interplay between the ornamental horticultural sector and environmental
319 management (environmental specialists/professionals, ornamental industry staff, and end
320 users/gardeners). Usually, while ornamental industry staff profit from ornamental plants and
321 end users use them for gardening and ornamentation, environmental specialists must deal with
322 the spread and (potential) impacts of those that have become invasive (see more details in [sub-](#)
323 [chapter 3.3](#)). These different groups might have divergent views due to their differing societal
324 roles with the ornamental plants, influencing how they feel about managing the ornamental
325 invasive plants and what they think the best management should be.

326 1.4 The global and sub-regional research needs that my thesis addresses

327 This thesis addresses four interconnected research needs that Shackleton, Shackleton et al.
328 (2019), and Shackleton et al. (2020) argued are fundamental to understanding the relations
329 between people and biological invasions. First, Shackleton, Shackleton et al. (2019) called for
330 improving the understanding of the role of invasive species in human livelihoods and wellbeing
331 over larger socio-ecological scales and in terms of culture, cultural services, and human
332 wellbeing, ensuring that policy, management, and governance reflect these understandings.
333 Second, Shackleton et al. (2020) called for a better examination of the role of different societal
334 sectors in shaping biological invasion processes and for a better understanding of the
335 knowledge systems and the socio-ecological contexts that shape people's awareness of
336 biological invasions. Third, both reviews reflected on the complexity of invasions, suggesting
337 the need for research that considers several stakeholder groups (Shackleton et al., 2020) that
338 can be better distinguished (Shackleton, Shackleton et al., 2019) to capture the nuances of
339 perceptions that might influence management practices and acceptance. Fourth, both reviews
340 called for more integrative methods and interdisciplinary and relational approaches to research
341 that account for the geographical, socio-cultural, political, and historical contexts and,
342 especially, the power structures shaping how stakeholder groups relate to invasions.

343 Such considerations would undoubtedly contribute to a holistic understanding of the relations
344 between biological invasions and people, lowering the chances for inappropriate approaches
345 that worsen socio-ecological realities. Focusing more specifically on ornamental-related
346 invasions, van Kleunen et al. (2018) suggest that the human drivers of these invasions and the
347 impacts and management of invasive ornamental plants need to be further explored (more in
348 [sub-chapter 2.4](#)). Properly tackling these research needs can make ornamental-related invasion
349 management an ethical practice grounded in local socio-economic and political realities that
350 prevents and tackles conflict and ensures justice and wellbeing for nature and people as part of
351 nature.

352 How does this thesis address the abovementioned needs? It uses a relational and
353 interdisciplinary approach integrating aspects of ecology, anthropology, sociology, geography,
354 and history, using qualitative and quantitative methods, with an overall non-positivist critical
355 realist lens (further explained in [chapter 3](#)). I have selected this approach to explore a multi-
356 stakeholder perspective and the relationship between the ornamental sector and plant invasions
357 across a sub-regional socio-ecological scale. My integrative and qualitative approach is
358 necessary given the complexity of interacting factors shaping perceptions and practices of

359 ornamental horticulture within different Southern African countries (further reflection about
360 the advantages of my philosophical and methodological approach in [chapter 3](#)).

361 1.5 Aim, objectives, and thesis structure

362 The thesis' aim is the examination of the role of the ornamental horticulture sector in plant
363 invasions in Southern Africa. By considering the different stakeholder groups involved in the
364 interplay between the sector and environmental management (environmental specialists,
365 ornamental industry staff, and end users) and the ornamental plants, this thesis addresses four
366 distinct but interconnected research questions:

- 367 i) Which invasive species are currently on sale as ornamental in Southern Africa?
- 368 ii) What do the ornamental horticulture sector's supply chain and practices look like
369 in Southern Africa?
- 370 iii) How do the stakeholders involved in the interplay between the ornamental sector
371 and environmental management perceive alien and invasive ornamental plants in
372 Southern Africa?
- 373 iv) What does an integrated governance approach to biological invasions look like for
374 ornamental-related plant invasions in Southern Africa?

375 These questions address the role of the ornamental horticulture sector in plant invasions by
376 focusing on the building blocks of this relation: the invasive plants on sale (question 1), the
377 structure (e.g., types of organisations in the supply chain, formality vs. informality), and
378 dynamics (e.g., practices, preferences, relations between organisations within the supply
379 chain) of the sector (question 2), and the perceptions about the plants by the key
380 stakeholders in this interplay (question 3). The answer to question 1 provides a baseline of
381 which traded species are currently invasive and the invasion debt of the sector in the sub-
382 region, i.e., the number of species that have the potential to become invasive in the future.
383 The answer to question 2 is a socio-ecological assessment of the links between the sector
384 and plant invasions by analysing how and why the sector uses alien (and invasive) plants.
385 The answer to question 3 allows us to understand how people think of and conceptualise
386 plant invasions more generally, analysing what factors intervene in their views and how we
387 can reconcile the differences and capitalise on the commonalities regarding management.
388 The fourth question is my practical contribution to the topic. Its answer provides an
389 overview of the governance of plant invasions related to the sector in several countries in
390 Southern Africa. My analysis of this overview results in recommendations that can

391 contribute to tackling the role of the ornamental sector in facilitating plant
392 invasions. Correspondingly, my thesis has the following objectives:

- 393 1. To identify which invasive plants are currently used within the ornamental horticulture
394 sector ([chapter 4](#));
- 395 2. to identify the supply chain's structure and dynamics and the practices within the
396 ornamental horticulture sector ([chapter 5](#));
- 397 3. to assess the perceptions of alien and invasive ornamental plants from environmental
398 specialists, ornamental industry staff, and end users ([chapter 6](#));
- 399 4. to provide recommendations for an integrated governance approach to ornamental-
400 related biological invasions ([chapter 7](#)).

401 1.5.1 Reflections on an artefact-based doctoral thesis

402 This thesis is an article-based dissertation (or artefact-based dissertation, per Coventry
403 University's terminology²) composed of eight chapters. The perceived value of this type of
404 thesis varies between countries, academic disciplines, and academic institutions. However,
405 ultimately, article-based theses can boost candidates' and supervisors' track records, as well as
406 institutions' pedigrees if the articles are published, given the paper-laden way in which the
407 science sector (and beyond) values researcher's performance, especially in natural sciences
408 (Mason, 2018). In addition, article-based theses tend to have broader reach in a shorter period
409 since a series of articles in different public databases are more likely to be read than a long
410 monograph in an institutional database. The article-based format is gaining popularity across
411 disciplines, institutions, and countries, but overall, it is a common practice in natural and
412 technological sciences (Mason, 2018; Mason & Merga, 2018).

413 This format has several challenges. One is creating a cohesive body of work where all those
414 articles integrate into a single joint narrative (Mason, 2018). In addition, the relative novelty of
415 this practice, especially in social and interdisciplinary fields, means institutions' policies tend
416 to lack clarity in terms of structure (Mason & Merga, 2018). There is often a lack of structural
417 guidance, resulting in a hybrid with traditional thesis elements (Mason & Merga, 2018).

418 My thesis is, hence, a hybrid. It uses a 'still very much emergent' approach for a thesis (Mason
419 & Merga, 2018) and falls back on traditional structures. It includes a separate literature review

² According to Coventry University rules, at the time of submission, the articles (chapters) do not have to be published or even accepted in a journal to be considered an article-based dissertation as long as they are in a format suitable for peer-reviewed journals.

420 and methodology section that offers the opportunity for a more comprehensive representation
421 of the research context and methodological approach than would otherwise have been possible.
422 The combination of elements of a traditional monograph-based thesis and an article-based
423 thesis implies some unavoidable repetitions within the thesis, especially regarding the research
424 context, background literature, and methodological approach.

425 1.5.2 Structure of the thesis

426 This introductory chapter offers the rationale for investigating the ornamental sector's role in
427 plant invasions in Southern Africa. [Chapter 2](#) includes the literature review that covers different
428 aspects of the human dimensions of biological invasions, focusing on plant invasions from the
429 ornamental sector, ranging from the debates around the conceptualisation of invasions to the
430 methods to study how we humans perceive and interact with species across the introduction-
431 naturalisation-invasion continuum. [Chapter 3](#) reflects on the philosophical grounds of my thesis
432 and the pertinence of the philosophical and methodological approach that I chose to investigate
433 human-plant interactions. In this chapter, I also highlight the relevance of my positionality to
434 my research practice as a brown woman academic from a geopolitically unique Global South
435 country (Cuba) conducting research in another geopolitically particular Global South sub-
436 region (Southern Africa) through a post-1992 British university³—amidst a nationwide crisis
437 related to, amongst other factors, Covid-19 pandemics. This section reflects on some personal
438 and identity factors that made me opt for this PhD and influenced my research practice and,
439 more specifically, my philosophical and methodological decisions. It acts, thus, as a preamble
440 to the analyses and interpretations presented in the four empirical chapters that follow.

441 [Chapter 4](#) compiles the invasive species currently on sale in 11 nurseries from three countries
442 in Southern Africa, Botswana, Namibia, and Zimbabwe, identifying the invasive plants
443 currently used within the sector (addressing objective i). [Chapter 5](#) describes the ornamental
444 sector in terms of the stakeholders involved in the supply chain, its practices, and how these
445 practices are related to alien plants in the sub-region, identifying the structure and dynamics of
446 the sector (objective ii). [Chapter 6](#) looks into how the different stakeholders involved in the
447 interplay between the ornamental sector and environmental management conceptualise the
448 main species categories in invasion science, how they perceive these species, and how they
449 understand the process of biological invasion (objective iii). [Chapter 7](#) provides practical

³ “In the UK, it is a former polytechnic or central institution that was given university status through the Further and Higher Education Act 1992, or an institution that has been granted university status since 1992 without receiving a royal charter” (https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Post-1992_university).

450 recommendations to improve the management of ornamental-related plant invasions (although
451 it can be applied to other sector-related biological invasions) based on my interpretation of
452 opinions and experiences shared by the participants in this project (objective iv).

453 [Chapter 8](#) integrates Chapters 4 to 7 to give an overview of how the links between the
454 ornamental sector and plant invasions in Southern Africa are influenced by what I call the
455 “products of history.” I expand this concept from the Zambian economist Grieve Chelwa’s
456 “artefacts of history” (Matsheza, 2022). According to Chelwa, “artefacts of history” are the
457 root cause of why the global trade system affects African countries (Matsheza, 2022). My
458 interpretation includes not only the geopolitics and history but also the co-evolutive relations
459 that we humans have with plants as macro-socioecological events that make synergy and
460 largely influence how alien ornamental plants are perceived and used, and hence, how the
461 ornamental sector relates to them. In addition, I make a final reflection about my PhD research
462 practice that relates to my previous positionality statement ([sub-chapter 3.4](#)). Unlike the
463 previous section, I emphasise my interpretations and the ethical concerns around giving back
464 to my participants and making the research tangible and usable for them and society.

465

466 2. Literature review

467 This chapter has five sub-chapters that cover relevant topics to understand the role of the
468 ornamental sector in plant invasions and, more broadly, the human dimensions of biological
469 invasions. [Sub-chapter 2.1](#) highlights the current conceptual and philosophical debate on
470 awareness of and responses and approaches to biological invasions from different stakeholders.
471 [Sub-chapter 2.2](#) consists of two parts. The first develops the argument around how the West
472 has influenced invasion science and how its hegemony prevails strongly through three
473 interrelated issues: geopolitical bias, epistemic bias, and the primacy of English. The second
474 reflects on the influence of Western hegemony in spreading species around the world and
475 furthering the process of biological invasion through the so-called development. [Sub-chapter](#)
476 [2.3](#) focuses on published evidence regarding the human dimensions of biological invasions and
477 the research needs of society. [Sub-chapter 2.4](#) expands further on the ornamental sector as an
478 important pathway for introducing and spreading plants, emphasising published research and
479 some of the remaining research needs. [Sub-chapter 2.5](#) briefly introduces approaches to
480 studying the human dimensions of biological invasions, focusing on the novelty and pertinence
481 of my selected approach.

482 2.1 Concepts and frameworks in invasion science: the debates

483 Invasion science has consistently grown as an interdisciplinary field since the first half of the
484 20th century, based on the increasing number of publications claiming to belong (Stevenson et
485 al., 2023; Vaz et al., 2017). This growth in research attention has led to increased scientific
486 understanding of biological invasions, but it has also come with many challenges. It is a field
487 that draws from and interacts with many academic disciplines and worldviews, while its study
488 process is a highly complex phenomenon that is hard to predict. Furthermore, its practice
489 suffers from the intrinsic ideological and operational issues that are typical in today's
490 mainstream scientific and academic sectors (e.g., reductionism, precarity, "parachute" science,
491 geographical and epistemic biases, inequalities) (Gray, 2020; Guibrinet et al., 2024; Pascual
492 et al., 2021; Putz, n.d; Rogers et al., 2013; Turnhout, 2024; Urai & Clare, 2023; Wehi et al.,
493 2023; Wilson, Datta et al., 2020; Wilson, Kumschick et al., 2020; Zambianchi & Van
494 Speybroeck, 2024).

495 Just recently, Wilson, Kumschick et al. (2020) described invasion science as maturing as a
496 discipline because there is a tendency towards standardisation despite the variety of
497 frameworks in use. The Intergovernmental Panel on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services

498 recently released the first global assessment on alien species and their control (IPBES, 2023).
499 According to Roy et al. (2024), this report "is the first global consensus that the threat of
500 biological invasions is major and requires urgent cross-sectorial cooperative and collaborative
501 action." However, it can be argued that this consensus happened at the top level of a select sub-
502 section of academics and policymakers. There are still differences of opinions, and even
503 polarisation, between people with different disciplinary training (e.g., biology, social science)
504 and work area (e.g., academic, practitioner) about core issues in invasion science (Shackleton
505 et al., 2022).

506 In that sense, Shackleton et al. (2022) reported that there was an overall high level of consensus
507 about four broad core themes of debate and critique (values, management, impacts, and
508 terminology) amongst a sample of 698 stakeholders (majority academics) working on multiple
509 invasive taxa in several geographical areas (but mainly Europe, North America, and Oceania).
510 However, specific aspects within those four themes did exhibit high polarisation (Figure 1 in
511 Shackleton et al., 2022 and Table 2.1 in this manuscript), reflecting some of the common
512 debates and/or controversies in academic, policy, and practitioner circles and beyond (Novoa
513 et al., 2024; Seboko et al., 2024; Zengeya et al., 2017). Based on those highly polarising
514 aspects, the sample was categorised into four groups whose main differences consisted of their
515 attitudes towards the critiques of invasion science, the recognition of benefits from non-native
516 species, and the need to revise the terminology. Only one group (called challenging) tended to
517 be neutral towards or agree with the critiques of invasion science, recognising the benefits of
518 non-native (alien) species and agreeing with revising the terminology (Shackleton et al., 2022).
519 This group comprised academics from biosciences, the majority of whom had no policy and
520 practice experience (the highest percentage across all groups) and a relatively higher
521 percentage of academics from non-biosciences. Two other groups (practical and conservative),
522 proportionally integrated by academics and non-academics from biosciences primarily and
523 with the highest percentages of participants involved in policy and practice across all groups
524 (but still less than 30%), tended to disagree with the critiques to invasion science and not to
525 recognise the benefits from non-native species. However, amongst one of them (the
526 conservative group, more equally distributed between academics and non-academics), a higher
527 percentage of people involved in policy and practice and non-biosciences did not agree with
528 the need to revise the terminology. The group that the relative majority of participants in the
529 study fell into was integrated mainly by academics from the biosciences, with the highest
530 percentage of participants from a biology background and the practical group. This group did

531 not agree with the invasion science critiques but advocated for revising the terminology. These
 532 results show that the academic community might be divided about epistemic, ontological, and
 533 semantic elements in invasion science, irrespective of their background and policy/practice
 534 experience. Other factors like the geographical area of experience and/or origin —and likely,
 535 epistemologies— played a role in their differences in attitudes, which Shackleton et al. (2022)
 536 briefly discussed and I will touch on in the next section ([sub-chapter 2.2](#)).

537 **Table 2.1: Aspects within broad themes in invasion science that show high polarisation**
 538 **across the sample of academics, policymakers, and practitioners working on biological**
 539 **invasions (based on Shackleton et al. (2022)).**

Broad theme	Aspects
Values	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Whether invasive species denial is a legitimate claim - Whether invasive species contribute to biodiversity - Whether invasive species should be included in biodiversity estimates
Management	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Whether commercial use of invasive species should be banned despite their potential benefits - Whether eradication is feasible - Whether stakeholders’ perceptions should influence management decisions - Whether use alone can effectively reduce impact and/or the extent of invasive species
Impacts	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Whether invasive species are a side effect of degradation - Whether the benefits of biological invasions are understated
Terminology	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Whether the definition of invasive species should be based on impact rather than spread alone - Whether species should be considered invasive in their native range - Whether the terminology used in invasion science is xenophobic

540
 541 Shackleton et al. (2022) identified *terminology* as a fundamental element creating divides
 542 amongst survey participants. The potential for terminology to create friction is tied to the
 543 importance of concepts created through language for our thinking about the world and as a
 544 basis of human societies. It has been argued that words matter since they shape and influence
 545 our perceptions and actions (Uusitalo et al., 2024). They are, therefore, also relevant to our
 546 perceptions and management decisions regarding invasive ornamental plants (Uusitalo et al.,
 547 2024).

548 As invasion science draws from so many other fields, there has been what Soto et al. (2024)
 549 called a “terminological tempest,” given the high number of interchangeable terms used (Soto
 550 et al., 2024) and sometimes overlapping frameworks (Wilson, Kumschick et al., 2020). Soto et
 551 al. (2024) found that 59 terms in English have been used to describe species in the context of

552 invasion science (see Table 1 in Soto et al., 2024). According to their analysis, the number of
553 terms has steadily increased from the onset of the discipline, whereas the rate at which this
554 number changes has tended to zero (see Figure 2 in Soto et al., 2024). The decrease is likely
555 due to the apparent consolidation that the discipline might be experiencing through the
556 influence of three well-established and complementary frameworks (Pathway Classification
557 Framework, Unified Framework for Biological Invasions, and Environmental Impact
558 Classification for Alien Taxa) that either influential international and regional entities have
559 adopted or are highly cited amongst invasion scientists (Wilson, Datta et al., 2020; Wilson,
560 Kumschick et al., 2020). Nevertheless, academics still publish papers addressing, debating on,
561 and/or criticising (and even testing) terms and frameworks in ‘invasion science’ (see Table 2
562 in Soto et al., 2024 for 37 references and Appendix 1 for additional references). Soto et al.
563 (2024), thus, proposed a basic terminology for classifying populations of non-native (alien)
564 species that aligns with the Unified Framework by Blackburn et al. (2011) —where impact
565 does not correlate with invasiveness (Ricciardi & Cohen, 2007)—and emphasises on the notion
566 that invasions happen at the population level (Sousa et al., 2024). In addition, these authors
567 presented this terminology in 29 different languages, providing a framework to counteract the
568 hegemony of the English language in invasion science (and in what we know as science in
569 general) (Copp et al., 2021; Zenni et al., 2023).

570 Human languages are the vehicle for making sense of the world and phenomena. Thus, they
571 express ways of being that are culturally specific (Uusitalo et al., 2024). The hegemony of
572 English, hence, hinders the pluralism, equity, and inclusion that science and management —
573 for the matter of this thesis, environmental science and management— desperately need in
574 order to help humanity face the current challenges (Angulo et al., 2021; Copp et al., 2021;
575 Guibrinet et al., 2024; Nuñez et al., 2021; Zenni et al., 2023). Other philosophical challenges
576 that translate into factual issues for invasion science and its application will be addressed in the
577 sub-chapter ([sub-chapter 2.2](#)).

578 According to Shackleton et al. (2022), the question of whether to consider impact (or not) as
579 being part of the *invasive* term has caused divided opinions between academics, policymakers,
580 and practitioners working within the discipline (Figure 1 in Shackleton et al., 2022 and Table
581 2.1 in this manuscript). Based on Kapitza et al. (2019) review of academic articles in English,
582 policy and practitioner circles tend to give more importance to impact. Likewise, Wilson, Datta
583 et al. (2020) suggest that the spread-based definition, framed in the Unified Framework by
584 Blackburn et al. (2011), seems more common in science circles. In contrast, policymaking and

585 management circles generally utilise the impact-based definition. Influential international
586 bodies in the policymaking and management of biological invasions, like the International
587 Union for Conservation of Nature (IUCN, 2000; Pagad et al., 2018) and the Convention on
588 Biological Diversity (CBD, n.d.), use an impact-based definition.

589 Studies in Europe, North America, and South America have reported that experts and non-
590 experts on the subject associate the invasive term with impact, harmfulness, and spread, giving
591 more importance to impact and harmfulness in general (Fischer et al., 2014; Jones et al., 2024;
592 Junge et al., 2019; Nguyen et al., 2020; Schüttler et al., 2011; Selge et al., 2011; van der Wal
593 et al., 2014). In contrast, gardeners in Britain define the term based on spread more than on
594 impact per se (Jones et al., 2024). Hence, according to Jones et al. (2024), the gardeners' overall
595 notion of invasive aligns better with the spread-based definition used by invasion scientists
596 than the impact-based definition from policymakers. Nonetheless, the gardeners' definition
597 reported by Jones et al. (2024) was generally limited to the space of their gardens, ergo,
598 denoting that spread alone might impact them. In their contexts, spread implies taking space
599 from a likely limited and highly human-transformed area, where personal preferences
600 determine appearance.

601 Based on the presented review—although I acknowledge that inclinations towards impact or
602 spread-based definitions vary between stakeholders—I believe that a greater variety of
603 stakeholders has adopted the impact-based definition, likely linked to the apparent higher
604 applicability in real-world problem-solving. Following this notion and in line with the
605 policymaking role of IPBES, the first global report on biological invasions (IPBES, 2023) used
606 a definition where the invasive stage is linked to having spread and exerted negative impacts.
607 According to Soto et al. (2024), subscribing the impact to the invasive stage can neglect the
608 real possibility that impact occurs in the other stages of the biological invasion process. Hence,
609 instead of facilitating prioritisation and making management more effective, the impact-based
610 definition could lead to unsuitable prioritisations of the limited resources for invasion
611 management. In addition, the focus on impact and harmfulness can lead to misuse of the term
612 for organisms seen as harmful or non-attractive, irrespective of their behaviour and abundance.
613 Nonetheless, risk assessment processes consider impacts regardless of the stage in the
614 introduction-naturalisation-continuum (e.g., Bayón & Vilà, 2019).

615 Whether the invasive term could be used for native species is another matter of division
616 amongst academics (Figure 1 in Shackleton et al., 2022 and Table 2.1 in this review).

617 Nevertheless, according to several studies (Fischer et al., 2014; Jones et al., 2024; Junge et al.,
618 2019; Kapitza et al., 2019; Selge et al., 2011), academics or specialists in the field tend to give
619 more importance to nativeness than other stakeholders that focus more on impact and/or spread
620 instead. When considering the term ‘nativeness,’ two controversial and widely debatable
621 ontologies become relevant: geographical boundaries and the time scale (Appendix 1). Set
622 geographical boundaries for nativeness are usually aligned with political-administrative
623 boundaries, which do not usually correspond to biogeographical and ecological boundaries.
624 Looking at biological invasions as a phenomenon operating at the population level could reduce
625 the controversies derived from the fussiness and mismatch between socio-ecological and
626 political boundaries (Soto et al., 2024; Sousa et al., 2024). Large continental countries with
627 disjunct biomes and ecoregions are likely to struggle more to define boundaries for
628 management (Nelufule et al., 2022). Therefore, I would argue that looking at biological
629 invasions from sub-regional and regional perspectives could facilitate the delimitation of socio-
630 ecologically relevant boundaries since a larger scale would be more likely to contain entire
631 non-disjunct socio-ecological areas. However, practical trade-offs emerge when considering
632 the management and coordination at sub-regional and regional levels, particularly if we address
633 biological invasion as a population phenomenon (Sousa et al., 2024).

634 The importance of nativeness and non-nativeness to guide management and their intrinsic
635 binarism also trigger the debates around xenophobia and reductionism (see review of Soto et
636 al., 2024 and Appendix 1, albeit only in English). Related to this, there are critiques around
637 humans being portrayed as artificial agents, hence, not part of nature, when mediating
638 biological invasions. These critiques argue that this portrayal only emphasises the
639 anthropocentric fracture between humans and nature at the core of the current environmental
640 and social crisis (see Appendix 1). However, counter-critiques stress that biological invasions
641 are another massive effect of the human footprint on the planet and are, hence, similar to
642 climate change, pollution, and land/sea use change, for example (see Appendix 1).
643 Interestingly, according to Courchamp et al. (2017), biological invasions are amongst the most
644 questioned drivers of global biodiversity change (Díaz et al., 2019). Unlike the other causes of
645 biodiversity change that represent human actions on ecosystem services, invasive species have
646 the evolutionary self-capability of reproduction, dispersal, acclimation, and adaptation, i.e., we
647 share these same properties. Thus, their abundance, spread, and impacts change over time and
648 space, and so do the perceptions of them across social groups as part of a socio-ecological
649 network of interactions amongst species and populations (Fitzgerald et al., 2007; García-

650 Llorente et al., 2008; Henke et al., 2024; Latombe et al., 2022; Luat-Hü‘eu et al., 2023; Novoa
651 et al., 2018; Pfeiffer & Voeks, 2008; Shackleton, Richardson et al., 2019; Wehi et al., 2023).

652 2.2 The hegemony of the West in invasion science and the biological invasion process: 653 a yin-yang example?

654 This sub-chapter has two sections. The first focuses on how the West has influenced invasion
655 science. The second reflects on the influence of Western hegemony in the process of biological
656 invasion through the so-called development. However, before going deeper into the core of this
657 sub-chapter, I shall define what I mean by West. Rooted in the Greek and Roman empires, it
658 is a fluid concept that changes depending on the lens and the context of the term (i.e., cultural,
659 geographical, political, historical). In the here presented review, the West refers to geopolitical
660 influential globally hegemonic capitalist countries, whose historical and classist supremacy
661 from roughly the 15th century onwards has imposed the globalisation of their concepts of
662 modernity, development, and behaviour, hence, being the model of how modern human
663 societies should operate (Anievas & Nişancıoğlu, 2015). However, their hegemony by no
664 means could have been achieved through their "divine intrinsic superiority," as Eurocentrism
665 has suggested, but through the uneven and combined development of exogenous forces, *i.e.*,
666 the Mongolian and Ottoman empires and the overseas colonies (Anievas & Nişancıoğlu, 2015).
667 Essentially, Western Europe and its former colonies that suffered settler colonialism at such a
668 scale that their post-colonial demographics are majority European descendants (i.e., the US,
669 Canada, Australia, and New Zealand) comprise the West.

670 2.2.1 Hegemony in invasion science

671 The hegemony of the West has influenced how the world defines and practices 'science' and,
672 hence, how academia, science/policy platforms, and practitioner circles (and the whole of
673 societies) function and "develop" (Anievas & Nişancıoğlu, 2015; Rogers et al., 2013; Pascual
674 et al., 2021; Turnhout, 2024). The Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity
675 and Ecosystem Services (IPBES) assessments, which strive to incorporate information from
676 diverse regions and knowledge systems (Guibrunet et al., 2024), might be illustrative. IBPES
677 experts conducted a bibliometric analysis of the sources of evidence cited in "Methodological
678 Assessment of the Diverse Values and Valuation of Nature" (IPBES, 2022) to explore the
679 epistemic and geographical pluralism of the literature included in the assessment (Guibrunet et
680 al., 2024). Although the results of Guibrunet et al. (2024) evidence IPBES experts' strategies
681 to diversify their knowledge sources across geographical and epistemic dimensions, the

682 Western hegemony prevails. Most of the literature that served as evidence for the
683 abovementioned IPBES assessment is English-language academic literature produced in (first
684 authored by and about) Western Europe, Canada, and the United States (Guibrunet et al., 2024).
685 Three interconnected issues derived mainly from the hegemony of the West in science and
686 practice emerge from this example that Guibrunet et al. (2024) identified as key areas to address
687 in the IPBES assessments, but that also apply beyond: 1) geographic bias, 2) epistemic bias
688 and 3) primacy of English. Within invasion science and practice, I argue that these three biases
689 are highly prevalent, hindering its capacity to deliver and implement practical and just solutions
690 for people and nature (with people as part of nature). Moreover, I argue that the geographical
691 bias is geopolitical.

692 Regarding the geopolitical bias, of the 33 original authors of three well-established and
693 influential frameworks in the field of invasion (Pathway Classification Framework, Unified
694 Framework for Biological Invasions, and Environmental Impact Classification for Alien Taxa),
695 26 are based in Europe, 3 in South Africa and one each in Australia, Canada, New Zealand and
696 the United States (Wilson, Datta et al., 2020). Furthermore, when looking at Shackleton et al.
697 (2022) sample of survey respondents working in the field of invasion, 32% were based in
698 Europe, 18% in North America, and 15% in Oceania (likely Australia and New Zealand, though
699 the authors do not clarify), meaning that 65% of the sample was based in likely western
700 countries.

701 South Africa stands out as the only non-western country in the abovementioned list. It
702 experienced the most extensive colonial settlement (and thus, displacement of people) in
703 Southern Africa (Limb et al., 2010; Ramutsindela et al., 2016). Colonial and Apartheid
704 administrations highly invested in an elitist, racially segregated, and capitalist Higher
705 Education sector (Reddy, 2004). It is not a surprise, then, that the post-colonial and post-
706 Apartheid South African academic institutions—especially the historically white
707 universities—are globally perceived as high-quality institutions producing internationally
708 recognised science, in line with the global Western hegemony in science and society.

709 The “IPBES thematic assessment report on alien species and their control” (IPBES, 2023)
710 reports “regional gaps in data and knowledge” in the so-called developing economies,
711 especially in Africa and Central Asia. All this highlights that the science and practice of
712 invasion suffer from a profound geopolitical bias based on the hegemony of the West (Nuñez
713 et al., 2022), which is not unique but representative of the wider sector (Amano & Sutherland,

714 2013; Castro Torres & Alburez-Gutierrez, 2022; Guibrunet et al., 2024; Mohammed et al.,
715 2022; Nuñez et al., 2019; Palmeirim, 2024; Pinson, 2022).

716 Regarding the epistemic bias, the “IPBES thematic assessment report on alien species and their
717 control” (IPBES, 2023) reports “gaps in knowledge on invasive alien species of particular
718 relevance to Indigenous Peoples and local communities.” Traditional Indigenous
719 epistemologies, although very diverse, tend to be relational and non-linear, where humans are
720 embedded in a web of relations with non-human entities, focusing on care for the human and
721 the more-than-human entities (Jax et al., 2018). These epistemologies contrast the Aristotelian
722 and Cartesian epistemologies that have dominated Western thinking and lifestyles that became
723 globally hegemonic from the 15th century onwards (Rogers et al., 2013). For example,
724 Macamo (2016) argues that Western epistemology exerts a “scientific power” through which
725 worldwide engrained concepts like “Africa” have been defined despite other epistemological
726 frameworks. Although constrained by its nature (Macamo, 2016), critical approaches within
727 Western science (e.g., feminist theories, post-colonial theories, political ecology, complex
728 thinking) have been challenging the “scientific power,” especially the lack of care and
729 reductionism, as well as the commodification of knowledge and nature that typifies the
730 mainstream capitalist ‘western’ science-policy-practice spaces (Frawley & McCalman, 2014;
731 Günel et al., 2020; Jax et al., 2018; Pascual et al., 2021; Rogers et al., 2013; Turnhout, 2024).
732 They usually come from social and interdisciplinary fields and anti-capitalist ideologies,
733 advocating for pluralism and justice in scientific practice.

734 Considering local and indigenous epistemologies, hence, is increasingly seen as critical for
735 effective environmental management and healthy conviviality without epistemic violence
736 (Convivial Conservation, 2024; Luat-Hū‘eu et al., 2021, 2023; Seebens et al., 2024; Wehi et
737 al., 2023). However, incorporating them into invasion science and management seems
738 complicated because of the differences in value systems and the prevalent power of a concept
739 of development imposed by the ‘West’ (Luat-Hū‘eu et al., 2021, 2023; Wehi et al., 2023). For
740 example, in Hawaii, the co-evolutive relationships between Kānaka (Hawaiians) and pua‘a
741 (pigs, *Sus scrofa*) have generated conflicts between the settler-coloniser conservationists and
742 the Kānaka communities. Moreover, Zengeya et al. (2017) summarised that most conflict-
743 generating cases in South Africa were based on differences in value systems and risk
744 perceptions in assessing invasive species trade-offs. Nonetheless, some steps are being
745 encouraged in the context of the IPBES thematic assessment of the topic (BESNet, n.d.). In
746 that sense—and intimately related to the geopolitical bias— Shackleton et al. (2022) highlight

747 that African survey respondents were more likely to acknowledge benefits associated with
748 invasive species than those from Europe, North America, and Oceania (likely Australia and
749 New Zealand). Although they said this was likely related to the fact that many introduced
750 species are promoted for economic and development purposes and remain crucial for local rural
751 livelihoods in Africa, I argue that differences in value systems and epistemologies likely
752 contribute to this tendency. The fact that people became academics in the Western modern
753 concept of it, for example, would not completely erase the values, worldviews, and experiences
754 that shape their personality and attitudes from early childhood to the present (Rogers et al.,
755 2013).

756 In addition, the knowledge and perceptions of lay people (i.e., non-professionals in a particular
757 subject) are often neglected by the arguable rigor of mainstream Western science (also see
758 Macamo, 2016 on “scientific power” above). Nonetheless, public engagement is increasing
759 through the so-called citizen science model, with not surprisingly more evidence in the English-
760 speaking West (Ellwood et al., 2023). In the field of invasion, a bibliometric analysis of papers
761 in English on The Web of Science database concluded that public engagement efforts have
762 certainly increased, but participatory engagement processes that counteract epistemic biases
763 and power relations perhaps not much (Shackleton, Adriaens et al., 2019). In addition,
764 scientific systems usually undervalue and do not fund engagement processes beyond academia,
765 discouraging scientific workers from co-designing activities with other stakeholders (Powell et
766 al., 2022). Reductionist views of what is rigorous, robust, valuable, and/or genuine can hinder
767 not only the fair incorporation of lay people and indigenous epistemologies but also the
768 possibility of evidence of this integration since usually only academic papers in English are the
769 trusted source of knowledge—even in purposively inclusive platforms (Guibrinet et al., 2024).

770 There is no doubt that English has become the universal language of science (Amano et al.,
771 2016; Amano & Sutherland, 2013; Copp et al., 2021; Nuñez et al., 2019; Nuñez et al., 2021).
772 Thus, in the first instance, only people who understand English can at least read and/or listen
773 to first-hand scientific information (Amano & Sutherland, 2013; Nuñez et al., 2019). Moreover,
774 this means that the application and understanding of non-English contexts of concepts need,
775 thus, double translation, first into non-English languages and second into non-scientific jargon.
776 This challenge also applies vice-versa when scientific processes consider lay knowledge—a
777 process entangled with the epistemic bias I touched on before.

778 The primacy of English has profound implications for invasion science and its application since
779 some terms do not have translation or meaning in other languages, especially non-Western,
780 non-hegemonic languages (Soto et al., 2024). Furthermore, as languages reflect and are
781 influenced by cultures, epistemologies, and geographies (Copp et al., 2021; Qiong, 2017;
782 Uusitalo et al., 2024), multilateral translations pose challenges to the appropriate interpretations
783 of meanings, and ultimately, management and consensus amongst stakeholders (Copp et al.,
784 2021). In that sense, Copp et al. (2021) showcase how the epistemic, cultural, and geographical
785 differences influence the ways people respond to uncertainty and risks in invasion management
786 by translating an Aquatic Species Invasiveness Screening Kit—a decision-support tool—into
787 23 languages. For example, they comment on the differences in risk perceptions when
788 translating the kit from English to Chinese since Chinese culture, based on the Ying-Yang
789 philosophy that accepts co-existence in contradiction, tends to have lower levels of
790 probabilistic thinking than Western cultures shaped by the Aristotelian logics. Then, Chinese
791 assessors could be more likely to accept the risks of non-native species if they generate
792 substantial benefits and evidence of local adverse impact is minor or non-existent (Copp et al.,
793 2021).

794 Moreover, within the academic sector, to be able to access a job and/or have a promotion, not
795 to mention gaining international recognition, pressures are high to publish in arguably ‘top-
796 quality’ journals in English (Paasche & Österblom, 2019; van Dalen & Henkens, 2012).
797 Nonetheless, knowledge sources in non-English languages are quite diverse, providing
798 fundamental insights into understanding the environment and its dynamics (Nuñez et al., 2021;
799 Zenni et al., 2023). For instance, Angulo et al. (2021) showcase the contributions published in
800 15 non-English languages, furthering the knowledge of the economic costs of biological
801 invasions. Despite the many journals and data in other languages (see, for example, Scielo and
802 Dialnet databases for Spanish and Portuguese), journals in English from multinational
803 publishers from the ‘West’ (e.g., Elsevier, Springer, Taylor & Francis) tend to be globally
804 perceived as more prestigious, granting people higher credibility if they author papers in such
805 journals (Gray, 2020).

806 Existing geopolitical and epistemic biases create synergies to uphold the primacy of English in
807 science and even the less but still dominating role of other hegemonic languages such as
808 Castilian and French. For example, Angulo et al. (2023) acknowledge that Castilian from Spain
809 (rather than from Spanish-speaking Latin America) and French from France (rather than from
810 French-speaking Africa) dominated the non-English database of documents reporting

811 economic costs of biological invasions that they created. Furthermore, Castro Torres &
812 Alburez-Gutierrez (2022) report that academic papers from 23 social science sub-fields based
813 on case studies in the West tend to claim universality. According to these authors, papers
814 written by people affiliated with institutions in the Global North (equivalent to the West
815 considered here) about issues in the Global North are less likely to reference the research
816 location than papers from people affiliated with institutions in the Global South about issues in
817 the Global South. Although ecology and environmental sciences tend to reference geographical
818 locations, the increasing inter- and transdisciplinary studies that address human and more-than-
819 human natures and non-human and human species interactions in invasion science would need
820 to be mindful of these biases.

821 Several people are proposing (and implementing) actions to address the abovementioned biases
822 (Angulo et al., 2021; Copp et al., 2021; Guibrinet et al., 2024; Günel et al., 2020; Haubrock et
823 al., 2024; Mohammed et al., 2022; Nuñez et al., 2021; Pascual et al., 2021; Powell et al., 2022;
824 Urai & Clare, 2023; Wehi et al., 2023; Zenni et al., 2023). However, I suggest these biases sit
825 within a complex feedback loop that is challenging to break. People working in the
826 academic/scientific sector are also victims of the precarious and highly unequal worldwide—
827 although financially, and perhaps, geographically and socially privileged based on the biases
828 presented before (Urai & Clare, 2023). As researchers, academics, scientists, policymakers, or
829 practitioners, we have the social responsibility to make efforts for systemic changes toward
830 environmental and social justice, pluralism, and decolonisation in our spaces of influence
831 (Pascual et al., 2021; Turnhout, 2024). However, I also acknowledge that these biases in the
832 sector are the representation of more prominent and more powerful political and economic
833 lobbies that influence societies globally (see the yearly anthology on global power and
834 resistance “State of Power” from the Transnational Institute
835 (<https://www.tni.org/en/topic/state-of-power>). There are exhaustive examples of how Western
836 modernity entangled in coloniality and neo-coloniality still shapes (and funds) the
837 environmental and conservation agendas across the world, reinforcing the synergies amongst
838 the abovementioned biases and hence, perpetuating its hegemony (Betsill et al., 2022; Büscher
839 & Thakholi, 2024; Clarke & Cisneros-Montemayor, 2024; Enns & Bersaglio, 2024; Matose,
840 2016; Shackleton & Gwedla, 2021; Spierenburg & Wels, 2010; Thakholi & Büscher, 2021;
841 Wieckardt et al., 2022). Pathways for change, hence, are convoluted and lengthy.

842 2.2.2 Hegemony in the biological invasion process

843 Humans have moved species worldwide since ancient times (Frawley & McCalman, 2014).
844 However, European imperial colonialism marked a milestone, not only for the rise of the West
845 and capitalism (Anievas & Nişancıoğlu, 2015) but for the establishment of non-native
846 populations of species that we have assimilated (or maybe not) into our territories, some of
847 which are now considered invasive (Frawley & McCalman, 2014; Lenzner et al., 2022; Raja,
848 2022; Wehi et al., 2023). Analysing Spanish, Portuguese, Dutch, and British colonial empires,
849 Lenzner et al. (2022) show that the alien flora in the different regions occupied by the same
850 empire have more similarity between each other than expected by chance. This similarity
851 increases with the duration of the occupation. In addition, centroids of similarity coincide with
852 economic and administrative hubs (e.g., South Africa and the Indo-Malay region for the Dutch
853 empire, Mexico for the Spanish empire). European colonialism—an accelerator of the Western
854 hegemony with its associated “modernity”—re-distributed humans and other species globally,
855 having a profound agency in the process of biological invasion (Raja, 2022).

856 Processes of enduring exploitation and extraction, forced displacement and migration, slavery,
857 and uneven settler colonialism, techno-industrial developments, and urbanisation have
858 modified the socio-ecological systems of both metropolis and colonies, shaping the territories
859 that we see today and their species. For example, Enns & Bersaglio (2024) tell the socio-
860 political and ecological stories of colonial settlers in Laikipia (current Kenya) and Torrejón et
861 al. (2004) of the influence of colonial settlers in the environmental history of Chiloé (current
862 Chile). Colonial settlers in Laikipia have perpetuated their ownership, identity, and right-to-be
863 through the manipulation and oppression of the space in different ways in time: first,
864 eliminating and displacing undesired species; second, rewilding with desirable species; third,
865 re-peopling the space to make it seem inclusive and capitalise on the biocultural diversity;
866 fourth, rescuing animals and other species at risk of extinction; and fifth, scaling up their
867 approaches as conservation models (Enns & Bersaglio, 2024). Colonial settlers in Chiloé
868 initially attempted to transform the Chiloean landscape based on their cultures and geographies
869 back home. However, the Chiloean geography limited these attempts, even though some
870 introduced species acclimated and were being assimilated by Indigenous people in the territory.
871 Concomitantly, colonial settlers appropriated cultural and ethnobotanical practices from the
872 indigenous people they displaced, generating a new socio-ecological system of uneven
873 coexistence between species (Torrejón et al., 2004).

874 In South Africa, a global hotspot in invasion research (IPBES, 2023), colonial settler histories
875 have driven the relations between people and other species, resulting in changing views and
876 approaches towards non-native and native species throughout time (Bennett, 2014; Bennett &
877 Kruger, 2015; Bennett & van Sittert, 2019; Canavan, Richardson et al., 2019). With the start
878 of European colonialism in the sub-region, waves of plant introductions from other areas
879 belonging to the colonial empires started and were often intended for forestry and agriculture
880 purposes in order to “build” the South African colony (Bennett & Kruger, 2015; Canavan,
881 Richardson et al., 2019; Henderson, 2006). The waves of ornamental plant introductions into
882 the sub-region started later, once colonial settlerism consolidated and colonial administrations
883 and ‘development’ were in place (Bennett & van Sittert, 2019; Canavan, Richardson et al.,
884 2019). For example, according to Canavan, Richardson et al. (2019), between 1850 and 1920,
885 European Victorian “plant hunters” promoted the fashion of alien plants, especially from Asia.
886 In South Africa, hence, bamboo, especially temperate species from China, became a
887 fashionable ornamental and status plant for wealthy people, following European trends.

888 By the first half of the 20th century, nonetheless, the identification with the Cape native flora
889 had become a mark for class, ethnic, and regional identity for the old urban imperial English-
890 speaking class from the Western Cape, who stayed in “a new nation” ruled by the rural
891 Afrikaans republicanism (Bennett & van Sittert, 2019; Comaroff & Comaroff, 2001; van
892 Sittert, 2003). In general, the wealthier (and whiter) strata of several countries in Southern
893 Africa, starting with South Africa, have led the movement that takes pride in the native flora
894 (Bennett & van Sittert, 2019). The colonial settler-descendant Africans have progressively
895 adopted a separate identity as Africans (Ginsburgh, 2022; Johanson Botha, 2009; Matthews,
896 2011; Rasch, 2018). In this historical collective process, these groups of people have
897 increasingly identified, in turn, with the non-human landscape and biodiversity that their
898 colonial ancestors found when they settled in the sub-region (Spierenburg & Wels, 2010). The
899 imagery of native ecosystems that have to be safeguarded from alien invasive species has been
900 used as an excuse for wealth and power accumulation and reaffirmation (e.g., mesquite
901 eradication along the Orange River in Southern Namibia by Moore & Lenggenhager, in press)
902 and white identity reinvention in the post-Apartheid era (e.g., wattle eradication in
903 Baviaanskloof Mega-Reserve, South Africa by Merron, 2010). All this shows how power
904 imbalances and oppression are normalised through nature conservation and science in the sub-
905 region (Comaroff & Comaroff, 2001; Ramutsindela et al., 2016; Spierenburg & Wels, 2010;
906 van Sittert, 2003). For instance, colonial and Apartheid legacies remain powerfully prevalent

907 in the urban greening of South Africa at the expense of indigenous worldviews and identities
908 (Shackleton & Gwedla, 2021).

909 These scenarios have triggered calls from critical scholars within ‘western’ science for
910 recognising and acting against the colonial legacies structuring conservation and environmental
911 practices (Convivial Conservation, 2024; Pascual et al., 2021). Steps have been taken. A recent
912 promising example is the conservation vision articulated by 520 Massai elders, women, and
913 youth from 26 villages of five districts (Ngorongoro, Longido, Monduli, Simanjiro, and Kiteto)
914 in the current Northern Tanzania (Massai Community Members & MISA, 2024). This vision
915 aims “to develop and promote an alternative to the colonial, fortress, violent and capitalistic
916 conservation model that is imposed on [our] Maasai community, leading to the alienation of
917 [our] land.” Again, pathways are long and winding, but hope remains.

918 2.3 Human dimensions of biological invasions

919 Biological invasions are intimately related to humans. Thanks to humans, many non-human
920 species have crossed biogeographical barriers that could not have been crossed otherwise
921 (Hulme et al., 2023; Seebens et al., 2017; 2018; Wilson, García-Díaz et al., 2016). Although
922 human agency is contested (see earlier in sub-chapter 2.1), it is fundamental to our
923 understanding of biological invasions. However, despite how fundamental it is, the topic has
924 not received as much attention as the (non-human) ecology of the phenomenon, for example
925 (IPBES, 2023). Questions related to human agency and human perceptions, such as how
926 different groups of people perceive specific invasive species and their impacts on the
927 landscape, how specific invasive species shape livelihoods and human well-being, how
928 management can be co-created, and how the different aspects of human societies influence the
929 biological invasion process, are core to comprehend the complexities and challenges derived
930 from biological invasions (Frawley & McCalman, 2014; Pfeiffer & Voeks, 2008; Shackleton,
931 Adriaens et al., 2019; Shackleton, Shackleton et al., 2019; Shackleton, Richardson et al., 2019;
932 Wehi et al., 2023).

933 According to Shackleton, Richardson et al. (2019), the hierarchical interrelation between
934 individuals, species, species' impacts, socio-cultural contexts, landscape contexts, and
935 institutional, governance and policy contexts shape people's perceptions of invasive species
936 (Figure 1 in Shackleton, Richardson et al., 2019). When referring to perceptions as a
937 neurocognitive activity, Qiong (2017) states that the primary factor accounting for their
938 diversity is culture, which the author describes as a construct encompassing three elements: a)

939 beliefs, values, and attitudes; b) worldviews; and c) social organisations. For instance, the
940 varying concepts that Māori (in current New Zealand), aboriginal Hawaiian (in current
941 Hawai'i'), and Anishinaabek (in current North America) peoples use to describe native, alien,
942 and invasive species denote positive, negative, and neutral attitudes that depend on their
943 worldviews and the species' services to the environment and its people (Wehi et al., 2023).

944 The mutual interactions between the different factors that Shackleton, Richardson et al. (2019)
945 and Qiong (2017) mentioned change over time and space, having lag times for each other and
946 different scales (Shackleton, Richardson et al., 2019). In addition, local, regional, and global
947 power relations and geopolitics—affected by history's uneven and combined development
948 (Anievas & Nişancıoğlu, 2015)—influence these factors and their interrelation (Ramutsindela
949 et al., 2016). For example, the introduction and establishment of feral pig populations in
950 Hawai'i' along with drastic changes in their socio-ecological contexts during the 19th century
951 due to the European colonisation, triggered a rapid bio-cultural evolution where pig hunting
952 was incorporated into the Hawaiian culture (Luat-Hū'eu et al., 2021). Nowadays, this practice
953 constitutes an important food source as well as a form of well-being (e.g., peace of mind,
954 adrenaline, and excitement) and traditional perpetuation for Hawaiian communities (Luat-
955 Hū'eu et al., 2023), but also a flashpoint of conflict with the settler-coloniser conservationists
956 (Luat-Hū'eu et al., 2021). In South Africa, policies and legislation targeting invasive species,
957 as well as the media and institutional portrayal of the species, have been driven by the changes
958 in perceptions of elite societal groups linked to the colonial and Apartheid legacies (Boehi,
959 2016; 2021; Bennett & van Sittert, 2019; Shackleton et al., 2020; van Sittert, 2003). In post-
960 colonial and post-Apartheid South Africa, a few species have stirred conflicts, such as mesquite
961 (*Prosopis* spp., now *Neltuma* spp.) and prickly pears (*Opuntia* spp.). Root causes for such
962 conflicts often lie in the systemic inequality derived from colonial and Apartheid times,
963 reflecting people's adaptations to the socio-ecological changes that geo-political forces trigger
964 (Canavan, Richardson et al., 2019; Shackleton & Gwedla, 2021; Shackleton et al., 2011; 2020;
965 Venter et al., 2020).

966 In addition, studies in rural communities of Botswana, Lesotho, Malawi, South Africa, and
967 Zimbabwe show that local perceptions of invasive species are likely to change over time,
968 informed and shaped by the effects that these species have on people's livelihoods and daily
969 lives (Chikuni et al., 2004; Mosweu et al., 2013; Makhorole, 2021; Kachena & Shackleton,
970 2024; Shackleton & Shackleton, 2018; Shackleton et al., 2015). For instance, South Africa's
971 nursery owners, land managers, game reserve owners, farmers, and the public have different

972 views of invasive ornamental cacti, primarily based on their interests (Kaplan et al., 2017;
973 Novoa et al., 2016; 2018). Moreover, species like *Prosopis* are controversial across the sub-
974 region because of the vital benefits they provide, like firewood and their negative impacts on
975 cattle grazing and health, for example (Chikuni et al., 2004; Mosweu et al., 2013; Shackleton
976 & Shackleton, 2018; Shackleton et al., 2015).

977 Beyond Southern Africa, García-Llorente et al. (2008) showcase how socio-economic status,
978 profession, and the extent to which people use and/or live in a place 'affected' by invasive
979 species influence their perceptions of such plants in a protected area in Spain. In that sense,
980 Novoa et al. (2024) conclude that across several geographical regions, key stakeholders who
981 benefit from alien trees or seek to promote their usefulness have more positive attitudes towards
982 these plants compared with other key stakeholders who do not benefit.

983 The human dimensions of biological invasions can be highly complex, given the number of
984 interrelated and varying factors playing a part. This complexity, thus, can complicate invasive
985 species management (Crowley et al., 2017; Shackleton, Adriaens et al., 2019; Zengeya et al.,
986 2017). For invasion management to succeed and be fair, meaningful engagement with
987 interested and affected stakeholders (Crowley et al., 2017; IPBES, 2023; Shackleton, Adriaens
988 et al., 2019; Zengeya et al., 2017), alignment with indigenous and local management
989 frameworks (Wehi et al., 2023) and an acknowledgment, at least, of the not so hidden,
990 underlying struggles (Frawley & McCalman, 2014; Enns & Bersaglio, 2024) would be
991 necessary.

992 [2.4 Plant invasions from the ornamental sector](#)

993 Humans have spread plant species worldwide for several reasons (e.g., forestry, food, fodder,
994 and ornamentation) (Hulme et al., 2023). Amongst these pathways, the ornamental sector has
995 played an important role in contributing to the emergence of plant invasions (see Box 3.5 in
996 Hulme et al., 2023 for the example of botanical gardens). According to van Kleunen et al.
997 (2018), approximately 94% of the plants that have established viable populations in spaces
998 beyond their native ranges were initially cultivated in botanical and/or domestic gardens for
999 mostly ornamental purposes. Several reports have unpacked this global estimate by regions and
1000 countries. For example, Dehnen-Schmutz & Touza (2008) have compiled that between 40%
1001 and 75% of the plants introduced and/or established in Australia, Belgium, Britain, Czech
1002 Republic, Germany, Ireland, Italy, and the United States were introduced primarily as
1003 ornamental. In Brazil, Zenni (2014) quantifies that 43% of the country's invasive plants listed

1004 in 2011 were introduced as ornamental. Giorgis & Tecco (2014) estimate that 91% of the
1005 woody plants considered invasive in Córdoba (Argentina) were introduced as ornamental.
1006 Meanwhile, surveying 49.1% of Ethiopia, Kenya, Rwanda, Tanzania, and Uganda (Eastern
1007 Africa), Witt et al. (2018) report that 61% of the recorded plants considered invasive were
1008 introduced as ornamental. Also, Rojas-Sandoval & Ackerman (2021) document that 54% of
1009 the plants considered invasive in 18 Caribbean archipelagos (Anguilla, Aruba, the Bahamas,
1010 Bonaire, Cuba, Curacao, Dominican Republic, Guadeloupe, Jamaica, Martinique, Puerto Rico,
1011 St. Barthélemy, St. Eustatius, St. Lucia, St. Martin, Saba, Trinidad and Tobago and the Virgin
1012 Islands) were introduced as ornamental. Furthermore, Banerjee et al. (2021) highlight that
1013 many plants considered invasive in India are used as ornamental compared to other uses.

1014 In Southern Africa, Henderson (2006) documents that approximately 84% of plants considered
1015 major invasives in South Africa were initially cultivated as ornamental. For Lesotho, Kobisi et
1016 al. (2019) report that almost 30% of the declared invasive plants are used as ornamental. In
1017 Zimbabwe, Maroyi (2017) details that 39% of the alien plants that have established populations
1018 were introduced as ornamental. Moreover, 57% of the species that exhibited the highest range
1019 increase from 2000 to 2016 in South Africa—based on records from the Southern African Plant
1020 Invaders Atlas—were also introduced as ornamental (Henderson & Wilson, 2017).

1021 These estimates—although limited to the species whose pathways of introduction are
1022 recorded—talk about the significant role of the ornamental sector in the key stages highlighted
1023 in the Unified Framework for Biological Invasions (see Figure 1 in Blackburn et al., 2011). In
1024 ecological terms, certain functional traits favoured for ornamental use can also favour plant
1025 invasiveness (van Kleunen et al., 2018). Trendy garden plants are often easy to grow, perform
1026 well in different climates and environments, and resist diseases and predation. The interrelation
1027 of the ease of propagation, fast growth, long flowering periods, and a broad climate niche has
1028 been indeed associated with increased plant invasiveness (van Kleunen et al., 2018). However,
1029 this varies depending on the plant group. For instance, slow growth is favoured in cacti (Novoa,
1030 le Roux et al., 2017), while sterility in best-selling plants like roses, carnations, and
1031 chrysanthemum (Gessert, 1993; Giovannini et al., 2021), which, in turn, are reducing their
1032 invasiveness. In political ecologist terms, these functional traits build the "plantiness" of plant
1033 species, determining their intimate relations with humans (Head et al., 2012; Uusitalo et al.,
1034 2024) and thus, driving co-evolutionary relationships between humans and ornamental plants
1035 (Altman et al., 2022; Gessert, 1993; Haviland-Jones et al., 2005; Huss et al., 2018; Wilson,
1036 Kendal et al., 2016).

1037 Moreover, plant surveys in human niches (i.e., urban areas) across the world show that, in
1038 general, introduced ornamental plants dominate (Castillo-Rodríguez & Pastrana-Falcón, 2015;
1039 Duncan et al., 2011; Hope et al., 2006; Knapp et al., 2010; Monalisa-Francisco & Nunes-
1040 Ramos, 2019; Pataki et al., 2013; Potgieter et al., 2020; Ottoni Batista dos Santos et al., 2012;
1041 Senademi Sogbossi et al., 2020; Wang et al., 2012). Urbanisation is being increasingly
1042 identified as a strong driver of selection and evolution (William et al., 2009; Piana et al., 2019),
1043 emphasising the idea that ornamental plants and humans have a mutualistic relationship
1044 (Wilson, Kendal et al., 2016; Altman et al., 2022). Several plants currently thriving in
1045 anthropogenic ecosystems —many ornamental plants (Potgieter et al., 2017)— might have
1046 evolved traits to support human-mediated dispersal (Spengler, 2020). The plants sometimes
1047 fulfill human spirits in exchange for an enhanced propagation probability and competitive
1048 superiority. In others, they use humans for dispersal and growth opportunities despite humans,
1049 i.e., weeds (Canavan et al., 2022; Kanapeckas et al., 2016; Wu et al., 2021).

1050 Due to several interrelated factors, the ornamental sector will likely have a prominent role in
1051 plant invasions in the future. Urban areas are expanding globally (Ritchie et al., 2024), creating
1052 a continuing market for the sector. In addition, gardening is increasingly promoted and adopted
1053 in response to the global environmental and humanitarian crisis (Cruz de Sousa et al., 2022;
1054 Francini et al., 2022; Gabellini & Scaramuzzi, 2022; Hinsley et al., 2025; van Kleunen et al.,
1055 2018). The horticultural industry is quickly evolving and expanding (Beruto et al., 2022;
1056 Hinsley et al., 2025) through e-commerce (Humair et al., 2015; Man et al., 2023), the culture
1057 of social media influencers (van Kleunen et al., 2018) and biotechnology creating 'super'
1058 cultivars (Beruto et al., 2022; Giovannini et al., 2021), as well as the changes in global trade
1059 patterns (Gabellini & Scaramuzzi, 2022; Hinsley et al., 2025; Industry Research, 2022).
1060 Although the sector could promote species and cultivars with low invasiveness (van Kleunen
1061 et al., 2018), a high propagule pressure (i.e., the quantity, quality and frequency of propagules
1062 such as spores, seeds, tubercles, or saplings released in a given location) can unleash
1063 successful invasions from those species that can seize the opportunities from a changing
1064 environment, where climate change (van Kleunen et al., 2018; Oduor et al., 2023; Omer et al.,
1065 2024) and anthropogenic transformation (Canavan, Kumschick et al., 2019; William et al.,
1066 2009; Piana et al., 2019) are selective forces.

1067 According to van Kleunen et al. (2018), these scenarios leave us with eight key research topics
1068 to better understand the role of the ornamental sector in plant invasions (Figure 2.1, see Table
1069 1 in van Kleunen et al., 2018). The human dimension is a common theme intersecting these

1070 research topics, but it is not appropriately addressed nor explicitly emphasised by the authors.
 1071 For example, in the first topic (Figure 1 and Table 1 in van Kleunen et al., 2018), the authors
 1072 suggest that knowing why certain species are introduced and based on what selection criteria
 1073 are priority questions, but none of the data the authors recommend appear able to answer these
 1074 questions fully. When suggesting the identification of current and future trends in ornamental
 1075 fashions and plant traits as priority questions (the second research topic, see Figure 2.1), the
 1076 authors recommend data from "questionnaires to horticulturist experts" and "different scientific
 1077 domains" to answer the question, which would likely be a more appropriate approach to address
 1078 this question and the ones mentioned for the first research topic. In the third research topic, the
 1079 focus on the synergies between invasions and other recognised global drivers of biodiversity
 1080 change is necessary and fundamental to understanding the complexities of these phenomena.
 1081 However, this research topic must also focus on how so-called indirect drivers of global
 1082 change, representing human values and behaviours (Díaz et al., 2019; Hulme et al., 2023),
 1083 interact with invasions. This focus is fundamental if drivers are to be identified and
 1084 comprehended since plant invasions from the ornamental sector are intimately related to
 1085 humans at different societal levels (Hulme et al., 2023; Shackleton, Richardson et al., 2019).
 1086 For instance, researching how sociocultural aspects, governance, and conflicts interact with
 1087 invasions from the sector could give more profound insights into the drivers that the third topic
 1088 aims to tackle.

1089 **Figure 2.1: Research needs to understand the role of the ornamental sector in plant**
 1090 **invasions, based on van Kleunen et al. (2018) review.**
 1091

1092 Overall, the much-needed consideration of the human dimensions to understand the relation
 1093 between the ornamental sector and plant invasions requires transdisciplinary approaches to

1094 research that go beyond the proposed questionnaires to horticultural experts (for the second
1095 research topic) and surveys and questionnaires of gardeners, authorities and managers of
1096 invasive species (for the eighth research topic) (Powell et al., 2022; Shackleton, Adriaens et
1097 al., 2019; Vaz et al., 2022). There are, for example, other qualitative methods —discussed in
1098 the following section— that can help to unpack better human behaviours and values
1099 underpinning the role of the ornamental sector in plant invasions. Finally, the eighth topic
1100 presented by these authors (Figure 1 and Table 1 in van Kleunen et al., 2018), although relevant,
1101 speaks with its focus on awareness of the narrow assumptions of the information deficit
1102 model—which have been proven non-realistic for science communication (Toomey et al.,
1103 2016). The priorities presented for this topic also reflect the common epistemic bias, where
1104 researchers are the key knowledge holders and must educate others. Nonetheless, I believe one
1105 fundamental question for the ethical management of ornamental plant invasions stands out:
1106 how to build mutually beneficial partnerships between stakeholders. Questionnaires and
1107 surveys, however, will not be sufficient to answer this question, but engagement tools to build
1108 mutual collaboration and understanding, including participatory methods, likely have this
1109 potential (IDS, n.d.; Powell et al., 2022; Shackleton, Adriaens et al., 2019; Vaz et al., 2022).

1110 [2.5 Methods to study the human dimensions of biological invasions](#)

1111 Research focuses on the human dimensions of biological invasions has increased, as well as
1112 the inter- and transdisciplinarity within invasion science, based on reviews of scientific
1113 literature in English in the ISI Web of Science, Scopus, and Google Scholar (Kapitza et al.,
1114 2019; Shackleton, Adriaens et al., 2019; Stevenson et al., 2023; Vaz et al., 2022). However,
1115 there is still much to be done since collaborations are often confined to sub-fields of ecology
1116 and environmental sciences, with collaborations with humanities and truly integrative socio-
1117 ecological studies challenging to find through the quantitative literature searches that the
1118 previously mentioned authors performed. The biases discussed earlier in section 2 of the
1119 present review influence this since the Western scientific system limits the possibilities for co-
1120 creation and long-term collaborations that could lead to a more holistic understanding of
1121 biological invasions and their human dimensions. In addition, distinct philosophical paradigms
1122 and methodological approaches within and across environmental sciences and humanities
1123 impede the integration of these fields to study biological invasions and, especially, their human
1124 dimensions.

1125 Positivism (or empirical realism) and post-positivism later became the hegemonic
1126 philosophical paradigms in science and, for the interest of this review, invasion of science.

1127 Hence, human dimensions in invasion science have usually been explored through quantitative
1128 surveys or the occasional mixed-method approaches, but with quantitative and post-positivist
1129 outlooks (Kapitza et al., 2019; Shackleton, Adriaens, et al., 2019). For instance, Kapitza et al.
1130 (2019) searched for research on social perceptions of invasive species, while Shackleton,
1131 Adriaens et al. (2019) addressed the status of stakeholder engagement in invasion science.
1132 Although these authors do not specify philosophical paradigms used in the reviewed papers—
1133 likely because this information is not stated in the papers, usually implying that the
1134 philosophical paradigm is post-positivism—they quantified the methods used in the papers,
1135 showing that over 50% of the papers used questionnaires (Kapitza et al., 2019; Shackleton,
1136 Adriaens et al., 2019). A lesser number (35% in Kapitza et al. 2019 and 20% in Shackleton,
1137 Adriaens et al., 2019) had mixed different methods. Kapitza et al. (2019) did not specify these
1138 methods. In contrast, Shackleton, Adriaens et al. (2019) referred to them as including more
1139 consultative, deliberative, and co-productive methods like focus groups, workshops, and key-
1140 informant interviews. Both reviews show that a minority of the papers (less than 20%) used
1141 "more integrative and social science type approaches" as per Shackleton, Adriaens et al. (2019)'
1142 words, which I would translate as more qualitative approaches to methods (e.g., observations,
1143 participatory mapping), and perhaps, non-positivist philosophies. Lately and by no means
1144 exempt from the biases discussed in section 2 (Conservation Culturomics, n.d.), conservation
1145 culturomics has emerged as another quantitative and post-positivist set of tools to study human
1146 behaviour and cultural trends in the context of human-nature interactions, with a few studies
1147 focused on the human dimensions of biological invasions (Henke et al., 2024; Novoa et al.,
1148 2024).

1149 Interestingly, according to Kapitza et al. (2019), when considering the studies on human
1150 perceptions of biological invasions conducted in Africa, interdisciplinary and mixed-methods
1151 approaches were more likely compared to North America, Europe, Asia, Oceania, and South
1152 America. In fact, of the eight papers from South Africa, seven followed an interdisciplinary
1153 approach (de Neergaard et al., 2005; Hertling & Luke, 1999; Shackleton & Gambiza, 2008;
1154 Tannent et al., 2010; Kull et al., 2011; Shackleton et al., 2011; Shackleton et al., 2015) and
1155 only one fit into a purely social science approach (Preston & Siegfried, 1995). All of them
1156 generated quantitative and qualitative data. However, they followed a quantitative approach to
1157 analysis overall, except for one that only collected qualitative data and used a qualitative
1158 perspective to analysis (Kull et al., 2011). Most papers mixed ecological surveys with either
1159 interviews and/or email-based questionnaires. Two papers used semi-structured interviews (de

1160 Neergaard et al., 2005; Shackleton et al., 2015). One (Hertling & Luke, 1999) used a similar
 1161 approach to ethnography to generate preliminary data to guide subsequent interviews and data
 1162 interpretation.

1163 Adding to these reviews, in order to uncover more of the methods used (and likely
 1164 philosophical approaches) for topical studies across Southern Africa and elsewhere, I have
 1165 reviewed additional literature published between November 2020 and the second half of 2024,
 1166 including various online databases and hegemonic academic publishers (Table 2.2). I started
 1167 in November 2020 with a search on Scopus [TITLE-ABS-KEY ((soci* W/2 research) AND
 1168 (invasive W/2 plant)) AND (LIMIT-TO (SUBJAREA , "ENVI") OR LIMIT TO
 1169 (SUBJAREA , "SOCI"); TITLE-ABS-KEY ((soci* W/2 research) AND "invasion science")]
 1170 for each country belonging to the Southern African Development Community (SADC).
 1171 Subsequently, I utilised the references of each article and looked for further relevant
 1172 publications on each of the different SADC countries. Furthermore, I conducted a similar but
 1173 simpler search on the Scielo database and Google in English, French, and Portuguese, looking
 1174 for the following terms: plants, perceptions, invasive, and exotic/alien. In addition, I searched
 1175 for the same terms on publicly available databases from the different SADC countries, accessed
 1176 through the African Digital Research Repositories hosted by SOAS University of London
 1177 (SOAS University of London, n.d.).

1178 **Table 2.2: Methods used in publicly available (online) research addressing the human**
 1179 **dimensions of plant invasions in countries of Southern Africa (search from November**
 1180 **2020 to the second semester of 2024).**

Methods	Title	Authors
face-to-face surveys, focus groups	Perceptions of <i>Prosopis glandulosa</i> and management options in rural communities in South Kalahari in Botswana	Mosweu et al. (2013)
archival analysis	History of introduction, spread and management of aquatic weeds	Kurugundla et al. (2016)
surveys	Perceptions of <i>Rosa rubiginosa</i> and its contribution to rural communities in northern Lesotho	Makhorole (2021)
semi-structured face-to-face surveys, key informant interviews, focus groups	Social effects of <i>Prosopis glandulosa</i> in Malawi	Chikuni et al. (2004)

face-to-face surveys and focus groups	Knowledge and perceptions of weed management in Tanzania	Laizer et al. (2019)
face-to-face surveys and literature review	Understanding of <i>Parthenium hysterophorus</i> in Tanzania	Musese et al. (2020)
face-to-face questionnaires	Effects of <i>Tithonia diversifolia</i> on rural livelihoods in Zambia	Witt et al. (2019)
community mapping exercises, time series analysis and key informant interviews	Social-ecological impacts of <i>Vernonanthura polyanthes</i> in the Eastern Highlands of Zimbabwe	Kachena & Shackleton (2024)

1181

1182 Additionally, I paid attention to resources in conferences where my colleagues or I participated
1183 (e.g., the South African National Symposium on Biological Invasions in July 2021 and July
1184 2022; the European Conference of African Studies in May 2023; International Conference on
1185 Ecology and Management of Alien Plant Invasions in October 2023; British Ecological Society
1186 Conference in December 2023; POLLEN Network Conference in June 2024; the World
1187 Congress of Environmental History in August 2024). Finally, I kept track of relevant
1188 manuscripts from known authors on Research Gate and LinkedIn social media. This approach
1189 has benefited me in terms of my up-to-date understanding of currently utilised methodological
1190 approaches and the latest findings on ornamental plant invasions in Southern Africa.

1191 Research into the perceptions of invasive plants in Southern Africa has used diverse methods,
1192 usually corresponding to a qualitative or a mixed quantitative-qualitative approach to data
1193 generation and interpretation (Table 2.2). It would be challenging to pinpoint the philosophical
1194 paradigms these studies reflect, but many appear to reflect perspectives between post-
1195 positivism and constructivism. However, my reflections are not intended to focus on
1196 philosophical paradigms but to emphasise the importance of qualitative approaches in this area
1197 of research (since doing the former would be outside my area of expertise as a researcher with
1198 post-positivist (and positivist) and quantitative training in natural sciences, who has only started
1199 exploring non-positivist and qualitative approaches with an inter-disciplinary lens during this
1200 PhD research).

1201 Qualitative approaches (as well as non-positivist philosophical paradigms) to research are
1202 helpful when exploring ‘new’ phenomena or understanding complex processes, such as the
1203 human dimensions of biological invasions. The papers using qualitative approaches to data

1204 generation and interpretation that previous reviews and mine have collated are examples of
1205 these uses. For instance, Mosweu et al. (2013) and Kachena & Shackleton (2024) took a
1206 qualitative and participatory approach to data collection and interpretation to be able to provide
1207 a detailed and nuanced documentation of human-plant interactions, which are highly complex.
1208 On the one hand, Mosweu et al. (2013) gave management recommendations for the specific
1209 community where the research occurred. On the other, Kachena & Shackleton (2024) described
1210 the situation with an emergent invasive plant whose invasion pathways, trajectories, and
1211 impacts had not been documented before, shedding light on potential avenues for effective and
1212 ethical management practices. Experienced researchers with a qualitative research background
1213 could criticise these papers and other examples I will introduce in the following paragraphs
1214 regarding methodological and philosophical congruence and transparency (e.g., Braun &
1215 Clarke, 2024). However, that is neither my expertise nor my intention here.

1216 Likewise, other works beyond Southern Africa have used qualitative approaches with similar
1217 endeavours. Selgue (2011) and Schuttler et al. (2011) interpreted the societal discourses on
1218 invasive species and their management in Scotland and Chile, documenting how the
1219 stakeholders involved in their research make sense of and feel about certain invasive species
1220 and, hence informing socially appropriate approaches to management. Uusilato et al. (2024)
1221 integrated the interpretation of contemporary literature and media content along with linguistics
1222 and palaeoecological analyses into a qualitative multidisciplinary approach grounded in
1223 political ecology to critically document the dynamics of perceptions of two garden plants in
1224 Finland. Erazo et al. (2024) used a mixed approach consisting of a stakeholder mapping process
1225 to identify stakeholders and design engagement strategies for six case studies across Argentina,
1226 Chile, and Brazil. Lastly, it is noteworthy to recognise the use of archival research for
1227 comprehending and contextualising human-invasive species relations in time and space. Luat-
1228 Hū'eu et al. (2021) used a primarily qualitative approach to archival research of the Hawaiian
1229 language to understand the co-evolving relationships between Hawaiians and feral pigs, and
1230 hence, contribute to balance the pig controlling measures with the State of Hawai'i's obligation
1231 to support Indigenous practices and public hunting.

1232 Calls from within invasion science, political ecology, and environmental humanities discuss
1233 integrating different knowledge systems and approaches that allow for a more holistic and
1234 ethical vision of biological invasions, especially their human dimensions. Qualitative and non-
1235 positivist approaches to research allow such integrations and for the much-needed co-creation
1236 and collaboration in invasive species management. Embracing these paradigms, although not

1237 exempt from challenges given the systemic, societal, and political obstacles, is fundamental for
1238 the long-term benefit of nature and for people as part of it (Crowley et al., 2017; Haubrock et
1239 al., 2024; Haubrock et al., 2025; Powell et al., 2022).

3. Methodology and philosophy of my research

In this chapter, I justify my approach to data generation and interpretation and the philosophy underpinning it. I highlight the novelty and pertinence of my approach to effectively address my research questions and objectives—while also considering my positionality and the context in which the research took place. Subsequently, I describe the data generation, analysis, and interpretation processes and methods that will enable the transparency of my research. I also include a graphic illustration of my analytical and interpretative approaches. Finally, I reflect on my positionality and the context that influenced my research practice.

3.1 Reflections on my research philosophical paradigm

(Post)-positivism dominates science, so the focus area for this thesis is invasion science. When approaching the human dimensions of biological invasions, this philosophical paradigm has fundamental problems that hamper the holistic understanding and interpretation. For example, the fact that this paradigm claims the existence of a single reality and, hence, the absolutism of knowledge until proven wrong contradicts the idea that humans co-construct their realities and their knowledges about them, meaning that multiple, socially-constructed realities exist, shaped by multiple and (hierarchically) interrelated factors (Bhaskar, 1975; Hennink et al., 2020; Sullivan, 2019). Furthermore, (post)-positivism does not allow for a layered reality where mechanisms of action could be in a domain that the empirical cannot measure or perceive (Price, 2019). In that sense, Price (2015) exemplifies the existence of layered domains of reality in the case of climate change (Figure 2.1 in Price, 2015), using critical realism as a philosophical framework (Bhaskar, 1975). This notion of a layered reality that can go beyond the empirical helps to unpack why it can be difficult for people (and amongst them, scientists) to acknowledge (and empirically predict) phenomena like anthropogenic climate change (Price, 2019).

Non-positivist philosophies, moreover, allow the consideration of the subjectivities that researchers imprint in all the stages of the research process, accounting for reflexivity on their role in the research process and the insights generated, both on their relationships with the objects/subjects of study and on their positionality (Braun & Clarke, 2023a; Braun & Clarke, 2024; Gani & Khan, 2024; Hennink et al., 2020; Price & Lotz-Sistka, 2015; Sullivan, 2019; Varpio et al., 2017; 2021). Criticisms from (post)positivist stand mainly target the acknowledgment of subjectivity and the existence of a reality beyond the empirical, as well as the use of nuanced (and subjective) interpretations to understand and explain phenomena

instead of objectively seeking the ultimate truth about a single reality. However, in these highly criticised elements (i.e., in nuanced and subjective interpretations), I have found a strong basis for developing my research practice by my objectives.

Returning to my specific focus, the human dimensions of biological invasions, I find the notions of layered domains of reality of critical realism helpful in approaching the ‘humanness’ of biological invasions. Drawing from the critical realist reflections and examples I have read (Bhaskar, 1975; Price & Lotz-Sistka, 2015; Price, 2019), I sketch what I consider the layered domains of reality in the case of biological invasions (Figure 3.1). Critical realism constitutes a framework upon which I develop my research practice, realising that:

- 1) mechanisms can exist in a domain that is hard to access from the empirical alone;
- 2) knowledges of realities are socially constructed and, hence, subjective and ever-changing; and
- 3) my research practice is also socially constructed and ever-changing, given that it is an intellectual and socioeconomic activity and livelihood subjected to power relations, cultural perceptions, social interactions, and political consequences (Bhaskar, 1975; Braun & Clarke, 2024; Price, 2015; Rogers et al., 2013; Toomey et al., 2017).

These premises, then, lead me to a reflexive combination of inductive, deductive, and retroductive reasoning to attempt to explain the humanness of biological invasions.

Figure 3.1: The real, actual, and empirical of biological invasions. Based on my understanding of critical realist reflections in Bhaskar (1975), Price & Lotz-Sistka (2015) and Price (2019). In this case, impact is any effect that can be measured and/or perceived.

I am using notions of critical realism and constructivism (Bhaskar, 1975; Braun & Clarke, 2022; Hennink et al., 2020; Price, 2015; Price, 2019; Sullivan, 2019) to:

- Understand the complexity and nuances of people’s perceptions, opinions, attitudes, and behaviours around alien and invasive plants, interpreting the meanings people give to these plants in Southern Africa.
- Interpret the social, cultural, economic, and ecological contexts in which human-plant interactions occur, understanding how the ornamental sector operates and its links to alien and invasive plants in Southern Africa.

The above-mentioned intentions link back to the objectives of this thesis, which is to examine the role of the ornamental sector in plant invasions across the sub-region.

My epistemological and methodological approach under a critical realist framework is experiential qualitative, where I see language as a reflection of people’s experiences and perspectives (Braun & Clarke, 2022). Although deemed as epistemologically closer to positivism and, hence, more conservative (see a brief but enlightening introductory discussion about this in Braun & Clarke, 2024), I believe it gave me a more open and flexible mindset to explore a topic where epistemic conflicts can frequently arise because realities depend on factors that can go beyond our senses. Coming from a (post)positivist education and training and navigating a field where that is the norm, I see myself softly (and cautiously) entering the necessary messiness of qualitative and non-positivist research. It seems necessary, though, to respond to the environmental challenges with the flexibility, nuance, and epistemic justice these require.

3.2 Reflections on becoming a “knowing researcher” and “owning my perspective” in qualitative research

These four years of PhD research have been teaching me how to become what Virginia (Ginny) Braun and Victoria Clarke call a “knowing researcher” in qualitative research, one that “owns their perspective” (Braun & Clarke, 2023a,b; Braun & Clarke, 2024). I did not know these metaphors before, but I believe the ever-evolving processes that these two scholars in health

psychology capture in their explanations of what becoming a knowing researcher is capture what I have been experiencing.

My training in (post)positivism and the training of the entire academic world surrounding me challenge my capacity to make my research practice understandable to others and myself. We (academics in the Western sense of it) are deeply rooted in a (post)positivist Aristotelian/Cartesian way of being and thinking. These perspectives are reflected in the philosophical incoherencies—where the positivist stances come out—that even academics doing non-positivist qualitative research have when carrying out their research practice and publishing in academic journals (Braun & Clarke, 2023a;b; Varpio et al., 2017; 2021). After reading several books and papers on the matter, having finished my project, and constantly reflecting on it, I feel that I am currently standing in the middle of the spectrum between the (post)positivist non-reflexive and conservative ‘small q’ and the non-positivist reflexive and radical ‘Big Q’ of qualitative research (Braun & Clarke, 2024).

The “positivism creep,” as Braun & Clarke (2023a) eloquently put it when referring to how to carry out a conscious thematic analysis, came out many times during my research practice. It reflects how I try to fit a qualitative approach into a positivist box of generalisation and objectivity. I mixed methods because I thought the research was going to be more robust and “realistic” if I quantified the number of participants saying this or the other and if I put effort into showing the demographics that could validate my subjective interpretations of the data I generated (the creep coming out). I lamented that the sample was too small and circumscribed to certain places, hampering the most wanted token in science, generalisation (the creep coming out, again). I used terms (e.g., triangulation) in a proceduralist way, not reflecting on the implications such specific terms have in qualitative research (Varpio et al., 2017; Braun & Clarke, 2023a). In addition, my thematic analysis (TA) turned out to be a mix of coding reliability TA and reflexive TA typology (Braun & Clarke, 2022; Braun & Clarke, 2023a), reflecting my epistemological tendencies to (post)positivism.

My relations with supervisors, journal reviewers, and thesis examiners have helped me learn what I want and do not want my research to be. In the process, I have gone in and out of a philosophical neglect to avoid more problems. For example, claiming that I acknowledge subjectivity without saying what philosophical framework underpins my research practice—perhaps because of the fear of falling into philosophical incoherencies—, claiming that I was doing thematic analysis without anchoring it to a theoretical framework or writing my

positionality without connecting it properly to my research practice. These issues, nonetheless, are widely shared in qualitative research (Braun & Clarke, 2023a; Braun & Clarke, 2024). I have tried to stick to the philosophical premises I chose early in 2021 when I became more aware of the need for a change in philosophical paradigms. In the following subsections, I explain my methodological approach, which I believe corresponds to the experiential qualitative research I conducted with a critical realist lens. “Knowing researchers” who “own their perspectives” can judge it. I will always be open to constructive and mindful criticism for evolution.

3.3 Reflections on the methodological approach

Patchwork ethnography is the methodological umbrella I chose, or perhaps I should say the one that fits my methodological approach under the philosophical framework I stated before (Günel et al., 2020; Günel et al., 2023; Günel & Watanabe, 2024). This approach enables researchers to 'patch' together seams of data (or the moments where you generate them) when complete immersion and dedication to the so-called 'fieldwork' is unrealistic while giving room for inclusivity, empathy, consideration, and flexibility in the research practice (Günel et al., 2020; Günel et al., 2023; Günel & Watanabe, 2024). These premises make the research process more ethical and resilient. Patchwork ethnography considers the researcher's circumstances, accounting for the neoliberal conditions, environmental concerns, and women (and queer) 's and neo-colonial contexts where academic research, and especially PhD research funded by globally hegemonic countries and corporations, are taking place (Günel et al., 2020; Günel & Watanabe, 2024). My circumstances, principles, history (or positionality), the restrictions relating to the Covid-19 pandemic, and the focus of this research led to this realisation and decision.

Like me, other women researchers have applied this approach during the COVID-19 pandemic, where the possibility of doing long, immersive, and interactive fieldwork was prohibited. Meneses (2023) used it to continue her research on the role of ordinary women in the context of the nationalist struggle in Mozambique during the 1960s and 1970s. Burnett (2023a;b) applied it to her PhD research on communities' resilience and agro-food systems in Germany and the UK. Di Matteo & Daminelli (2024) used it to investigate migrant support volunteer tourism facing multiple crises in Lesbos (Greek island), the COVID-19 pandemic amongst them. Apart from the impossibility of close human contact, the COVID-19 pandemic made the chronicity of the inequalities, oppressions, and crises derived from the capitalist global order

even more visible (Tippet, 2020; Wallace et al., 2020). Patchwork ethnography rescues academic researchers, especially those in vulnerable positions like me, because of the synergy of their nationalities, labour and financial statuses, genders, cultural identities, and skin colors.

In contrast to quantitative and qualitative methods under a (post)positivist paradigm, my choice enabled me to acknowledge the interactive and co-constructive nature of research with human participants, not denying our humanness and accounting for the interrelation between contexts and our lives, going beyond only facts and supposedly causal correlations. Although I based my research design on previous literature and a conceptual framework developed by Shackleton et al. (2019), I started my study with no assumptions or pre-conceptions of my result, given that I knew very little about the topic and the geographical space. Patchwork ethnography (Swettenham & Langley-Evans, 2024) and other critical approaches to the 'scientific method' in ecology (Feinsinger, 2014; Price, 2019) allow for such a "naïve" 'kickstart. Hence, I used deductive, inductive, and retroductive approaches to design, generation, and interpretation (Braun & Clarke, 2022; Sullivan & Forrester, 2019; Hennink et al., 2020). The design and generation of data were governed by deductive and retroductive reasoning, whereas inductive reasoning governed the analysis. For my interpretation, I used a combination of deductive and retroductive reasoning.

In addition, the combination of methods enabled me to account for how my positionality was perceived in Southern Africa. As I was seen as a white (sometimes coloured or mixed) foreign woman, hence, affluent and an outsider to most Southern African people's eyes, I learnt Setswana, one of the official languages of the country where I stayed the longest (Botswana). When I was speaking Setswana, people from the ethnic majorities did not perceive me as much as a white tourist (likely British) anymore but as an individual making an effort to speak in a local language⁴ (mother tongue for some or familiar language for others). My efforts were nicely welcomed and highly appreciated, especially since these are not common amongst foreigners living in the country. Thus, speaking in Setswana was the "golden gate" for interacting with participants and people in Botswana, especially (and to an extent in Namibia

⁴ Setswana is hegemonic in Botswana, where ethnicities like Kalanga and the nomadic indigenous people have been oppressed, hence, their languages as well. Therefore, I am not romanticising Setswana as a local language. I acknowledge that the sub-region and Botswana have many more languages. I could only learn Setswana, as the vast majority of the country speaks it (as a national language), and my time was limited. English is the official language being part of the persistent colonial legacy in the country (<https://www.gov.bw/about-our-country>).

and Zimbabwe). They were more open to talking to me, slightly balancing the power relations and perceptions towards me. On the other hand, minorities (e.g., expats, European descendants, and Indian descendants) perceived me as one of them or alike. Thus, they would be open to speaking to me as a similar, using English as the language of communication.

The fact that I am a 'mixed-race' Caribbean with both European and African heritage gave me the ability to blend in between these groups better as I did not fit in precisely with any of them, but I would have similarities with both. For instance, Afro-Cuban dance and music are central to my existence; thus, I would feel and dance to black Southern African music "very well," according to black and brown Southern Africans. My passion for dance gave me an aura of familiarity that perhaps most black Southern Africans could not understand well. However, it was enough to grant me empathy and a sense of being similar, if not equal. For the other groups like European white/coloured descendants or Indian descendants or expats, I was similar because I am not a black African; I was from another country, and I have lived in Britain, which is the former colonial power of a vast part of the sub-region. Hence, I was somehow connected to their British (or European) ancestry, influence, and/or identity. Being a woman also contributed to my smooth insertion in gardening circles, as most of the gardening community is female.

Of course, being a non-black woman foreigner posed a challenge to my safety. I experienced harassment, but most of it was not enough to threaten my integrity. As a lone perceivably white woman, men sexually harassed me often because white is "prime meat here," as a close Kalanga friend explained to me once. Generally, this comes from the perception of me being affluent and capable of having connections abroad (as in Europe or North America) to take them out of their countries for "greener pastures." Also, it has a colonial component whereby white is better, which did not take me by surprise. I come from the Caribbean, where sexual harassment is a daily reality and battle, and being white is perceived as being superior.

Both in the Caribbean and Southern Africa, there is a historical and geopolitical assumption that white foreigners are more affluent, having the potential to take locals out of poverty, usually through marriage. I protected myself by, firstly, diving into the day-to-day life in Botswana, learning their history from any possible space (i.e., academic books, conferences, dialogues with people from different backgrounds and ages in the sub-region), learning the national language, making friends and training martial arts in Gaborone. However, I felt safe most of the time. For example, I travelled by foot and public transport and hitchhiked within

and between countries. Although deemed as dangerous for some people because of the assumption of who I was and how people would view and interact with me, it was the best way to experience the realities of the places out of the privileged and touristic bubbles (which, nonetheless, I also experienced because they are part of the reality as well).

I prioritised respect, cultural sensitivity, and safety in my interactions. I balanced my research practice to get as much social interaction as possible while keeping my safety and being respectful. For instance, even though I am not Christian, I participated in the morning Christian prayers when I was in spaces where these were usual practices. My upbringing was secular, but I was surrounded by religious practices, both Christian and Santería (from Yoruba religion). Besides, I have lived in multicultural and multi-religious British cities (Aberdeen and Coventry). Hence, I am comfortable with religious practices.

This thesis conveys and interprets the views, opinions, and insights from 191 people: 81 environmental specialists, 38 ornamental industry staff, and 72 ornamental gardeners or non-commercial users. Of these, 104 were from Botswana, 50 from Namibia, 18 from Zimbabwe, 13 from South Africa, 3 from Zambia, 2 from the Democratic Republic of the Congo, and 1 from Eswatini. I visited and interacted with people in 67 ornamental-related establishments, comprising formalised private businesses, informal businesses, governmental institutions, and non-governmental projects/initiatives across Botswana, Namibia, and Zimbabwe (Appendix 2). Given the different roles of stakeholders and places they occupied and could reach out to, I utilised slightly different approaches to engage with the three groups of stakeholders. Therefore, in the following paragraphs, I provide a detailed, separate account of the sampling strategies and methods used for each group of stakeholders.

Environmental specialists

For environmental specialists, semi-structured interviews, informal conversations, and two workshops were used (Table 3.1). Initially, potential participants were identified through a review of subject-relevant academic publications, project reports, online databases, and participant lists from relevant regional events. Exploratory online/email conversations with relevant professionals in Namibia, Botswana, and South Africa helped identify further contacts among their professional networks. From August 2021, potential participants were contacted through email to hold online semi-structured interviews, with the rationale of the project provided in a participant information sheet and an informed consent form to be signed before the start of each interview. Subsequently, more participants were recruited following a

snowballing approach whereby interviewed (or otherwise contacted) participants would be asked to recommend other potential participants.

Table 3.1: Sample of environmental specialists by country, occupation, and method of interaction. In occupation, ‘researcher’ refers to researchers based in non-academic institutions like non-governmental organisations, protected areas, private businesses, etc.

ID	Country	Occupation	Method of interaction
1	South Africa	manager, researcher, practitioner	online semi-structured interview
5	South Africa	manager, practitioner	online semi-structured interview
6	South Africa	academic researcher	workshop (face-to-face)
10	Zambia	academic researcher	online semi-structured interview
11	Zimbabwe	academic researcher	online informal conversation
12	Botswana	academic researcher	online semi-structured interview
13	Zambia	academic researcher	online semi-structured interview
15	South Africa	manager, researcher, practitioner	online semi-structured interview
17	Namibia	Researcher	online semi-structured interview
18	Democratic Republic of the Congo	academic researcher	informal conversation through email
19	Democratic Republic of the Congo	academic researcher	online informal conversation
21	Namibia	academic researcher	online semi-structured interview
26	Zambia	manager, practitioner	online semi-structured interview
29	Zimbabwe	activist, practitioner	online semi-structured interview
30	Botswana	academic researcher	online semi-structured interview
31	Eswatini	academic researcher	informal conversation through email
32	Zimbabwe	manager, researcher, practitioner	online semi-structured interview
34	South Africa	academic researcher	workshop (face-to-face)
35	South Africa	academic researcher	workshop (face-to-face)
36	South Africa	academic researcher	workshop (face-to-face)
37	South Africa	postgraduate researcher	workshop (face-to-face)
38	South Africa	academic researcher	workshop (face-to-face)
39	South Africa	postgraduate researcher	workshop (face-to-face)
40	South Africa	postgraduate researcher	workshop (online)
41	South Africa	postgraduate researcher	workshop (online)
42	South Africa	postgraduate researcher	workshop (online)
43	Botswana	researcher	face-to-face informal conversation
44	Botswana	manager, practitioner	face-to-face informal conversation
45	Zimbabwe	researcher	informal conversation through email

46	Botswana	governmental manager	officer,	face to face informal conversation
47	Botswana	manager		face to face informal conversation
48-52	Botswana	governmental managers	officers,	face to face informal conversation through a meeting
53-94	Botswana	governmental managers	officers,	open fora workshop

I initially contacted via email 33 potential participants from across the continental members of SADC (Angola, Mozambique, Tanzania, Democratic Republic of Congo, Zambia, Zimbabwe, Namibia, Botswana, Eswatini, Lesotho and South Africa). Of these, I could interview 13 (approximately 39%) from the six countries Democratic Republic of Congo, Zambia, Zimbabwe, Namibia, Botswana, and South Africa. Another two from this initial recruitment process interacted with the primary author in a later workshop in South Africa (ID 6) and during the online informal conversation (ID 11). Initially, participants ID 43–94 were not recruited for online interviews, but I identified them through my ongoing ‘snowballing’ process and then interacted with them while in Southern Africa (Table 3.1).

Semi-structured interviews

I designed a guide for approximately one-hour-long semi-structured interviews (Appendix 3) that was tested through two pilot interviews with two environmental specialists—participants of the virtual South African National Symposium on Biological Invasions-May 2021—before the start of interactions with participants. The guide roughly referred to the following aspects: the influence of the ornamental sector on spreading alien plants across the sub-region; the stage of the research, management, control, and prevention of invasive ornamental plants in the sub-region; perceptions of alien and invasive ornamental plants amongst people; and actions needed to tackle plant invasions derived from the ornamental sector more effectively. However, the interviews flowed differently each time, depending on the interactions between the participants and me. They were free to focus on other related aspects of their experiences. Most were held on Zoom, ranging from 45 minutes to one hour. Two of them were held on WhatsApp, resembling a chat where voice notes and text were used at the participant’s own pace, meaning they could continue our asynchronous dialogue whenever they had the chance. This approach was a pragmatic adaptation because these participants were willing to participate but could not do so in a classical interview format. One had too poor internet capacity to hold a Zoom meeting, whereas the other did not have time for it.

Workshop

I designed and co-facilitated (with my Director of Studies) a workshop for a group meeting at the Centre for Invasion Biology, Stellenbosch University, South Africa, in May 2022. I started by giving the project's rationale in a PowerPoint presentation. I used a version of the perception exercise "Past, present and future" (see Salas et al., 2010) to identify the participants' perceptions of the role of the ornamental horticulture sector in plant invasions in South Africa (Appendix 3). The participants took part online and face-to-face (Table 3.1) and were asked to make notes of their responses and stick them to flip charts that I had already created with mind maps of codes from previous interviews (Figure 3.2a). After the discussion, the flip charts were revealed for participants to place notes, collectively sorting their thoughts into pre-existing or new main themes (Figures 3.2b-d).

Informal conversations

These included email exchanges and face-to-face and online conversations. For example, I categorised informal conversations as interactions with participants who did not formally agree to be interviewed but shared relevant information through emails. I also held face-to-face and online meetings that happened spontaneously.

Ornamental industry staff and ornamental gardeners or non-commercial end users

I used questionnaires, participant observations, semi-structured interviews, and plant surveys for the people working within the ornamental horticulture sector and those buying/using plants for non-commercial reasons. During the project's scoping phase, before data generation started officially, I searched for potential participants within the sector on Google Maps and social media groups. Later, some environmental specialists I interviewed pointed me toward potential participants within the Botswana, Zimbabwe, and Namibia sectors. Regarding the public, the time spent in Southern Africa allowed me to build relationships, find spaces to distribute the questionnaire to the public, and informally interact and engage with people about the topic.

In June 2022, I arrived in Botswana after having established an agreement with the Department of Soil and Crop Science from the Botswana University of Agriculture and Natural Resources and being granted a research permit by the Ministry of Environment, Natural Resources, Conservation and Tourism from Botswana [ENT 8/36/4 LII (38)]. Two academics from this university whom I had previously interviewed online became my local PhD advisors. They identified potential participants in Gaborone, Francistown, Selebi-Phikwe, and Maun. Additionally, as I lived in Botswana for ten months, the recruitment combined snowballing among participants, friends, and neighbours and searched in the street and classified advertisement magazines. One participant pointed me toward the directory of the gardening magazine "SC Gardens Botswana." Another permitted me to post online surveys for professionals in the sector and members of the public (non-commercial users) on the Gabs Gardeners Facebook group (Gabs Gardener, 2022).

Given the ubiquitous and normalised nature of using mobile phones and WhatsApp among people in Southern Africa, including those from diverse backgrounds, I primarily used this app to contact participants. The circumstances allowed me to have semi-structured interviews, questionnaires in online and paper form, informal conversations, extensive observations, and experiences with multiple stakeholders related to the sector. For the non-commercial users, I also advertised the online survey in WhatsApp groups and through my friends' and participants'

WhatsApp statuses and other social media. Facebook posts and stories and WhatsApp statuses are common social platforms in Botswana across all ages. I also used the one-week courses on Floriculture and Flower Arrangement and Landscaping that the Botswana University of Agriculture and Natural Resources offers to the public to advertise the online and paper-based versions of the questionnaire. Additionally, I contributed to the SC Gardens Botswana Magazine with a short article where I advertised the survey to the public (Rodríguez-Cala et al., 2023).

In Zimbabwe, recruitment and interactions occur differently. One of the Zimbabwean specialists I interviewed online invited me to attend the 2022 edition of the Annual Garden Show in Harare, which she co-organises. In September 2022, I spent 13 days in Harare, attending the garden show and experiencing the sector beyond the show. This key contact introduced me to several businesses participating in the show, some of whom I interviewed during the show, visited their business sites, and with whom I had informal conversations. I advertised the online questionnaire to the public on the show through leaflets. My host in Harare advertised the online survey for the public amongst her contacts.

I also visited several neighbourhoods in Harare (Highlands, Borrowdale, Chisipite, Greendale, Cranbone, and Mount Pleasant) and interacted with people in ornamental-related sites. All of those neighbourhoods are considered low-density wealthy suburbs. I made those visits alone by public transport, on foot, and/or by lift. Based on the advice of interviewees from Zimbabwe, Zimbabwean friends in Botswana, and my host in Harare, I did not visit less-wealthy medium to high-density neighbourhoods as a foreigner travelling alone. Through my interactions within and beyond the show and a contact list of businesses from Zimbabwe the show's co-organiser had shared with me previously, I sent a link to the online questionnaire for the sector through WhatsApp and email to those with whom I could not converse. In addition, I posted the link to the online questionnaires for the sector and the non-commercial users on the Zimbabwe Gardening and Plant Lovers Facebook group (Zimbabwe Gardening and Plant Lovers, 2022). In addition, I contributed to the Zimbabwean Gardener Magazine with a short article where I advertised the survey for non-commercial users (Rodríguez-Cala, 2023).

Interactions with participants in Namibia occurred in April-May 2023. A Namibian key informant I had interviewed put me in contact with the Department of Natural Resource Management at the Namibian University of Science and Technology (NUST) and the executive board of the Botanical Society of Namibia. I was invited to give a guest lecture to the Honours

degree (Hons) students of Natural Resources Management and a talk to members of the Botanical Society of Namibia within its "Illustrated Talks" program (Figure 3.3). Both opportunities were used to collect data. I distributed paper-based questionnaires to the Hons students' families and relatives. The talk for the Botanical Society of Namibia was designed as a form of focus group. Key informants and collaborators from the Botanical Society of Namibia helped contact potential participants and visit establishments around Windhoek and further North in Okahandja. Site visits were complemented with informal conversations and observations. Business directories were used to reach out to businesses through WhatsApp and email with the link to the online version of the questionnaire.

Figure 3.3: Networking opportunities in Namibia were used to recruit participants and collect data. (a), Talk to the Hons students of Natural Resource Management at the

Namibian University of Science and Technology. (b), Focus groups with members of the Botanical Society of Namibia. Photo a Tendai Nzuma; photo b Diana Rodríguez Cala.

Questionnaire (online and paper forms)

Two questionnaires were designed for those working in the sector (Appendix 5a-c) and the public (Appendix 6a-c). The questionnaire for professionals in the ornamental horticulture sector was co-designed with one of the environmental specialists from Zimbabwe, who co-organises the Annual Garden Show in Harare. After consulting with other researchers and testing the questions, I made three versions of the two questionnaires for each of the three countries to account for the differences in administrative organisations and others (Appendix 5a-c and 6a-c). For example, in Botswana, where people residing in the capital usually have a second house in their home village, the questionnaire for the public specified that respondents could choose the house they preferred to talk about if they did not have time to fill out the questionnaire twice. Furthermore, a Botswanan friend with experience in Setswana-English translation translated the questionnaire to Setswana for distribution in Botswana. Respondents were invited to respond in Setswana if preferred. I translated their responses myself.

The questionnaire for the sector had three sections (Appendix 5a-c). The first asked about businesses' structure and customer base. The second asked about the factors influencing the businesses' operation, the most popular plants, the supply chain, and waste management. The third section covered the understandings of the biogeographical origin, behaviour, and impact of plants within and beyond the business. Likewise, the questionnaire for the public had three sections (Appendix 6a-c). In the first section, people were asked to describe their spaces, what their favourite plants are and why, where they source their plants from, and how they maintain their spaces with plants. The second section focused on people's criteria for choosing plants for their spaces. The third section focused on how people understand plants' origins, behaviour, and impact within and beyond their spaces.

Semi-structured interviews

These followed the broad topics from the questionnaire's sections: business operation, customer base, factors influencing its operation, popular plants, supply chain, waste management, and their understanding of plants' behaviour and impact. However, given its semi-structured nature, the conversation flowed depending on the interaction between participants and me.

Informal conversations coupled with participant observations

These occurred when visiting ornamental-related sites and my daily life in the three countries. I often engaged with people in 'small talks' related to the topic of interest (e.g., plants people talked about). I took diary notes of all these interactions. I also kept WhatsApp, email exchanges, and small talk records. Some of these interactions guided me to websites and online media, which people I interacted with relate to when talking about invasive plants (e.g., iNaturalist, nurseries' websites, initiatives' websites). Therefore, these conversations and observations enriched my understanding and helped me diversify into different aspects of how the sector operates, informed by the perspectives of people from the sector and the public, expanding on the sector's dynamics on factors influencing the sector's operation and people's preferences, specific experiences with plants, understanding of invasive plants and on reactions to their impact. In addition, I paid attention to the broader social context explicitly and/or implicitly represented in the interactions.

Focus group

Focus groups were held with 23 people who attended the Illustrated Talk "Exploring the ornamental gardening sector in Southern Africa with a critical environmental lens" (Botanical Society of Namibia, 2023) in April 2023 (Figure 3.3b). The audience was divided into three groups and asked to answer six questions about their favourite plants, the places where they source them, and the challenges they faced when gardening. The session was finalised with a collective discussion on how to face those challenges, specifically regarding invasive plants (Appendix 7).

Plant surveys

Combining a Google map search with data sharing and validation through informants in Botswana, Namibia, and Zimbabwe, I compiled the contacts of formally established plant nurseries across the three countries. I visited and/or interacted with 11 major nurseries: three from Botswana, two from Namibia, and six from Zimbabwe. Four nurseries shared their list of plants in stock (two in Botswana and two in Zimbabwe), while the other three (one in Namibia and three in Zimbabwe) had up-to-date lists on their websites. I identified plants from the Instagram page of two nurseries (one in Namibia and one in Zimbabwe) and a visit to a nursery in Botswana. I used Pl@ntNet app (Pl@ntNet n.d.) and guides (Bromilow, 2018; Pienaar & Smith, 2011) for identifying plants.

I gathered demographic data from the participants: age, gender, ethnicity, level attained in the formal education system, and profession. I did not ask these explicitly in semi-structured

interviews, informal conversations, and observations. However, often, I could infer the information from the conversation and interaction when participants referred to it directly or indirectly. The questionnaire did not have pre-defined categories for any demographic data, except for the level in the formal education system. I decided to let people choose their words with no inputs, especially for the ethnicity data, since I believe ethnicity can be controversial in Southern Africa, given the legacies of the oppressive colonial and Apartheid systems that are still prevalent in present societies.

3.3.2 Data analysis and interpretation

An overall qualitative and reflexive approach governed my analysis and interpretation of the data I generated through the methods explained earlier (Figure 3.4a). Verbal interactions were recorded and later transcribed, or handwritten notes were taken and digitalised. I used thematic analysis (Braun & Clarke, 2022) to analyse the textual data. The quantitative part of the survey was coded through quantitative content analysis (Sullivan & Forrester, 2019).

Figure 3.4: General data analysis and interpretation. (a) Workflow to data analysis and interpretation; (b) Cluster of codes after analysing seven participants' transcripts; (c) An example of a theme-building mind map. (d) A preliminary map of the themes where sub-themes are meaning-oriented, while themes tend to be topic-oriented.

I familiarised myself with the information given by participants by listening to the recorded interactions several times to correct the transcriptions since Zoom and Microsoft Outlook transcribing tools tend to not understand well the accents of English speakers outside of what more stereotypical British, US, South African, Australian, Canadian and New Zealand accents are. While handwriting other interactions with participants, I became familiar with their information, which was reinforced later when I digitalised (i.e., typed) them. I passively and actively coded my data by carefully reading and re-reading the information and highlighting the codes manually. First, I actively coded; second, I used Nvivo 1.5 to organise and visualise codes from different sources (Figure 3.4b); and thirdly, I manually mapped the codes into themes. These steps were conducted iteratively by adding more participants to the analysis each time. Each step contributed to developing the subsequent one. Mind mapping is a valuable tool for making sense of coding (Fearnley, 2022), which I utilised for organising and building themes from the codes (Figure 3.4c). For the quantitative content analysis, I used the word count tool of Nvivo 1.5 and manual counting.

My approach to thematic analysis is inductive and stands in between the codebook and reflexive typologies, with both meaning-oriented and topic-oriented themes being part of the analysis (Figure 3.4d) since I wanted to understand but also typify or describe the role of the ornamental sector in plant invasions (Braun & Clarke, 2022; Braun & Clarke, 2023b). Following my experiential qualitative and critical realist approach, I analysed the text at a

semantic level, assuming that what participants say reflects their realities (Braun & Clarke, 2022). I interpreted the data I generated through deductive and retroductive reasoning.

As the reflection in Box 3.5 from Braun & Clarke (2022) states, I used Nvivo 1.5 primarily for organisational purposes since my coding and theme building were manual. Reflecting on my beginnings, I perceived that Nvivo 1.5 was needed to validate the analytical procedure. I often found myself telling my PhD colleagues that Nvivo 1.5 was not the magic tool that would do the coding for you, that your hands were supposed to “get dirty” in the art of coding by hand.

Data from the plant surveys was standardised based on the Plants of the World Online (POWO) checklist (Board of Trustees of the Royal Botanic Gardens, Kew, n.d.) and organised by the nursery. I matched my compilation with the records from the SADC’s countries found in the Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species (GIIRS) (GBIF Secretariat, n.d.). I provide a characterisation of the resulting subset of the species that could create conflicts of interest regionally due to their recorded evidence of negative impacts and value for the ornamental sector. The data management was carried out with R v. 4.2.1, using the “lcvplants” package for taxonomical standardisation and species matching across databases (Appendix 8). The workflow is presented in [Chapter 4](#).

For each chapter, I integrated the data that responded to each chapter’s objective. For interpretation, I looked at the interactions between the data and the complexity derived from these interactions. Furthermore, I focussed on the nuances of the perspectives of the different types of stakeholders, socio-cultural backgrounds, geographies, and individuals represented by the participants. Participants’ quotes in Chapters 5 to 7 were given nicknames. My previous approach was identifying them with a numeral code, but a journal reviewer of one of my chapters pointed out how impersonal numeral codes feel. I agree with their comment and changed the numeral IDs for names.

3.4 Positionality, more than just asserting it

I, a Cuban brown woman, conducted my PhD research in an unknown region, Southern Africa, sponsored by a post-1992 British university. I was foreign to the sub-region subject of study and the country sponsoring it. I put effort into immersing myself in the sub-region even when I was not there physically. I learnt a national and hegemonic language in the sub-region—Setswana. I read about the region’s history and culture. Once I finally made it there, I experienced the daily lives of the majorities as much as I could, even though majorities considered me a member of a privileged minority (i.e., white foreigner or “expat”). In the UK,

majorities consider me a member of a discriminated minority. Researching an underexplored topic in an unknown geographical space within a limited timeframe of less than three years, with movement restrictions due to a global pandemic, a passport that cost me a quarter of my research budget in migratory permits and visas, and a research background in ecology and positivism, meant that, even on reflection, it could have only happened with the (new-to-me) philosophical and methodological approach I took (see a brief final reflection in [sub-chapter 8.2.1](#)). I consider myself a social and resilient person; thus, interacting with participants and their environment and maximising the opportunities to generate data ethically underpinned my methodological practice based on my philosophical premises.

Compared to many Southern Africans, I was privileged because I had a monthly PhD stipend from a British university and a research budget of a few thousand pounds. My monthly stipend, although precarious in England because it is below the take-home salary on a minimum wage, granted me a higher purchasing capacity in Southern Africa. My higher purchasing capacity made me feel like the residents from hegemonic and affluent countries who come to less powerful, less wealthy territories to alleviate their stress and oppression, enjoying the many privileges that a job paid in hard currency and/or a bank account in hard currency provides. When I contemplated applying to this PhD vacancy, I found myself debating between several conflicting ideas.

First, the position allowed me to develop a career in invasion science, which I initiated in Cuba, towards inter- and transdisciplinarity. It would also bring me closer to achieving one of my childhood dreams, going to Africa, as I had seen in the BBC and National Geographic documentaries—which I later realised are rooted in colonial extractive naturalist and adventurous research practices and worldviews. Second, I found it bizarre to apply for a project about a region I was not from, funded by a British institution. As a conservationist in Cuba working for Cuban research institutions, I had been exposed to the typical extractive, disrespectful, and passive-aggressive colonial practices from European and North American academics, mainly from Germany and the United States, when “collaborating” with Cuban fellows. Therefore, I was terrified to reproduce those practices from which my colleagues and I suffered (see my final reflections in [sub-chapter 8.2](#)).

In the end, a critical combination of ideas won. I realised that I had an outsider perspective but was familiar at the same time. I come from a Caribbean-Latin country with a dominant (although discriminated) African heritage, historical (and of course, contested) relations with

the Anti-Apartheid and anti-colonial movements in Southern Africa (Bonacci et al., 2020), a collapsing “socialist” regime (López Hernández, 2023) and a perceivably perpetual presence in the List of Comprehensively Sanctioned Countries from the Office of Asset Control of the US Treasury Department (US Department of the Treasury, n.d.). Despite the uniqueness of my identity, I share cultural and idiosyncratic commonalities with the different ethno-racial groups in Southern Africa (on top of the apparent commonalities that we all share just because we are humans).

I made the most of those commonalities to develop my research practice by my ethical and philosophical principles. For example, connecting with perceivably white Africans and expats was easy. I perceived that for white Africans, I am also white, opposite to white Europeans and Cubans, who do not consider me white usually. For the expats, I was also an expat. Connecting with “mixed” Southern Africans was also generally easy, although my mix is similar to theirs. Connecting with perceivably black Southern Africans was more complex and varied depending on their experiences with Latin Caribbean cultures and people. It entailed deeper and longer interactions that could break the stereotype of not looking “black” enough and being a perceivably affluent foreigner. The dancing culture of my country and region, which I proudly represent, helped me break stereotypes and show my commonalities. In the case of Botswana, being able to speak basic Setswana opened the hearts of several participants. In the case of Namibia, the historic relations with Cuba brought me reverence amongst people who supported and/or benefited from the independence. In contrast, it brought suspicion and discomfort amongst others whose privileges were affected. I navigated their emotions with care and respect. Several times, I had to suppress my instinctive reactions to racist/discriminatory comments, jokes, and opinions for the sake of my work and mental integrity.

My positionality and moral codes limited my interactions with the road sellers (or street vendors), for whom I seem more affluent and undoubtedly a foreigner. For example, I could not go to places in Harare where I had wished to go to interact with the road sellers because of safety reasons as a lone foreign woman or interact deeper with several road sellers across the cities I visited in the sub-region because of my awkwardness, their suspicions and the obvious ethical issues around asking questions for research purposes. What was I going to offer them? How were these questions going to help them? These were questions that I was constantly reflecting on, and that formed part of my discomfort and awkwardness (see my final reflections about this in [sub-chapter 8.2.3](#)).

On the other hand, my positionality and critical realist lens made me aware of the critical underlying socio-historical and geopolitical issues that permeate people's relations to biodiversity and, specifically, invasive ornamental plants when analysing and interpreting the data I generated. Other researchers with different positionalities would not have seen these as critical, nor would they have focused on them the same way I did. Indeed, my intense focus on socio-historical and geopolitical issues in Southern Africa generated resistance and hesitance (see my conclusions in [sub-chapter 8.1](#) and reflections on the matter in [sub-chapter 8.2.2](#)). However, I think these issues are relevant to explain what I saw regarding the use and perceptions of ornamental plants in Southern Africa, reflecting the sort of retroductive “hunch” that Price (2019) defends for the practice of a critical realist ecology ([sub-chapter 8.2.2](#)). They lay in the real domain of realities, entangled hierarchically with other causal mechanisms from the individual to the cosmological levels (see example of causal mechanisms influencing the mainstreaming of sustainability at Rhodes University, in Togo, 2015).

As Jasmine K. Gani and Rabea M. Khan reflected, acknowledging positionality can be a narcissistic act of legitimising privilege and oppression and solely an attempt to redeem guilt from the hegemonic researchers (Gani & Khan, 2024). Therefore, I did everything I consciously could not to reproduce oppressive and disrespectful patterns arising from my symbolic and practical privileges. I conducted this research with humility, acknowledging that the PhD system I am in is colonial, capitalist, and neoliberal by nature, giving me a very narrow margin for a genuinely emancipatory and non-extractive research practice.

4. Established alien and invasive ornamental plants on sale in Botswana, Namibia and Zimbabwe: potential sources for plant invasions

Abstract

Ornamental gardening is one of the main historical pathways for plant introductions into Southern Africa. A few introduced ornamental plants have become invasive, sometimes triggering stakeholder conflicts. Knowing which alien plants are being sold and used as ornamentals in the sub-region is important to assess the potential for future biological invasions and stakeholder conflicts. This chapter identifies and characterises the ornamental plants on sale in three southern African countries and compares these to lists of plants considered invasive in the continental Southern African Development Community (SADC). I compiled all plant taxa sold across eleven nurseries in Botswana (3), Namibia (2), and Zimbabwe (6) by accessing the plants in stock either on the nurseries' website or on social media and the stock lists that nursery owners shared with me. The compilation was matched with the Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species to identify the invasive taxa. I characterised this sub-set by taxonomical family, growth form, and biogeographical origin. I identified 1,211 species on sale, of which 289 have established alien populations and 82 are considered invasive in at least one continental SADC country. Many of these plants are popular trees and shrubs in the sub-region and worldwide. This chapter demonstrates that the ornamental sector might be contributing to the invasion debt in Southern Africa. Further sale of established and invasive species should be reconsidered. However, approaches to reduce their sale need to be considered carefully since their current popularity across the sub-region and worldwide could make them a source of conflict for the stakeholders involved in the interplay between the ornamental horticulture sector and the management of biological invasions. My results provide a baseline for an invasion risk assessment of the ornamental sector at a sub-regional level.

4.1 Introduction

Ornamental plants have accompanied humanity since the early days of civilisation (Wilson, Kendal et al., 2016). With transoceanic exploration, European colonisation and later industrialisation, ornamental gardening and landscaping became an industry that has moved thousands of plant species worldwide (Hinsley et al., 2025; van Kleunen et al., 2018). This movement introduced and spread alien plants following trends, fashions, and passions (Altman et al., 2022; Wilson, Kendal et al., 2016; van Kleunen et al., 2018). In Southern Africa,

ornamental gardening has been one of the main historical pathways for plant introduction, accounting for ~30%–70% of the intentional introductions in different countries of the sub-region between the 19th and 20th centuries (Henderson, 2006; Kobisi et al., 2019; Maroyi, 2017). Introduced ornamental plants like *Lantana camara*, *Pontederia crassipes*, and *Tithonia diversifolia* have become invasive in the sub-region, showing the complex dynamics of cost/benefit balances that vary with time, space and stakeholders (Novoa et al., 2018; Shackleton, Richardson et al., 2019).

Those abovementioned species were introduced in the sub-region over a hundred years ago. However, the development of the ornamental industry in Southern Africa continues nowadays, with South Africa at the frontline. According to Faulkner et al. (2020), plant introductions for ornamental horticulture in South Africa will likely continue increasing. Alien plants are generally dominant in gardens and public spaces across the urban areas of the sub-region (Kashe et al., 2022; Mafokate et al., 2013; Milton & Dean, 2025; Richardson & Potgieter, 2024; Shackleton & Shackleton, 2016; 2018). The intentional spread, environmental suitability, species' invasiveness, and residence time could cause biological invasions. Knowing what species are sold and used as ornamentals in the sub-region is an essential step to assess the likelihood of some of them becoming invasive and/or a source of conflicts of interest. Hence, this chapter reports what plant species are sold and used as ornamental in three southern African countries (Botswana, Namibia, and Zimbabwe) in light of the alien taxa recognised as established and invasive in the sub-region.

4.2 Materials & Methods

Data collection and analysis took place from mid-2022 to mid-2024, combining different sources of information from 11 major nursery businesses in Botswana, Namibia, and Zimbabwe (Figure 4.1). The willingness of nursery owners to share the information on their stocks and/or allow me to survey their stock on-site, as well as the online visibility of their stock on the internet (i.e., through social media or website), determined my ability to access the data. In addition, my mobility capacity and the role of gatekeepers (also participants) influenced my capacity to reach nurseries and access their stocks. I will describe my workflow to collect and analyse the data in the following lines.

Figure 4.1: Workflow for creating a list of plant species on sale in nurseries in Southern Africa that have established alien populations in the subregion and a commented list of invasive species.

1. **Nursery identification and validation:** I used a Google map search, data sharing and validation, and further participants’ input (snowballing sampling) and in situ identification in Botswana, Namibia, and Zimbabwe. The Google map search allowed me to identify 18 nurseries in Botswana, 2 in Zimbabwe, and 1 in Namibia. Participants indicated 9 more nurseries, and I identified a dozen other nurseries in Botswana. In Harare, Zimbabwe, the co-organiser of the Annual Garden Show indicated 33 nurseries. I identified other 8 nurseries in the show and other 6 in the city. In Namibia, I identified 10 nurseries.
2. **Inputs:** I accessed 3 formal nurseries identified in Botswana, 2 in Namibia, and 6 in Zimbabwe. Four nurseries shared their list of plants in stock (two in Botswana and two in Zimbabwe), while the other three (one in Namibia and three in Zimbabwe) had up-to-date lists on their websites. I identified plants from the Instagram page of two nurseries (one in Namibia and one in Zimbabwe) and a visit to a nursery in Botswana. I also calculated a species accumulation curve per nursery to know how much trade I covered with the “vegan” R package (Oksanen et al., 2017).
3. **Plan identification** was facilitated using the Pl@ntNet app (Pl@ntNet n.d.) and plant guides (Bromilow, 2018; Pienaar & Smith, 2011).

4. **Taxonomical standardisation** was conducted with the “lcvplants” R package (Freiberg et al., 2020), using the 2023 version of the Leipzig Plant Catalogue as the taxonomic backbone (see the R script in Appendix 8).
5. **Matching with Global Register for Introduced and Invasive Species (GRIIS):** The resulting plant inventory was matched with the register of introduced and invasive species for the 12 continental countries belonging to the Southern African Development Community (Braun et al., 2020; Chase & Pagad, 2020; Figueiredo et al., 2020; Groom et al., 2020; Hae & Pagad, 2020; Heath et al., 2020; Maroyi et al., 2020; Mwanyambo et al., 2020; Pagad, 2022; Robinson et al., 2020; Witt & Pagad, 2020; Witt et al., 2020). I used the “lcvplants” R package for database matching (Freiberg et al., 2020) (see the R script in Appendix 8).

GRIIS records alien species and native-alien populations of native species that have been established in a given country, particularising whether the species has evidence of a negative impact on species, ecosystems, and services (Pagad et al., 2018). If the species has evidence of adverse impact—which includes being widespread, highly abundant, and fast-spreading—GRIIS categorises it as invasive. Although this definition implies that becoming invasive has a negative impact—which is not what the conceptual framework of biological framework implies (Blackburn et al., 2011)—the GRIIS approach could be a proxy to unveil potential conflict species amongst the stakeholders involved in the interplay between the ornamental sector and invasion management in the sub-region. That is because GRIIS is an ‘expert’-based compilation, where most country editors are from or based in the given country, allowing for a likely more direct reflection of the views of the particular research community from that given country.

The abovementioned steps resulted in an inventory of the established alien plant species in any of the continental SADC countries that are currently in the ornamental trade of Botswana, Namibia, and Zimbabwe (Figure 4.1).

6. **Extraction of species labelled as invasive:** I filtered the alien established species labelled as invasive in any of the continental SADC countries, resulting in a checklist of invasive plant species on sale within the ornamental sector across Botswana, Namibia, and Zimbabwe.

This list was characterised by growth form, native range, family, and SADC countries in which it is considered invasive. “Plants of the World Online” (POWO) [Board of Trustees of the

Royal Botanic Gardens, Kew, n.d.] was used to collect information on growth form and geographical origin. I grouped the growth forms found in POWO into six broad categories (herb, liana, epiphyte, shrub, succulent, and tree). For biogeographical origin, I used the nine level-1 botanical regions of the World Geographical Scheme for Recording Plant Distributions of the Taxonomic Databases Working Group (Brummitt, 2001).

4.3 Results

I compiled 1,835 plant names from 11 formal nurseries in Botswana, Namibia, and Zimbabwe (Appendix 10) without reaching the asymptote in the accumulation curve (Appendix 9). The taxonomical standardisation (Appendix 11 shows the metadata) resulted in 1,211 accepted species names, 320 synonyms, 207 unfound names, and 12 unresolved names (Appendix 12). The numerical difference between the initial compilation (1,835) and the total outcome of the standardisation (1,750) is because initially, plant names had spelling errors and spaces or x in between the genus and the specific epithet (e.g., *Abutilon x grandiflora*, *Abutilon grandiflora*). Of this plant inventory, 289 species (24%) have established alien populations in at least one continental SADC country (Table 4.1, Appendix 13 and 14). Of this list of established species, 82 (28%) are considered invasive in at least one continental SADC country (Table 4.2, Appendix 15).

Table 4.1: Ornamental plants on sale in 11 nurseries in Botswana, Namibia and Zimbabwe that have established alien populations in any of the continental countries of the Southern African Development Community (SADC) as per the Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species (GRIIS).

Country	Number of established species considered invasive in GRIIS	Number of established species considered non-invasive in GRIIS	Total
Angola	1	38	39
Botswana	4	25	29
Democratic Republic of Congo	0	94	94
Eswatini	1	46	47
Lesotho	3	5	8
Malawi	10	41	51
Mozambique	5	18	23
Namibia	9	10	19
South Africa	57	167	224
Tanzania	29	20	49
Zambia	29	19	48
Zimbabwe	15	48	63

Table 4.2: Plant species sold in nurseries in Botswana, Namibia and Zimbabwe that are considered invasive in at least one continental country of the Southern African Development Community (SADC), according to the Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species (GRIIS).

Species	Number of countries with invasive records (out of 12 continental SADC countries)
<i>Lantana camara</i> L.	9
<i>Opuntia ficus-indica</i> (L.) Mill.	6
<i>Psidium guajava</i> L.	6
<i>Agave americana</i> L.	5
<i>Jacaranda mimosifolia</i> D.Don	5
<i>Parkinsonia aculeata</i> L.	5
<i>Agave angustifolia</i> Haw.	4
<i>Caesalpinia decapetala</i> (Roth) Alston	4
<i>Canna x generalis</i> L.H.Bailey & E.Z.Bailey	4
<i>Canna indica</i> L.	4
<i>Dolichandra unguis-cati</i> (L.) L.G.Lohmann	4
<i>Sphagneticola trilobata</i> (L.) Pruski	4
<i>Tecoma stans</i> (L.) Juss. ex Kunth	4
<i>Toona ciliata</i> (Roxb. ex Rottler) M.Roem.	4
<i>Cascabela thevetia</i> (L.) Lippold	3
<i>Catharanthus roseus</i> (L.) G.Don	3
<i>Erigeron karvinskianus</i> DC.	3
<i>Ipomoea carnea</i> Jacq.	3
<i>Persicaria capitata</i> (Buch.-Ham. ex D.Don) H.Gross	3
<i>Antigonon leptopus</i> Hook. & Arn.	2
<i>Cestrum elegans</i> (Brongn. ex Neumann) Schlttdl.	2
<i>Cinnamomum camphora</i> (L.) J.Presl	2
<i>Duranta erecta</i> L.	2
<i>Euphorbia tirucalli</i> L.	2
<i>Furcraea foetida</i> (L.) Haw.	2
<i>Grevillea robusta</i> A.Cunn. ex R.Br.	2
<i>Ipomoea indica</i> (Burm.f.) Merr.	2
<i>Ligustrum lucidum</i> W.T.Aiton	2
<i>Lonicera japonica</i> Thunb.	2
<i>Nephrolepis cordifolia</i> (L.) C.Presl	2
<i>Pteridium aquilinum</i> (L.) Kuhn	2
<i>Schinus molle</i> L.	2
<i>Schinus terebinthifolius</i> Raddi	2
<i>Senna bicapsularis</i> (L.) Roxb.	2
<i>Senna spectabilis</i> (DC.) H.S.Irwin & Barneby	2
<i>Tradescantia zebrina</i> Bosse	2
<i>Acrocarpus fraxinifolius</i> Wight ex Arn.	1

<i>Alternanthera brasiliana</i> (L.) Kuntze	1
<i>Alternanthera sessilis</i> (L.) R.Br. ex DC.	1
<i>Asclepias curassavica</i> L.	1
<i>Buddleja madagascariensis</i> Lam.	1
<i>Carpobrotus edulis</i> (L.) N.E.Br.	1
<i>Casuarina cunninghamiana</i> Miq.	1
<i>Cestrum aurantiacum</i> Lindl.	1
<i>Clusia rosea</i> Jacq.	1
<i>Cortaderia selloana</i> (Schult.) Asch. & Graebn.	1
<i>Cotoneaster franchetii</i> Boiss.	1
<i>Delonix regia</i> (Bojer ex Hook.) Raf.	1
<i>Dichondra micrantha</i> Urb.	1
<i>Elaeis guineensis</i> Jacq.	1
<i>Euryops chrysanthemoides</i> (DC.) B.Nord.	1
<i>Foeniculum vulgare</i> Mill.	1
<i>Fraxinus americana</i> L.	1
<i>Hedychium coccineum</i> Buch.-Ham. ex Sm.	1
<i>Helianthus annuus</i> L.	1
<i>Homalanthus populifolius</i> Graham	1
<i>Hypoestes phyllostachya</i> Baker	1
<i>Ipomoea alba</i> L.	1
<i>Jatropha curcas</i> L.	1
<i>Nerium oleander</i> L.	1
<i>Oenothera biennis</i> L.	1
<i>Phyllostachys nigra</i> (Lodd. ex Lindl.) Munro	1
<i>Prunus cerasoides</i> Buch.-Ham. ex D.Don	1
<i>Pyracantha crenulata</i> (Roxb. ex D.Don) M.Roem.	1
<i>Quercus robur</i> L.	1
<i>Ravenala madagascariensis</i> Sonn.	1
<i>Salix babylonica</i> L.	1
<i>Sambucus canadensis</i> L.	1
<i>Solanum betaceum</i> Cav.	1
<i>Solanum pseudocapsicum</i> L.	1
<i>Spartium junceum</i> L.	1
<i>Spathodea campanulata</i> P.Beauv.	1
<i>Stictocardia beraviensis</i> (Vatke) Hallier.f.	1
<i>Syzygium cumini</i> (L.) Skeels	1
<i>Syzygium jambos</i> (L.) Alston	1
<i>Syzygium paniculatum</i> Gaertn.	1
<i>Terminalia catappa</i> L.	1
<i>Tipuana tipu</i> (Benth.) Kuntze	1
<i>Tradescantia fluminensis</i> Vell.	1
<i>Vinca major</i> L.	1

<i>Vitex trifolia</i> L.	1
<i>Ziziphus mauritiana</i> Lam.	1

Most of these species labelled as invasive in at least one continental SADC country are shrubs (27, 33%) and trees (26, 32%), followed by herbs (13, 16%), lianas (9, 11%), succulents (5, 6%) and epiphytes (2, 2%) (Figure 4.2a). The group spans 41 taxonomical families, with Fabaceae leading the numbers (8, 10%), followed by Apocynaceae and Convolvulaceae (5 each, 6% each), Asteraceae, Bignoniaceae and Myrtaceae (4 each, 5% each), and Agavaceae, Euphorbiaceae and Rosaceae (3, 4% each) (Figure 4.2b, Appendix 15).

Figure 4.2: Growth form (a) and taxonomic family (b) of the 82 plant species traded as ornamental in Botswana, Namibia, and Zimbabwe that are labelled as invasive in at least one continental country of the Southern Africa Development Community (SADC) as per the Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species (GRIIS).

The origins of the remaining species span eight botanical regions: Africa, Asia-Temperate, Asia-Tropical, Australasia, Europe, Northern America, Pacific, and Southern America. The majority have a broad native range, including more than one botanical region (43, 52%), with Southern and Northern America being the most common combination (24, 29%). A further 44% (19) of them span different combinations, including Asia-Tropical, Asia-Temperate, Africa, Australasia, Europe, and the Pacific. The rest of the species (38, 46%) native ranges include a single botanical region, where Africa and Southern America lead with 11 species each (13%), followed by Asia Temperate and Northern America with 5 each (6%).

4.4 Discussion

This chapter documents that at least 289 out of 1,211 (i.e., 24%) plant species stocked in 11 major nurseries in Botswana, Namibia, and Zimbabwe have established alien populations in at least one continental country of the Southern Africa Development Community. This subset of plants on sale are part of the ornamental trade and flora worldwide (Álvarez de Zayas, 2008; Beaury et al., 2021; Costa et al., 2017; Humair et al., 2015; Kashe et al., 2022; Milton & Dean, 2025; Mukubu Pika et al., 2024; Petřík et al., 2019; Radji & Kokou, 2013) (Appendix 16). For example, 17 out of these 289 species are amongst the 100 species with the highest average number of offers per day on eBay in 2014, according to Humair et al. (2015). Moreover, at least 74 species from this subset are in the nursery trade across the United States (Beaury et al., 2021). In contrast, the ornamental plant trade in Kinshasa (Democratic Republic of Congo) shares 33 species with the presented subset in this chapter (Mukubu Pika et al., 2024).

When zooming in on the 82 species labelled as invasive in at least one continental SADC country (Table 4.2), 56 of these (68%) are used and/or traded as ornamental (and more) in other countries of Africa (including Botswana and South Africa), the Americas, Asia, Australasia and Europe (Appendix 16). Moreover, the relative distribution of growth forms across this subset follows the general pattern reported for the established and invasive flora across Southern Africa (Henderson, 2006; Omer et al., 2021; Richardson et al., 2020), where shrubs and trees dominate. The relative distribution of taxonomical families follows another general pattern in the ornamental flora worldwide and across Southern Africa (Humair et al., 2015; Mukubu Pika et al., 2024; Semanya & Maroyi, 2020) and the established/invasive flora in

Southern Africa (Henderson, 2006; Henderson & Wilson, 2017; Richardson et al., 2020), where Fabaceae, Myrtaceae, Euphorbiaceae, Asteraceae, Apocynaceae and Rosaceae lead the numbers. Concerning the native ranges, the Americas, Asia, and Africa are the main contributors, similar to the reported ornamental flora in Togo (Radji & Kokou, 2013) and the established and invasive species in the sub-region (Henderson, 2006; Omer et al., 2021).

Notably, most species in the invasive subset have native ranges extensively spread along latitudinal and longitudinal gradients, showing high climatic plasticity. In that sense, Omer et al. (2024) point out that although climatic suitability will likely decrease for cultivated alien plants across the sub-region, this predicted decrease might be less for species native to tropical areas, the southern hemisphere, and those already established. Moreover, several of these species have a long residence time in the sub-region. For instance, according to Henderson (2006), *Catharanthus roseus* arrived in continental Southern Africa before the Dutch colonisation of the Cape in 1652. In contrast, *Opuntia ficus-indica*, *Quercus robur*, and *Salix babylonica* arrived between 1652 and 1700, and *Canna indica* and *Psidium guajava* before 1800. During the 1800s, *Nerium oleander*, *Agave americana*, *Ligustrum lucidum*, *Oenothera biennis*, *Lonicera japonica*, *Lantana camara*, *Caesalpinia decapetala*, and species of *Grevillea* and *Syzygium* were introduced (Henderson, 2006). A wide native range can be a proxy of a wide alien range, which, coupled with a long residence time, can explain plant invasiveness (Wilson et al., 2007). The subset of invasive ornamental plants I report in this chapter exhibit both traits. Also, a significant proportion of this subset is made of nitrogen fixers, which Wilson et al. (2007) found to have high spread rates across South Africa—although limited to *Acacia* species. Moreover, species reported in this chapter, like *Tecoma stans*, have shown the highest spread rates in the Southern African Plant Invaders Atlas (SAPIA) from 2000 to 2016 (Henderson & Wilson, 2017), the highest abundance in arid urban areas like Gaborone in Botswana (Mafokate et al., 2013) and high self-seeding capacity in arid towns like Prince Albert in South Africa (Milton & Dean, 2025).

Other species reported here have been in the market for a long time (e.g., *Catharanthus roseus*, *Canna indica*, *Lantana camara*, and *Vinca major*), subject to selective breeding or hybridisation. I cannot confirm whether those species are traded as sterile cultivars or what specific cultivars are in the market. Alien and Invasive Species Regulations in South Africa allow the trade of sterile cultivars of several declared invasive species reported here (e.g., *Catharanthus roseus*, *Canna indica*, *Vinca major*). However, even sterile cultivars of such species, for instance, could reproduce asexually. Mainly, species like *Jacaranda mimosifolia*,

Tecoma stans, *Schinus molle*, *Schinus terebinthifolius*, *Nerium oleander*, and *Casuarina cunninghamiana* are frequently planted in urban areas across South Africa (Milton & Dean, 2025; Shackleton & Shackleton, 2016; 2018). In addition, other traded species that are not included as invasive in the GIIRS database, like *Dodonea viscosa* subsp. *angustifolia*, *Washingtonia robusta*, and *Cupressus sempervirens* are noteworthy because Milton & Dean (2025) report high self-seeding in a town in the South African Karoo. All these nuances pose challenges for invasion risk assessment and environmental regulation, which require attention and investment.

Rouget et al. (2016) and Henderson & Wilson (2017) have shown that South Africa has a high invasion debt, which could suggest that the sub-region also has a high invasion debt. Nonetheless, this has to be quantified. This research, along with others like Semenya & Maroyi (2020), Mukuba Pika et al. (2024), and Milton & Dean (2025), provides the baseline to quantify the invasion debt linked to the ornamental sector across the sub-region. As this subset presented here is being actively traded and used as ornamental, the constant propagule pressure and gene flow coming from this exchange could contribute to further invasions by providing genetic diversity or could slow these by continually diluting adaptations to the Southern African environments (Wilson et al., 2007; 2009). Moreover, these species could be a source of conflict for the stakeholders involved in the interplay between the ornamental horticulture sector and the management of biological invasions since several of them are popularly used globally (Appendix 16) and in the sub-region (Milton & Dean, 2025; Shackleton & Shackleton, 2016; 2018). Research efforts that cover a bigger trade size and unpack the perceptions and impacts of that subset of species reported here would be necessary to prevent and/or solve conflicts—added to the previously mentioned cases like *Tecoma stans* or *Dodonea viscosa* subsp. *angustifolia*, *Agave americana* could be another interesting case study because agaves are often confused with aloes, and trends towards water-wise and indigenous species are increasing across the sub-region (see next chapter) and worldwide (van Kleunen et al., 2018). This chapter generally provides a baseline for an invasion risk assessment of the ornamental sector and the systematic consideration of such protocol at the sub-regional level.

5. Links between ornamental sector and alien plants in Southern

Africa

Abstract

Humans and ornamental plants have a long relationship that could explain why ornamental gardening has been one of the main reasons for intentionally introducing and spreading plants worldwide. In Southern Africa, a significant part of the alien flora was introduced for ornamental purposes. Some species have become invasive, with ecological and socio-economic impacts that can create conflicts between stakeholders, depending on their relations with the species. This paper unpacks how the ornamental industry in Southern Africa operates as well as people's preferences for ornamental plants and practices in order to highlight links between the industry and plant invasions and to help address potential conflicts. Drawing on empirical data primarily collected in 2022/23 in Botswana, Namibia, and Zimbabwe (and other Southern African countries), my results show that the global industry, but predominantly the South African, highly influences Southern Africa's ornamental industry. The sector provides 'formal' and 'informal' jobs to people in urban areas, especially middle-aged women from ethnic majorities. The sector's operation and gardening practices show expressions of the typical cultural hybridity of postcolonial states where hegemonic and subaltern practices coexist and mix. Alien plants and foreign styles often symbolise higher social status, but controversially, socially privileged groups are publicly leading shifts towards more geographically contextualised practices and native plants. We conclude by arguing that recognising historical processes' influences on the sector's operation and its links with alien plants is essential for a more ethically sound and fair stakeholder engagement in preventing and managing plant invasions from the ornamental sector in Southern Africa.

5.1 Introduction

Humans have been using ornamental plants for over 10,000 years (Nadel et al., 2013) for a complex range of aesthetic, cultural, genetic, and psychosocial reasons (Altman et al., 2022; Wilson, Kendal et al., 2016). The increasing globalisation has led to the human-aided movement of ornamental plants worldwide, contributing to the introduction of many plants to regions where they could not have reached without humans. Species introduced to a place through intended or unintended human activity are called alien species in the receipt places, per Blackburn et al. (2011) Unified Framework for Biological Invasions. Today, alien ornamental plants dominate urban areas globally (see Potgieter et al., 2017, for a review). For

example, estimates are that 30 to 70 % of the alien flora in Southern Africa was introduced for ornamentation (Henderson, 2006; Kobisi et al., 2019; Maroyi, 2017). Waves of plant introductions in Southern Africa differed in time.

Upon the start of the European colonisation of the Cape region in South Africa (Western Cape currently), the colonial administration introduced plants for forestry and agriculture, primarily intending to "build and develop" the new colony (Bennett & Kruger, 2015; Canavan, Richardson et al., 2019; Henderson, 2006). As colonial administration changed and colonial settlerism consolidated, the plant introductions for ornamental purposes surpassed the other purposes (Bennett & van Sittert, 2019; Canavan, Richardson, et al., 2019). According to Canavan, Richardson et al. (2019), between 1850 and 1920, European Victorian "plant hunters" promoted the fashion of alien plants, especially from Asia. Hence, following European trends, bamboo, especially temperate species from China, became a fashionable ornamental and status plant for wealthy people.

Concomitantly, by the first half of the 20th century, when rural Afrikaans republicanism was ruling the "post-colonial" South African Union, the old urban imperial English-speaking class from the Western Cape was using the Cape native flora as a distinctive mark for class, ethnic and regional identity (Bennett & van Sittert, 2019; van Sittert, 2003). Wealthier (and whiter) strata of society, thus, have led the movement that takes pride in the native flora (Bennett & van Sittert, 2019). Colonial settler-descendants have progressively increased their sense of belonging to Southern Africa (Ginsburgh, 2022; Johanson Botha, 2009; Matthews, 2011; Rasch, 2018), in turn, increasingly identifying with the non-human landscape and biodiversity that their ancestors found when they settled in the sub-region (Spierenburg & Wels, 2010).

Human relationships with ornamental plants, specifically alien plants, are thus a reflection of broader mechanisms operating at a macro scale across Southern Africa (e.g., socio-cultural, geopolitical). For example, colonial and apartheid legacies remain powerfully prevalent in the urban greening of South Africa at the expense of indigenous worldviews and identities (Shackleton & Gwedla, 2021; Venter et al., 2020), where wealthier (and usually whiter) people can afford a higher diversity of plants in gardens compared to less wealthy (Davoren et al., 2016). In addition, social media gardening groups (e.g., Gabs Gardener [n.d.] in Botswana, Gardening and Plant Lovers [n.d.] in Zimbabwe, Flower Gardening in Malawi and around Malawi [n.d.], Gardening in and around Zambia [n.d.]) show a preference for alien plants. In

Kinshasa (The Democratic Republic of Congo), for instance, Mukubu Pika et al. (2024) reported that 91% of the ornamental species on sale are alien.

However, some alien plants introduced as ornamental and invasive in South Africa have stirred stakeholder conflicts (Novoa et al., 2016; Shackleton et al., 2011), manifesting broader inequalities in South African society. The notion of a native flora that has to be safeguarded from invasive species has been used as an excuse for wealth and power accumulation (see examples in sub-chapter 2.2.2). These dynamics show how power imbalances and oppression are normalised through nature conservation and science in the sub-region (Ramutsindela et al., 2016; Spierenburg & Wels, 2010; van Sittert, 2003). This chapter, then, provides an integral analysis of which ornamental plants people prefer, how they use them, and the factors shaping their preferences. Doing so proves highly relevant to understanding the links between the ornamental industry and plant invasions while considering the underlying socio-ecological and geopolitical mechanisms.

A better understanding of gardening preferences could lead to management approaches guided by principles of care and justice (Turnhout, 2024), where conflicts between stakeholders involved could be minimised (Crowley et al., 2017). Considering justice and care in the management could contribute to an ornamental sector that can prevent and reduce the negative impacts of plant invasions and ensure the long-term socio-environmental sustainability of its practices (Hinsley et al., 2025; van Kleunen et al., 2018). Although a few studies have analysed factors shaping ornamental gardening or landscaping in parts of Southern Africa (e.g., Davoren et al., 2016; Jansen van Vuuren et al., 2020; Molebatsi et al., 2010; Nemudzudzanyi et al., 2010), they have not linked these factors to plant invasions. There are studies about perceptions of invasive ornamental plants in Southern and Eastern Africa (Canavan, Richardson et al., 2019; Shackleton et al., 2011, 2017; Witt et al., 2019), but none of them go one step back in the introduction-naturalisation-invasion continuum (Blackburn et al., 2011) to focus on alien plants. Furthermore, the focus on the factors influencing the preferences for alien plants at a sub-regional level is even less. With this chapter, I aim to unpack the ornamental industry's operation and people's preferences for ornamental plants and practices in several countries of Southern Africa, highlighting the connections between the industry and plant invasions to help address potential conflicts.

5.2 Approaches to studying the links between the ornamental sector and alien plants in Southern Africa

Previous authors studying the human dimensions of plant invasions in Southern Africa have used diverse methods (more details in sub-chapter 2.5). For example, Shackleton et al. (2011; 2015) and Shackleton & Shackleton (2016; 2018) used interviews, including key informant interviews, to assess perceptions of specific invasive plants in different parts of South Africa, as well as their contribution and disservices to people's livelihoods and wellbeing. Cronin et al. (2017) and Arnoldi & Shackleton (2021) used questionnaire-based interviews to assess the level of compliance with the South African legislation of plant nurseries in Cape Town and examine the role of commercial plant nurseries in shaping the urban forests across major cities in South Africa respectively. Ngorima & Shackleton (2019) combined interviews, focus groups, and participatory mapping to explore the contributions and disservices to rural communities' livelihoods of an invasive plant species in Eastern Cape, South Africa. Mosweu et al. (2013) used questionnaire-based interviews and focus groups on rural communities in the Southern Kalahari area of Botswana to assess the extent of the invasion of a plant species, people's perceptions of it, and the potential management actions to control its spread. Gaertner et al. (2017) combined questionnaire-based interviews, email-based surveys, and a workshop to assess the suitability of a decision-making framework to support the management of invasive species populations in urban ecosystems in Cape Town. Furthermore, Kachena & Shackleton (2024) merged participatory qualitative methods, community mapping exercises, time series analysis, and key informant interviews to explore the socio-ecological and economic implications of an invasive species and its management in Chimanimani, Zimbabwe.

Following these footsteps, I also merged several methods to ensure that my research practice was adequate to the geographical area, the type of stakeholder, and the individual needs and circumstances of the participants and mine (Table 5.1). Thus, I integrated semi-structured interviews (Appendix 3), a workshop (Appendix 4), questionnaires (Appendix 5 and 6), a focus group (Appendix 7), informal conversations, and participant observations (further details [sub-chapter 3.3](#)). However, different from previous authors, we conducted these methods under a patchwork ethnography approach (Günel et al., 2020; Günel & Watanabe, 2024) and a critical realist framework (Bhaskar, 1975; Price & Lotz-Sistka, 2015) to describe and interpret how the ornamental sector operates in Southern Africa and what factors influence it, especially concerning alien plants. I then conducted experiential qualitative research (Braun & Clarke, 2022; Braun & Clarke, 2024).

Table 5.1: The number of participants involved in this evaluation of the ornamental industry in Southern Africa. Participant observations took place during the site visits and beyond in daily life; thus, they included interactions with several people.

	semi-structured interviews	workshop	informal conversations	questionnaires	focus group	visits
South Africa	3 environmental specialists	10 environmental specialists	0	0	0	0
Botswana	2 environmental specialists	0	10 environmental specialists; 1 ornamental industry staff	14 ornamental industry staff; 35 end users	0	29
Namibia	2 environmental specialists	0	2 environmental specialists; 7 ornamental industry staff	3 ornamental industry staff; 13 end users	23 end users	10
Zimbabwe	2 environmental specialists	0	2 environmental specialists	13 ornamental industry staff; 1 end users	0	20
Zambia	3 environmental specialists	1 ornamental industry staff	0	0	0	0
Democratic Republic of Congo	0	0	2 environmental specialists	0	0	0

Patchwork ethnography consists of the combination of different methods and moments of data generation when a strictly continuous "data collection" period is unrealistic, allowing for inclusivity, empathy, consideration, and flexibility in the research practice (Günel et al., 2020; Günel et al., 2023; Günel & Watanabe, 2024). This approach proved appropriate for ethically developing my research practice, as it occurred during the COVID-19 pandemic and was subject to time, logistical, ethical, and safety challenges. It enabled the research process to adapt to local context and practices, ensuring feasibility and allowing for the best balance between geographical reach, stakeholder coverage, and in-depth understanding while being culturally sensitive and appropriate. The combination of methods allowed me to reach out to a greater diversity of participants within each stakeholder group while considering several of the above-mentioned factors. Should I have used a single method, the method's limitations would have limited the generation of relevant data. Combining different methods allowed me to complement a particular method's limitation with another's strength.

A critical realist lens to exploring the links between an economic sector like the ornamental industry and alien plants and, ultimately, plant invasions is helpful because of its premises that knowledge and reality are socially co-constructed, subjective, and ever-changing and that realities can exist in a domain beyond the empirical (Bhaskar, 1975; Braun & Clarke, 2024, Price, 2015). These are fundamental if I, as a researcher, aim to consider the social, political, cultural, economic, and ecological contexts influencing these links (Price & Lotz-Sistka, 2015) to seek conciliation and mutual understanding in the management of plant invasions related to the ornamental sector.

I targeted three types of stakeholders: environmental professionals, ornamental industry staff, and end-users. With this selection of stakeholders, we aimed to cover the breadth of those involved within the ornamental sector and environmental management. Environmental professionals include researchers, academics, scientists, university students, government officials, managers, entrepreneurs, educators, and activists working on various environmental topics, including biological invasions. Ornamental industry staff are people whose livelihood—or at least part—is associated with activities involving ornamental plants across the private, non-profit, and governmental sectors (e.g., landscaping businesses, nurseries, government offices managing urban spaces). End-users are the people buying/using ornamental plants for and within their spaces.

Participant recruitment and data collection occurred between August 2021 and May 2023, for which we obtained ethical approval from Coventry University (P120192) (further details in [sub-chapter 3.3](#)). First (Aug 2021–May 2022), I conducted online discussions with environmental professionals across continental Southern Africa. After COVID-19-related travel and social restrictions ended, I alternated between online and face-to-face meetings with all three stakeholder groups, focussing on Botswana, Namibia, and Zimbabwe. To facilitate this second phase, agreements with the institutions represented in this paper were established. A research permit from Botswana's Ministry of Environment, Natural Resources, Conservation and Tourism [ENT 8/36/4 LII (38)] was received for work in Botswana. In-situ research in Namibia and Zimbabwe was more short-term and guided by my ethical principles and those of participants who acted as gatekeepers.

I based each interaction on respect and written and/or verbal informed consent. However, given the informal and spontaneous nature of some interactions, there were instances where obtaining formal consent as per Coventry University's ethical clearance (i.e., filling out the relevant forms

while talking to people on public transport or during site visits) was not feasible nor appropriate. For example, a gatekeeper participant from Zimbabwe "warned" that Zimbabwean nursery owners would not sign any consent form nor even bother to look at it if presented. Instead, this participant introduced me to several potential participants, allowing me to engage honestly and in a culturally appropriate way with them, as Macdonald (2024) suggests. This alternative to the formal universities' ethical process is common (Macdonald, 2024; Maunganidze & Ruggunan, 2021), reflecting the inadequacies and impracticalities of academic institutions' current ethical clearance systems. Hence, the derived information from these engagements is considered experiential knowledge, acknowledging that it comes from interactions with people. The project was designed to maximise flexibility, which allowed them to seize opportunities when they emerged. Unfortunately, I could not reach places I would have wished to for safety reasons (e.g., Mbare in Harare, where selling activities are intense). Nonetheless, my flexible and patchwork approach was fundamental for successful ethical research practice, guaranteeing feasibility and allowing for the best balance between reach and in-depth understanding while being culturally sensitive and appropriate (Günel & Watanabe, 2024; Macdonald, 2024; Maunganidze & Ruggunan, 2021).

We interacted with 138 participants: 28 environmental professionals based in South Africa, Namibia, Botswana, Zimbabwe, Zambia, and the Democratic Republic of Congo, 38 ornamental industry staff, and 72 end users from Botswana, Namibia, and Zimbabwe. Another environmental professional from Zimbabwe co-designed the questionnaires for the ornamental industry staff and end-users (LC).

When possible, I gathered some demographic data, including age, gender, and ethnicity. These were only explicitly asked about in the questionnaires (Appendices 3 and 4). However, other participants sometimes mentioned these details directly or indirectly. I did not pre-define ethnicity since participants could have perceived it as inappropriate or perhaps unethical, given the legacies of colonial and Apartheid ethnic segregation in the sub-region (Funada-Classen, 2013; Ginsburgh, 2022; Hughes, 2010; Limb et al., 2010; Mgadla, 2014).

Although each method covered multiple aspects by the objectives of this thesis, this chapter focuses on i) the structure and dynamics of the ornamental industry, ii) the most popular ornamental plants and reasons for their popularity, iii) traits plants must have to be considered ornamental; and iv) factors influencing businesses' operations and people's ornamental practices and preferences.

Verbal interactions were either recorded or later transcribed or journaled and later digitalised. I used inductive thematic analysis (TA) to analyse the textual data and quantitative content analysis to count the frequencies participants consider certain plants as popular and/or favourite for them and the reasons for their preferences (Sullivan & Forrester, 2019). My TA typology stands between the codebook and reflexive TA (Braun & Clarke, 2022). Following my experiential qualitative and critical realist approach, I analysed the text at a semantic level, assuming that what participants say reflects their realities (Braun & Clarke, 2022). I interpreted the data through deductive and retroductive reasoning (details in [sub-chapter 3.3](#)). I mostly coded the textual data by hand but used Nvivo 1.5 and manual mapping (Fearnley, 2022). My interpretation intended to capture the dynamics of interactions amongst coding categories, considering the broader geographical and socio-historical contexts.

Throughout my analysis, I acknowledge my active role in the research process (Braun & Clarke, 2024; Rogers et al., 2013). For example, my positionality made me aware of the critical underlying socio-historical and geopolitical issues permeating people's relations to biodiversity, specifically invasive ornamental plants (see a more detailed explanation in [sub-chapter 3.4](#)). When analysing and interpreting the data, my positionality was particularly helpful to have that sort of retroductive "hunch" that Price (2019) defends for the practice of a critical realist ecology. Other researchers with different positionalities would not have seen these as critical, nor would they have focused on them.

5.4 Structure and dynamics of the ornamental sector in Southern Africa

My analysis indicates that the ornamental sector in Southern Africa has a transboundary and heterogeneous supply chain, with high logistic dependence on the hegemonic sub-regional player, South Africa. The so-called informal sector, in the form of road selling, makes a significant part of the sector. In general, alien plants and gardening styles driven by globally hegemonic countries within the industry are very popular. In the two following sub-sections, I unpack the sector's characteristics in two themes. Each sub-section corresponds to a theme whose evidence I describe and further discuss based on the available literature.

5.4.1 Transboundary and heterogeneous sector that reflects higher geopolitical relations

My fieldwork showcases that the sector varies across the sub-region, with different stakeholders involved in the supply chain in each country and noticeable differences in the sector's complexity. Participants perceive the countries' ornamental industries to be in different stages of development. According to them, South Africa leads, and the rest countries should

learn from it. This situation does not always seem to have been the case. A Botswanan nursery owner remembered Zimbabwe as a powerhouse in floriculture before their economy crashed. One Zimbabwean environmental professional commented on the industry's sub-regional picture:

“[...] [In Botswana] the garden industry is virtually non-existent. [...] Mozambique as well, not so much. Malawi would be interesting [...], but again, the plant sales industry on a domestic level is not well established or sophisticated. [...] Zambia is more sophisticated than Malawi [...], but again, it is not that big [...]"

(environmental specialist Leyla)

Although several participants qualified Botswana's industry as “infant, new,” the owner of the biggest nursery business in Botswana briefly described the market dynamics and the increase in competition over the years:

“In the beginning we were the only people who grew carnations [*Dianthus caryophyllus*]. There wasn't a big market for growing carnations for exports. But then, we got into fruit and vegetables and we're doing well. And eventually, slowly, the supermarkets were getting more and more filled up with fruit and vegs and the imports are probably coming big time. So, we've competing against imports from South Africa, sold through supermarkets, shops, etcetera. Now you get a lot of plant people selling along the road, which is quite new. It's been around for maybe 4-5 years.”

(ornamental industry staff Anders)

Based on my observations and interactions, the different stakeholders structuring the supply chains vary in size, roles, and services provided and often have multiple types of connections between them. South African franchises monopolise the supply of propagules, saplings, gardening materials, and tools to their branches and supermarkets (e.g., Spar, Pick' n Pay) in the neighbouring countries. For instance, small businesses and the public in Botswana commonly buy plants and propagules from branches of the South African franchise Builders (Builders, n.d.). Other South African well-established wholesale companies like Ball Straathof (Ball Straathof Pty Ltd, n.d.) and Malanseuns (Malanseuns, n.d.) supply businesses across the sub-region. According to a Botswanan professional, “let's say maybe 95% of the ornamental plants [are imported] from South Africa” (environmental specialist Seloapi). This dependency reaches as far north as the Democratic Republic of Congo, where “ornamental plants are imported directly from South Africa,” according to a participating professional (environmental specialist Gabriel). Nevertheless, Botswana, Namibia, and Zimbabwe plant businesses and end-users have multiple sources: they grow their plants, take propagules from wherever they go, and source from bigger nurseries within and beyond their countries.

In addition to commercial transactions and trade relationships across the Southern African horticultural sector, participants and interactions reflected that the non-commercial (and transboundary) exchange of plants and knowledge between friends, relatives, and neighbours or members of a group/community also shapes local plant exchange practices and the heterogeneity of the sector. A South African environmental professional said that plant sharing between friends and/or relatives is very common across the middle-income population in South Africa. With the popularity of social media, there are Facebook groups in other countries that articulate networks through which people exchange/sell knowledge, experiences, and plants (e.g., Gabs Gardeners from Botswana [Gabs Gardeners, n.d.] and The Zimbabwe Gardening and Plant Lovers [The Zimbabwe Gardening and Plant Lovers, n.d.]). Regular activities like the Annual Garden Show in Zimbabwe (“our equivalent of Chelsea [the RHS Chelsea Flower Show]” as the main organiser put it [environmental specialist Leyla]) and groups like the Botanical Society of Namibia encourage and facilitate this exchange and the development of businesses. Government forestry departments and botanic gardens also play important roles — from commercial to educational. In Botswana, for instance, apart from their commercial mandate, the forestry nurseries have promoted backyard nurseries as business models to alleviate financial poverty. Their work seems to have been reflected in an increase in these types of businesses within Botswana (see also interviewee comment above by ornamental industry staff Anders).

As my participants commented, figures from other authors indicate that, indeed, South Africa and Zimbabwe stand out for the development of their ornamental industry within the sub-region and worldwide (Matthee et al., 2006; Mrema & Sauriri, 2014; Netnou-Nkoana & Eloff, 2012). Their position, I believe, relates to a combination of historical facts that differentiate these two countries from their neighbours. South Africa and Zimbabwe received more colonial settlers than the other countries represented in my sample (Bennett & van Sittert, 2019; Ginsburgh, 2022; Limb et al., 2010; Mgadla, 2014). Particularly relevant in the context of this research, the dominance of Dutch and British colonial powers also led to the spread and dominance of Western European gardening traditions that tied in with notions of orderliness, familiarity, and status. This phenomenon formed the basis for building global horticultural empires, whose legacies persist in the present global and sub-regional market, as the above-mentioned British and Dutch descendant family monopolies in South Africa exemplify. Their influence continues to shape everyday gardening in the former metropolises and colonies (Alcorn, 2023; Alcorn & Holloway, 2020; Altman et al., 2022; Bennett & van Sittert, 2019; Canavan, Richardson et al.,

2019; Kuhn, 2023; Netnou-Nkoana & Eloff, 2012; van Sittert, 2003). Compared with Namibia and Botswana, the more benevolent conditions for sedentary farming in South Africa and Zimbabwe led to more extensive colonial settlement and, thus, horticultural development at large scales. Southern African indigenous flora, especially the Western Cape flora and the exotic flora successfully cultivated in Southern Africa, has also shaped the ornamental sector worldwide, with native species of *Agapanthus*, *Protea*, and *Aloe* and rose exports amongst the most valuable in the demanding European and global markets (Hughes et al., 2015; Mrema & Sauriri, 2014). Hence, historical and geographical facts have shaped South African and Zimbabwean ornamental industries. These industries, in turn, have influenced the countries themselves, the sub-region, and the world. The industry, hence, also reflects the historical geopolitical hegemony of South Africa in the sub-region and, more specifically, the persisting socio-economic powers of the former colonial rulers and their descendants.

5.4.2 The significant and contested informal sector

Road selling characterises the sector in the sub-region, usually considered informal or “illegal”, as one Zimbabwean landscaper opined (ornamental industry staff Caroline). Referring to Zimbabwe, one of the environmental professionals said:

“[...] Here [in Zimbabwe] we are very different [from South Africa]. I would say that 80 to 85% of our nurseries are in the informal sector, called ‘side of the road’ nurseries. They are not registered businesses. They have no websites. They have no registered contact details. Ownership changes sometimes on a monthly basis [...]”

(environmental specialist Leyla)

According to a professional, “in almost any urban settlement” across Zambia, “you can find florists” (environmental specialist Michelo). Another Zambian specialist said that in Lusaka, there is “a proliferation of small nurseries popping up in all parts of the city” (environmental specialist Ryan), and quickly growing plants are sold to make extra money. In Botswana, however, road selling does not mean illegality or informality per se, as some participating road sellers have licensed backyard nurseries.

It was usual to hear well-established formal business owners saying that informal businesses are an unfair competitor because they do not pay taxes nor water bills, usually selling easily propagated plants at lower prices. However, these views vary across the sub-region. A garden centre owner and a landscaping company owner based in Botswana said that they do not have problems with the informal sector, as long as it is small, in the form of backyard nurseries.

They even said that they support those small backyard nurseries. However, about informal businesses in their country, a Zimbabwean nursery owner said:

“[...] we have a lot of our indigenous guys, who've got no shoes that you would have seen on the side of the road. They are all illegal, did you know it? [...] That's how people are surviving in this country and we've just come to accept that they are there. They sell the plants for half the price of it would be...So we've just accepted them as part of our dynamics. They prove that they're not going to change it. It becomes a racial thing sometimes and so we've just learned to live with them [...].”

(ornamental industry staff Gerrit)

Regarding relationships with customers, a Botswanan backyard nursery owner stressed that customers tend to think road sellers are desperate; hence, they bargain more than they would if they bought from supermarkets, franchises, or the biggest garden centre in Gaborone. This tendency is unfair to her, dismissing the efforts and love that road and backyard nursery sellers put into growing and selling plants. In Windhoek, Namibia, we witnessed the tensions between road sellers and the leader of an initiative to clear the city from invasive cacti (Cactus Clean-Up, n.d.). Some road sellers sell cacti despite the group's persuasion to sell alternatives.

Per my observations, the sector increasingly provides formal and informal livelihoods for ethnic majorities, especially middle-aged women. Young to middle-aged men are not an exception, particularly as hard labourers in bigger businesses. It was common to hear amongst backyard nursery owners (and road sellers) in Botswana that, although they have always loved working with plants, taking their love to a business level responded to situations such as retirement, unemployment, and/or the need for money. Two environmental professionals from Zimbabwe and Zambia also mentioned this trend. Women dominated my sample, which environmental professionals from Botswana and Zimbabwe highlighted as sector characteristics. We observed that while ethnic minorities (e.g., white, foreign residents) and majorities share the “formal” side of the sector, white, usually family-run businesses, and/or foreign residents who employ ethnic majorities, run the biggest and better-established businesses (in terms of reputation, duration, and scale). In contrast, the “informal” side, usually in the form of road selling and backyard nurseries, comprises ethnic majorities (Appendix 2).

The sector's “informality” across the sub-region is widespread in African countries, which, according to Zein-Elabdin (2009), is one of the many expressions of the postcolonial hybridity (i.e., deep cultural mixing resulting from the colonial processes) found in African countries. The so-called informal sector provides economic opportunities to those often excluded or

retired from “formal” employment (Bandauko & Arku, 2024; Biao, 2017; Mukubu Pika et al., 2024; Mitullah, 2003). Mukubu Pika et al. (2024) report that young to middle-aged men are road plant sellers in Kinshasa (Democratic Republic of Congo). In a study of roadside vending in Gaborone (Botswana), although not explicitly referring to plant selling, Biao (2017) highlighted that 91% of the vendors were middle-aged women, further arguing that roadside vending in Botswana represents “a significant domain of adult workforce in the country.”

The industry reflects the social inequalities and segregation rooted in colonial and Apartheid times. While historically privileged groups conserve their power within the industry—having the formality before law and society and usually bigger businesses—informality is limited to historically segregated groups. Laws prohibiting street/roadside vending or hawking in Africa originate from colonial administrations and aim to suppress indigenous people’s livelihood activities and rights, having not substantially changed in postcolonial times (Bandauko & Arku, 2024; Mitullah, 2003). Not surprisingly, thus, insecurity, vulnerability, and instability—the marginalisation recipe—are usual in this prevalent “informal” economy, which my results reflect, other authors (Bandauko & Arku, 2024; Biao, 2017; Mukubu Pika et al., 2024) highlight across Zimbabwe, Botswana and the Democratic Republic of Congo. As my results highlight, these influence their interactions with “formal” businesses and clients, forging conflictive interactions and perceptions amongst them. Geographical nuances, nonetheless, are noticeable. Tensions felt stronger in Zimbabwe and Namibia than in Botswana. White minorities ruled Zimbabwe and Namibia under colonial and Apartheid regimes. These countries experienced the anti-colonial independence movements that later became the ruling political parties in the postcolonial and Apartheid states (Melber, 2019). On the other hand, Botswana was a “minimalist colonial state” (i.e., a land-locked arid enclave that was not important for the colonial powers as its resource-rich or strategically positioned neighbours) that after independence became a multiracial state⁵ amidst Apartheid states, sheltering people escaping from the surrounded segregation (Mgadla, 2014). Colonial legacies, tribalism, and segregation still play significant roles in these countries’ collective societal mindsets, reflected in the tensions perceived with the informal sector of the economy (Bandauko & Arku, 2024).

⁵ However, I do recognise that even in multiracial Botswana, historically nomadic minorities (the different Khoe-San ethnicities) have been systematically oppressed by the state (Molosi-France, 2018), as well as other ethnicities that are not part of the leading Tswana-speaking group. Werbner (2002) provides an interesting analysis of the case of Kalanga in Botswana.

5.5 Factors shaping the sector

The questionnaires and other interactions highlighted that demand is the most important factor driving the sector from the businesses' perspectives, along with costs related to sourcing and maintenance (Appendix 18). End-users raised factors related to plant traits and services, culture, and market dynamics (Appendix 18). Moreover, utilitarian (as food or medicine) and traditional and spiritual values play a significant role in people's preferences (Appendix 18). Participants also highlighted that the ease of propagation and maintenance, growth speed, and water use also inform people's decisions (Appendix 18). In the following two sub-sections, I describe two themes that group these factors, discussing them further based on the available literature.

5.5.1 Colonial legacies and Western consumer culture shape modern ornamental preferences and practices

Referring to the weight of demand, a Zimbabwean professional (environmental specialist Leyla) explained that, due to its high demand as an ornamental grass, nurseries in Harare have been forced to stock feather grass (*Cenchrus setaceus*). In her words, this grass is “hugely, hugely problematic, completely unpalatable to grazing animals and invades our indigenous grasslands”. In Botswana, stakeholders claim that roses are so popular that businesses must stock them, even if the direct costs (importing, water, plague control, fertilisers) are high. About roses, a backyard nursery owner said:

“There are plants that are not easy to grow, like the roses, but customers like them a lot, so I am planning to pass a course in South Africa on how to grow roses.”

(ornamental industry staff Joy)

One of the Zambian professionals, a private environmental consultant with a plant nursery, noted that during COVID-19 restrictions, demand increased due to ‘people spending much more time at home and then wanting to do more landscaping’ (environmental specialist Ryan). For backyard nurseries and road sellers in Botswana, the COVID-19 restrictions had variable effects on demand, depending on their relative locations to their customers. A road seller in Gaborone said that demand increased during restrictions. In contrast, backyard nurseries in Selebi-Phikwe, whose primary clients are road sellers in Gaborone, said the movement restrictions resulted in a sharp decrease.

The supply and demand scheme relates to another feature some participants mentioned: consumerism. According to a Botswanan environmental specialist's reflection, consumers are:

“[...] hungry of a new plant, so that makes the breeders to work, work... coming up with a new variety, coming up with a new plant with one or two characteristics [...]”

(environmental specialist Seloapi)

In that sense, a Zimbabwean nursery owner implicitly talks about the consumer culture embedded in the industry when referring to a typical customer’s behaviour of buying plants for inappropriate places:

“[...] Lastly, everyone comes in and says: I want a plant that will live in the bathroom. And bathrooms normally are hot, humid and dark. So, they kill it. So, they keep it for three months and then it dies and then they come back, which is great for us 'cause I keep on selling it.”

(ornamental industry staff Gerrit)

Participants said that fashions and trends influence demand and offer, and thus, the market consumer culture. In Botswana, for example, where, according to a landscaping business owner, “the gardens were just sand traditionally,” “formal gardens like your formal French, English gardens” (ornamental industry staff Petrus) have become trendy. We observed that many households in Botswanan villages practice some of the ‘traditional’ gardening practices, where a woman carefully sweeps the sand in the front yard, usually made of bare sand with central trees. Some participants explained that this is aesthetically pleasing and helps detect snake tracks, although others questioned the need for this practice when snake populations are decreasing in urban areas. Areas of swept bare ground are slowly being replaced with grass lawns. Referring to fashions and trends in Zambia, a professional said:

“[...] what is driving a lot of gardening and landscaping in Zambia is [...] garden voyeurism, where somebody sees either somebody within Zambia that's done something that they really liked or even pictures from gardens overseas [...] where, then, people are trying to recreate what they've seen on Google in another style. So, there isn't much of a style of the ornamentation industry in Zambia, only usually follows trends on what is happening elsewhere [...]”

(environmental specialist Ryan)

Regarding Zimbabwe, an environmental specialist said there is “a huge post-colonial hangover” (environmental specialist Leyla) in the ornamental industry and practice. According to her, when she started pushing for native plants in gardening, “white-owned” businesses in Zimbabwe were initially reluctant to deviate from what their ancestors —colonial settlers— used to grow back in South Rhodesia. Although that previous reluctance has changed, according to her, “wealthy housewives” (environmental specialist Leyla) still love maintaining

lawns and alien hedge plants. Indeed, observations noted that well-off Zimbabweans in Harare dedicate significant resources to their lawns and hedges. Two other participants, a business owner based in Botswana and a Zambian environmental professional, said that wealthy women from both countries usually buy alien plants.

Based on my interactions and observations, lawns, water features, and combinations of gravel for planting are sought-after styles. The lawns are as strikingly popular as they are controversial. Referring to the social roles and environmental implications of lawns, three participants from Zimbabwe, Botswana and Zambia said:

“We also live in a country [Zimbabwe], where a green garden is a wealth status. A green lawn is a wealth status [...] If you don't have a green flashy lawn, you are not considered wealthy or rich. [...] a lot of it in this country is a wealth status: beautiful garden, and roaming lawns and full flower beds [...]”

(ornamental industry staff Caroline, Zimbabwe)

“I understand why some people want it [lawn], 'cause it's nice for children to play on soft grass. So, there's a lot of reasons to have lawn. I think lawn has been fundamental around the world, but I think there's a different approach and now that we have these fake lawns, you can actually use them really nicely. That's what I've got. So I don't have any lawn in my garden, just because you spend so much time on water on [...] I cannot have that big one, but that smell of fresh cut grass is quite wonderful. I'm sure it's something that other people don't wanna get rid of.”

(ornamental industry staff Sofia, Botswana)

“[...] Lusaka has limited water resources and if we continue just to pump out and maintain your green grass, at the height of the dry season that is a huge waste of water! [...] Unfortunately, Lusaka is a massively growing city, so that demand on water resources is increasing year on year [...]”

(environmental specialist Ryan, Zambia)

Participating landscapers say trends are moving towards hard landscaping, replacing lawns with static features like sandstone gravel and paving, and encouraging water-wise gardens. In Botswana, for instance, after a severe drought hit in 2012, the government prohibited using clean water for gardening, thus accelerating the move towards hard landscaping. As mentioned above by one of the participants, artificial lawns have also become popular as a solution for the high water consumption of lawns. However, another landscaper based in Botswana argues against it for its environmental implications:

“People love their lawns here. In the dry times, they did change to artificial grass. But we don't support artificial grass at all, because it's trillions of km of plastic, which is

going to end up on a dump site and burnt and pollute there [...] If a client would insist on it, then they do have to find a different contractor. We're just quite against it because of the amount of plastic and it's also not environmentally friendly at all. It becomes very hot. Even paving is better [...] I'd rather gravel down, 'cause even in gravel you can have something better with the water going into the soil and this being absorbed. [...] I mean it [artificial grass]'s got its place. I suppose if it's on a rooftop and people have something just to make it green. Otherwise, no[...]"

(ornamental industry staff Petrus)

Moreover, a Zimbabwean landscaper based in Botswana (ornamental industry staff Sofia) generalised that “anything that does not come from here that looks good” would be ornamental, which other participants from the industry confirmed. A Namibian nursery owner, who specialises in Southern African native trees, admitted that around 40 % of his profits only come from the alien flowers section. A Namibian environmental professional commented that people often do not use native plants for gardening because they are perceived as “drab or just wild and not garden worthy” (environmental specialist Sandra). Moreover, a Botswana environmental professional said that most native Southern African trees are deciduous and/or slow-growing, discouraging customers from adopting them. In addition, native plants or bush plants—as they are contentiously named—are associated with “poverty and underdevelopment.” A Botswana professional added:

“[...] It is, in the simplest form, about black and white. As in black things are bad, white things are good. So, anything that comes from white is good, thing that comes from black is bad [...] ‘Setlhare sa sekgowa’, meaning it is an English tree. With English, they are saying ‘It is a white people’s tree or plant’. ‘Se Tswana’, it is a Setswana tree or plant, so is local. So, they are able to say ‘I do not want Setswana plants, I want English or white...[...]"

(environmental professional Thato)

Apart from the historical European colonial influence, other colonial-related migrant groups like Indians are influencing the industry. In the words of a Zimbabwean landscaper based in Botswana:

“Palm trees, obviously everyone loves them 'cause it gives that kind of beach concept, but I think there's a large Indian population here and I think that was maybe where it started to become super popular because they really love the palm trees. It gives them the sense of home, I guess..."

(ornamental industry staff Sofia)

Movements towards “wild indigenous” gardens are also increasing. According to several participants from the industry, people are slowly becoming more conscious of climate change and the environmental crisis. However, according to participants, usually, wealthy people — “who earn in USD” (environmental specialist Ryan), as a Zambian professional put it— can afford and are interested in those gardens. In addition, three participants from Zimbabwe and Botswana raised concerns over the poor availability of “indigenous species” in the market and the slow bureaucracy around permits to access “indigenous plants” as compared to how easily “exotic plants” can be accessed. Related to this, two professionals from Zambia and Namibia highlighted the serious risk the wild plant trade poses to endangered plant species in Southern Africa.

Socially privileged groups of the population are publicly leading the trends toward indigenous gardens while the Indigenous traditional knowledge related to plants and nature is eroding. According to participants from Namibia and Botswana, this Indigenous traditional knowledge:

“[...] is not being passed down like it used to be [...]”

(environmental specialist Katy, Namibia)

“[...] is not being kept because there is no reason anymore to have it, apparently [...]”

(ornamental industry staff Sofia, Botswana)

A Zimbabwean environmental professional reflected on this knowledge erosion as follows:

“[...] the youngest generation in Africa have grown up exposed to ‘western’ media, wanting the British lifestyle or the American [...] Because I think most of them have grown up seeing their mothers, fathers, grandparents poor, planting in fields and trying to send them to school. When they go to school, it is all about maybe business, not necessarily hands on stuff with nature. Because the hands-on stuff with nature they have grown up seeing from the older generation is all connected somehow to poverty [...]”

(environmental specialist Tinotenda)

The consumer culture, linked to the colonial legacies in modern practices, shows that the medley of ornamental gardening practices in Southern Africa expresses a deep cultural mixing, which, according to Zein-Elabdin (2009), typifies the African postcolonial states. The socio-cultural legacies imposed by the colonial processes and the ongoing globalisation of the capitalist modern development concepts also influence gardening practices in the sub-region (Davoren et al., 2016; Matthee et al., 2006). Studies on gardening and landscaping styles in communities in South Africa have highlighted changes in aesthetic values, landscaping approaches, and plant uses from ‘traditionalist’ rural areas to modernised urban areas (Davoren et al., 2016; Jansen van Vuuren et al., 2020; Molebatsi et al., 2010; Nemudzudzanyi et al.,

2010). For instance, the Batswana and AmaZulu gardens have undergone a replacement of typical functional micro-gardens (e.g., “unmanaged/wild areas” for animal grazing in tshimo [Setswana] and muzi [Zulu]) with lawns and hedges of minimal function (Davoren et al., 2016; Jansen van Vuuren et al., 2020; Molebatsi et al., 2010; Nemudzudzanyi et al., 2010). Similarly, the Mier communities of the South African Kalahari mostly use alien trees for shade and ornamentation nowadays (Shackleton & Shackleton, 2018).

My work suggests that gardening practices and aesthetic values showing different levels of cultural mixing coexist, where subaltern and dominant gardening practices mix and make synergy. Perceptions of beauty have been argued to be a biosocial construct (Altman et al., 2022) that, in turn, interacts with the environmental history of the landscape and its inhabitants (Altman et al., 2022; Haviland-Jones et al., 2005; Huss et al., 2018; Pfeiffer & Voeks, 2008; Wilson, Kendal et al., 2016). The coexistences of diverse aesthetic values and gardening practices seen here are, hence, reflecting socio-historical dynamics linked to the social dimensions and to the anthropogenic transformation of spaces, whereby the use of certain ornamental species and landscaping styles symbolise social status in already heavily modified environments like urban spaces (Altman et al., 2022).

One significant and interesting example emphasised by my participants is the lawn. Lawns have become mainstream in urban planning worldwide since the 20th century when they became an important industry within the ornamental and landscaping sector (Altman et al., 2022; Ignatieva et al., 2020). I interpret that the synergies between capitalist development and the Western colonial legacies have put the lawns as a status mark and an essential element of a modern city in Southern Africa, as in other regions of the world (Ignatieva et al., 2020).

In addition, my work shows that as people become more “modern” and/or wealthier and move to and/or modify these urban spaces, gardens can act as status symbols and reflect an ascent on the socio-economic ladder, according to the mainstream modern concept of human development. Alien plants and foreign gardening styles can then be perceived as symbols of that development and modernisation (Davoren et al., 2016; Jansen van Vuuren et al., 2020; Molebatsi et al., 2010; Nemudzudzanyi et al., 2010). According to Altman et al. (2022), indirect and prestige biases drive aesthetic values, whereby individuals copy aesthetic habits and styles from other individuals or groups with higher social status. An increase in income and possessions comes with a dominance of perceived ideas of Western gardening/landscaping practices in a context of deep cultural mixing. Moreover, as urbanisation processes are similar

around the world —highly influenced by our ecological and biological commonalities as human species and the mainstream capitalist concept of development— Duncan et al. (2011) suggest that urban flora worldwide might converge into a particular set of functional traits, where ornamental features are key.

Wealthy and/or urban people display their privileged status through certain styles and plants that relate to foreign countries and colonial legacies and are expensive to maintain (Davoren et al., 2016; Jansen van Vuuren et al., 2020; Molebatsi et al., 2010; Nemudzudzanyi et al., 2010). Concomitantly, wealthy (and historically whiter) strata in the sub-region have publicly led the movements taking pride in the Southern African nature and encouraging “wild indigenous” gardens —which often resulted in the displacement and discrimination of ethnic majorities and the poor (van Sittert, 2003). As my study shows, “indigenous” gardens are becoming trendy, but their affordability and popularity amongst majorities are in question.

5.5.2 Plants have to be versatile, pretty and fast

Participants highlighted other types of beautiful and colourful plants besides lawn grass. In that sense, a South African nursery owner based in Botswana said that for African people, gardens are preferably for food and medicines as opposed to what he perceived as a Western notion that prioritises aesthetics.

Based on the questionnaires, fruit trees appear like the most popular plants since they are multifaceted, providing food, shade, beauty, protection, and medicinal and culinary herbs. Succulent plants, roses, palms, and annual flowers like petunias are the best-selling strictly ornamental plants (Appendix 19). In Zambia, an environmental specialist said that cultivars of *Echeveria*, *Agave*, and *Sedum* —that South African breeders introduced— have become popular for their foliage and flowers. In Botswana, *Duranta erecta* is one of the most popular plants nowadays. According to the Botswana participants, its versatility (e.g., tolerance of pruning into shapes, the colours of the leaves, the flowers) and the ease of maintenance make it the plant everyone wants. Evergreen trees that provide shade all year round are also important. In that sense, a Namibian environmental professional affirmed that having an evergreen tree in the garden makes “it look so much nicer” (environmental specialist Katy). She exemplified how attractive the green foliage of Prosopis trees (*Neltuma* spp.) looks in the Namibian landscape during the dry season.

Moreover, in the words of a Zambian environmental professional, “instant gratification plays a huge part in the ornamental industry in Zambia” (environmental specialist Ryan), linking back to the consumer culture explained above. A key worker from one of the biggest nurseries in Harare seconded that statement. Moreover, a South African landscaper based in Zimbabwe said that most clients “are very impatient to wait to grow, so they just want it instantly” (ornamental industry staff Linda).

The abovementioned insights show that the ornamental sector in Southern Africa reflects a long-lasting relationship between humans and ornamental plants (Altman et al., 2022; Wilson, Kendal et al., 2016). The factors that participants mentioned as important to inform their decisions about what plants to choose or sell highlight that ornamental plant structures and organoleptic properties fill an emotional/spiritual niche in humans (Altman et al., 2022; Gessert, 1993; Haviland-Jones et al., 2005; Huss et al., 2018; Wilson, Kendal et al., 2016). Some popular plants in the sector (e.g., rose cultivars of succulent plants like *Sedum*) depend entirely on human intervention. Some authors argue that this is a pattern of a convergent evolution towards an anthropogenic dispersal syndrome (Altman et al., 2022; Gessert, 1993). Other popular plants mentioned by participants (e.g., succulent plants like agaves and feather grass) thrive in human-modified ecosystems (i.e., urban areas). Urbanisation is increasingly a potent agent of selection and evolution (Piana et al., 2019; Williams et al., 2009). Sometimes, these plants fulfill human spirits in exchange for an enhanced propagation probability and competitive superiority. In others, they seize the opportunities humans give them for dispersal and growth, even to the detriment of humans, i.e., weeds (Canavan et al., 2022; Kanapeckas et al., 2016; Wu et al., 2021).

Also, my participants shared here that multipurpose plants are important and dominant in the contemporary urban areas of Southern Africa to satisfy many needs, including food and overall well-being. Hence, multi-functionality is still essential (Sardeshpande & Shackleton, 2023; Semanya & Maroyi, 2020). For example, they highlighted fruit trees that give food, shade and have ornamental value as well, some of which are native and have a long history of use in the sub-region (Esterhuysen & Hardwick, 2017; Sardeshpande & Shackleton, 2023). Concomitantly, alien plants are also important for home gardens. In Limpopo Province, for example, Semanya & Maroyi (2020) show how relevant alien plants are for the Bapedi, Vahvenda, and Vatsonga people due to their many functional roles and ornamental use.

5.6 Conclusions

The ornamental industry in Southern Africa is highly influenced by the industry worldwide, especially the South African industry. Entangled in colonial history, South Africa plays a hegemonic role in it, being the leading supplier and the model to follow in the sub-region. The sector increasingly provides formal and informal livelihoods in urban areas, especially for women. Generally, the ornamental sector and practices show the deep cultural mixing typifying postcolonial states that permeate cultural and economic spheres (Zein-Elabdin, 2009). This phenomenon has been suggested to be essential to understanding the supply chain and production networks of a similar sector like the flower industry in the Western Cape, South Africa (Hughes et al., 2015). The synergies between the human co-evolution with plants, the (neo)colonial legacies, the Indigenous cultures, and the globalised capitalist notion of development shape the sector in many contrasting ways. Alien plants and foreign styles usually symbolise higher social status. However, concomitantly, modern trends towards more geographically contextualised gardening practices and the use of native plants are in fashion, too, often led by socially privileged groups (e.g., whites and immigrants from Global North countries, so-called expats).

Notably, the ornamental sector also pressures the already scarce water resources in Southern Africa. Longer dry periods under climate change and increasing urbanisation come with challenges around water use and other inputs like pesticides and fertilisers for those trendy plants and features businesses cannot afford to stop stocking. The demand for water-wise and succulent plants is increasing in response to the increasing risks of drought. Succulent plants like cacti have invaded the sub-region through the ornamental trade initially (Novoa, le Roux et al., 2017), and several Agavaceae species are considered invasive in South Africa, Zimbabwe, and Zambia (Maroyi et al., 2020; Walters et al., 2011; Witt & Pagad, 2020). Thus, increasing trade and exchange of succulent species could pose risks and generate conflicts if their invasiveness and potential impacts are not addressed (Kaplan et al., 2017; Novoa et al., 2016; 2018). Accidental introductions posing phytosanitary and environmental risks might come concomitantly (Faulkner et al., 2016; 2017; 2020). Increasing interest in indigenous plants also threatens species already at risk of extinction (Hinsley et al., 2025). Managing all those risks becomes even more challenging given the transboundary relations within the industry and the socio-economic framework enveloping these relations.

I have described the ornamental sector in several Southern African countries, unpacking some of the socio-historical, anthropological, and ecological factors shaping the interplay between

the sector and alien plants—ultimately hinting at plant invasions. My results—and their critical appraisal—offer an assessment of the socio-ecological contexts in which invasion management might unfold for the plant invasions derived from the ornamental sector in Southern Africa. Ultimately, this chapter showcases that socially constructed processes throughout the history of Southern Africa have shaped the ornamental sector and, subsequently, its links with alien plants. Being aware of the socio-historical connotations of these links is essential for a more sensitive and ethically sound engagement process with stakeholders when it comes to managing and preventing plant invasions derived from the sector. With this, I refer to the recognition of how the sector reflects long-lasting human-plant relationships and historical processes of supremacy and oppression in Southern Africa. Likewise, gardens and plants reflect individuals and groups’ historical, political, and social contexts and aspirations within this social framework. These considerations should lead to a more participatory and horizontal conversation between stakeholders where power relations are adequately recognised and balanced to deliver fair environmental solutions for different groups of people and nature, with people being part of nature.

6. Stakeholder awareness of plant invasions and perceptions of ornamental invasive plants in Southern Africa

Abstract

Successful management of biological invasions often requires broad societal buy-in. However, invasive plants have costs and benefits that change over time and space, as do views on the need for management. Therefore, it is important to understand how invasive plants are perceived by those who are impacted if management is to be seen as legitimate. In this study, we focus on the ornamental horticulture industry in Southern Africa. The sector has a long history of plant introductions and related invasions, with some studies describing conflicts in managing invasions from South Africa. We expand on these studies and explore how, across the sub-region, the stakeholders involved in the interplay between the sector and environmental management understand plant invasions and perceive invasive ornamental plants. I combined several methods under the umbrella of patchwork ethnography and critical realism. Specifically, we interacted with 78 environmental specialists, 38 ornamental industry staff, and 72 ornamental gardeners from Botswana (104), Namibia (50), Zimbabwe (18), South Africa (13), and Zambia (3). I found that all stakeholder groups broadly understand invasion in the same way they are used in academia and policymaking. Non-specialist stakeholders are often aware of ecological processes like spread and impact, but they do not necessarily use the ‘scientific’ terms to describe such processes. However, participants differed in how they perceived specific plants. These differences relate to their specific interests as potentially influenced by professional roles, socioeconomic and cultural backgrounds, and personal trajectories—all of these are in the context of macro socio-ecological and geopolitical dynamics. Differences in terms used and how people perceive particular plants can lead to conflict. I concluded that relational, balanced, and regular communication between the different stakeholder groups, where the capacities and types of knowledge from all sides are valued and respected, could result in mutual agreement and ensure any subsequent management is seen as legitimate. However, such communication spaces would need to address the racial and classist segregations shaping power dynamics and mutual perceptions and their relations with invasive plants and landscapes.

6.1 Introduction

Invasive species are recognised as one of the five direct drivers of global biodiversity change by, for example, the Strategic Plan for Biodiversity 2011–2020 (CBD Secretariat, 2012) and

the post-2020 Global Biodiversity Framework (CBD Secretariat, 2022) (IPBES, 2019; 2023; Roy et al., 2024). However, while biological invasions have been well conceptualised in ecological and evolutionary terms (Blackburn et al., 2011; Zenni et al., 2017), their social and political implications (and particularly their management) are often contested (Courchamp et al., 2017; Kendle & Rose, 1999; Larson, 2007; Lidström et al., 2015; Rejmánek et al., 2002; Richardson et al., 2008; Richardson & Ricciardi, 2013; Simberloff, 2003; Warren, 2007; 2023; Wehi et al., 2023). According to Courchamp et al. (2017), the notion of invasive species as a cause of biodiversity change has encountered more societal resistance than other causes like pollution, overexploitation, or habitat loss.

Nonetheless, the three main concepts used to define biological invasions (ecological dominance, negative impacts, and the crossing of biogeographical barriers and resulting population growth and spread) and the importance of context to definition are, arguably, widely understood beyond science and policy domains (Fischer et al., 2014; Jones et al., 2024; Junge et al., 2019; Nguyen et al., 2020; Novoa et al., 2024; Oficialdegui et al., 2024; Selge et al., 2011; Schüttler et al., 2011; van der Wal et al., 2011). This situation supports the increasing evidence questioning the idea that there is an information deficit that limits efforts to manage biological invasions (Toomey et al., 2016). More and more studies show that how humans affect and interact with biological invasions is complex (Luat-Hū‘eu et al., 2021, 2023; Shackleton et al., 2022; Wehi et al., 2023; Zengeya et al., 2017). If those tasked with managing biological invasions do not appreciate differences in perceptions and sensitivities, people will increasingly react negatively against management efforts (Courchamp et al., 2017; Crowley et al., 2017; Latombe et al., 2019; Shackleton, Adriaens et al., 2019; Shackleton, Shackleton et al., 2019; Wehi et al., 2023; Zengeya et al., 2017).

The human dimensions of biological invasions depend on an array of hierarchically interrelated factors that vary over time and space (Shackleton, Richardson et al., 2019). Drawing from Shackleton, Richardson et al. (2019) 's framework of people's perceptions of invasive alien species, the critical realist notions of layered and laminated realities (Bhaskar, 1975; Price, 2015) and the notion that biological invasions should be addressed as a population-level phenomenon (Sousa et al., 2024), I use a specific framework to ground my research (Figure 6.1). My framework accounts for how regional and global geopolitics influence how societies, social groups, and individuals develop and relate to non-human species' populations (Ramutsindela et al., 2016).

Figure 6.1: Factors accounting for the human dimensions of biological invasions, based on Shackleton, Richardson et al. (2019)’s framework of people’s perceptions of invasive alien species, Sousa (2024)’s notion that biological invasions are a population-level phenomenon and critical realism (Bhaskar, 1975; Price, 2015). I say that human individuals and groups of human individuals directly interact with populations (and sometimes a few individuals) of the species rather than the species as a category.

Complications in management are likely to arise when there are spatial and temporal differences in who benefits from alien species and who bears the costs of subsequent invasions (van Wilgen & Richardson, 2014; Novoa et al., 2024). Differences in value systems and risk perceptions can also stir conflicts (Zengeya et al., 2017). For instance, the Hawaiian Indigenous community’s perceptions of feral pigs have sparked conflicts with the settler-coloniser conservationists whose proposed management actions do not align with the Indigenous community’s needs and worldviews (Luat-Hū’eu et al., 2021, 2023), reflecting the epistemic and environmental injustices derived from historical power relations. Furthermore, the management of invasive cacti in South Africa has provoked conflicts between those stakeholders whose livelihoods benefit from the cacti abundance and quick spread and those whose livelihoods and properties are negatively affected (Novoa et al., 2016; Shackleton et al., 2011). Similarly, a study in Cape Town (South Africa) documented that nursery businesses’ compliance with the South African legislation focused on alien and invasive species is subject to socio-economic factors, where smaller businesses tend to be less compliant. In contrast, bigger ones have a better capacity to cope with changes to legislation (Cronin et al., 2017).

These examples reflect the factors involved in the relation between people and invasive species (Figure 6.1) and the imperative for a holistic invasion management that considers epistemic, social, and environmental justice. For the management of biological invasions to be successful in tackling the environmental crisis and contributing to nature and people as part of nature, the social and geopolitical context must be considered (Convivial Conservation, 2024; Crowley et al., 2017; IPBES, 2023; Ramutsindela et al., 2016; Shackleton, Adriaens et al., 2019; Powell et al., 2022; Wehi et al., 2023; Zengeya et al., 2017).

Awareness of the need to integrate diverse worldviews and practices in invasion management has increased over the past decade (IPBES, 2023; Kaplan et al., 2017; Novoa et al., 2018; Vimercati et al., 2022; Wehi et al., 2023) as has research on stakeholder engagement (see Shackleton, Adriaens et al., 2019 for a review). These studies highlight that the successful and equitable management of invasions requires meaningful engagement with interested and affected stakeholders (Crowley et al., 2017; IPBES, 2023; Kaplan et al., 2017; Shackleton, Adriaens et al., 2019; Zengeya et al., 2017) and alignment with indigenous and local management frameworks (Wehi et al., 2023). For instance, Novoa et al. (2016) illustrated how a dialogue process between stakeholders bearing the costs and those benefiting from ornamental cacti in South Africa could reach some negotiated settlement. Their work resulted in a proposal for a national cacti management strategy with stakeholder involvement at its core (Kaplan et al., 2017).

The ornamental sector in Southern Africa has had a significant history of plant introductions and spread, leading to biological invasions (Maroyi, 2017; Kobisi et al., 2019; Canavan, Richardson et al., 2019; Richardson et al., 2020). However, related management conflicts and proposals for resolutions have only been documented in South Africa so far (Bennert & Sittert, 2014; Canavan, Richardson et al., 2019; Cronin et al., 2017; Kaplan et al., 2017; Novoa et al., 2016; Novoa et al., 2018). In this chapter, I explore how the stakeholders involved in the interplay between the ornamental industry and environmental management in Southern Africa understand plant invasions and recognise and perceive invasive ornamental plants. I do this to contribute to conflict prevention and management across the sub-region, paying attention to the stakeholder groups whose positions within this interplay could potentially lead to divergent perceptions that complicate the management of plant invasions from the sector. My interest focuses on their perceptions of invasion-related concepts and issues to foster effective communication and mutual understanding while considering broader factors (Figure 6.1) that would ultimately lead to a management that is perceived as legitimate and acceptable.

6.2 Materials & Methods

6.2.1 Philosophical approach

I combined several methods under critical realism and patchwork ethnography to explore people's understandings of plant invasions and perceptions of invasive plants. Critical realism helps explore human perceptions of invasive plants because it acknowledges subjectivity in the research process, the co-constructive and ever-changing nature of knowledge, and the layered nature of realities (Bhaskar, 1975; Braun & Clarke, 2024; Price, 2015). These are fundamental if we, as researchers, seek understanding, conciliation, and justice rather than imposition and epistemic violence, as well as a holistic consideration of factors influencing people's perceptions (Price & Lotz-Sistka, 2015) (see [Chapter 3](#) for further details).

Studies addressing perceptions of invasive species in Southern Africa usually combine different methods (Shackleton et al., 2011; 2015; Mosweu et al., 2013; Shackleton & Shackleton, 2016; 2018; Cronin et al., 2017; Witt et al., 2019; Ngorima & Shackleton, 2019; Gaertner et al., 2017; Kachena & Shackleton, 2024). However, patchwork ethnography consists of the combination of different methods and moments of data generation when a strictly continuous "data collection" period is unrealistic, allowing for inclusivity, empathy, consideration, and flexibility in the research practice (Günel et al., 2020; Günel et al., 2023; Günel & Watanabe, 2024). This approach proved appropriate for ethically developing my research practice, as it occurred during the COVID-19 pandemic and was subject to time, logistical, ethical, and safety challenges. It enabled the research process to adapt to local context and practices, ensuring feasibility and allowing for the best balance between geographical reach, stakeholder coverage, and in-depth understanding while being culturally sensitive and appropriate.

My philosophical and methodological approach allows for reflexivity before and during the research process, giving greater flexibility and capacity for adaptation to changes and obstacles (Braun & Clarke, 2024; Sullivan, 2019). Furthermore, it considers my research practice a socioeconomic activity and livelihood subjected to power relations, cultural perceptions, social interactions, and political consequences (Bhaskar, 1975; Braun & Clarke, 2024; Price, 2015; Rogers et al., 2013; Toomey et al., 2017).

6.2 Recruitment and data generation processes

I assumed that talking to people would give us an idea of what they thought (i.e., experiential qualitative research) (Braun & Clarke, 2022). Based on that, combined semi-structured and structured interviews (questionnaire-based), workshops, informal conversations (in the form of

email exchanges, conversations, and meetings), surveys (online and paper-based questionnaires), participant observations and consultation of relevant websites and documentation pointed out by research participants (see chapter 3 for more details). I selected methods suitable to the geographical area, the type of stakeholder, and the participants' needs and circumstances, as well as mine. Such adaptation and flexibility were necessary for a successful and ethical research practice (Günel & Watanabe, 2024). Recruitment and data generation took place between August 2021 and August 2023. Following a purpose-sampling strategy (Robinson, 2014), I recruited from three (non-mutually exclusive) types of stakeholders, covering the interplay between plant invasion management and the ornamental horticulture industry. These are:

1. Environmental specialists: These include researchers, academics, scientists, university students, government officials, managers, educators, and activists working on a wide range of environmental topics, including biological invasions from five continental countries of Southern Africa (Botswana, Namibia, South Africa, Zambia and Zimbabwe). Members of this group are widely perceived to be key knowledge holders on the topic.
2. Ornamental industry staff: People whose livelihood—or at least part of it—is tied to activities with ornamental plants across the private, non-profit, and governmental sectors (e.g., landscaping businesses, plant nurseries, government offices managing urban spaces) in Botswana, Namibia, and Zimbabwe.
3. Non-professional ornamental gardeners: People who use and/or buy ornamental plants in Botswana, Namibia, and Zimbabwe.

I obtained ethical approval from Coventry University (P120192) before the first phase of online data generation began in August 2021, while COVID-19-related travel restrictions between and within the UK and Southern Africa were in place. This phase focused on environmental specialists. After restrictions eased, a second phase of recruitment and data collection across the three stakeholder groups in South Africa, Botswana, Zimbabwe, and Namibia occurred between May 2022 and August 2023. To facilitate this second phase, agreements with the institutions represented in this paper were established. For Botswana, I obtained a research permit from the Ministry of Environment, Natural Resources, Conservation, and Tourism from Botswana [ENT 8/36/4 LII (38)]. Nonetheless, my ethical principles and those of participants who acted as gatekeepers also informed my research practice there and in the other two countries, Namibia and Zimbabwe, where in-situ research was shorter term and, hence,

research permits were unfeasible (see Maunganidze & Ruggunan [2021] for a reflection on the challenges to obtaining research permits in Zimbabwe for PhD research).

The recruitment strategy combined searches in online sources, conference participant lists, countries' classified advertisements, and snowballing, i.e., asking participants for support in recruiting additional participants across the three stakeholder groups (details in Supporting Information, S1). This study involved 188 participants: 78 environmental specialists, 38 ornamental industry staff, and 72 gardeners (Table 1). Of these, 104 were from Botswana, 50 were from Namibia, 18 were from Zimbabwe, 13 were from South Africa, and 3 were from Zambia.

Table 6.1: Number of participants per type of stakeholder by country and direct data collection method (excluding participant observations because these are indirect interactions).

	semi-structured interviews	workshops	informal conversations	questionnaires
South Africa	3 environmental specialists	10 environmental specialists	none	none
Botswana	2 environmental specialists	42 environmental specialists	10 environmental specialists; 1 ornamental industry staff	14 ornamental industry staff; 35 ornamental gardeners
Namibia	2 environmental specialists	none	2 environmental specialists; 7 ornamental industry staff; 23 ornamental gardeners	3 ornamental industry staff; 13 ornamental gardeners
Zimbabwe	2 environmental specialists	none	2 environmental specialists	13 ornamental industry staff; 1 ornamental gardener
Zambia	3 environmental specialists	none	none	none

I used a semi-structured guide, inviting environmental specialists to share their thoughts about the role of the ornamental sector in plant invasions ([sub-chapter 3.3](#), Appendix 3). The exploratory and semi-structural nature of these interviews allowed for flexibility and a unique flow of each, based on the interactions, with the interviewees free to focus on any related aspects of their experiences ([sub-chapter 3.3](#)).

I conducted two workshops with environmental specialists. One is based at Stellenbosch University's Centre for Invasion Biology in South Africa, where we asked participants to share their opinions about the role of the ornamental sector in plant invasions in South Africa (Appendix 4). The other was the Annual Meeting of the Department of Forestry and Range Resources in Botswana, where we asked officers in open forums to share their opinions and experiences on the topic.

Based on published literature (Touza et al., 2014; Novoa, Dehnen-Schmutz et al., 2017) and the aim of this research, we developed two different but related types of questionnaires for each of the three countries of focus (Botswana, Namibia, and Zimbabwe): one for the ornamental industry staff (Appendix 5) and another for ornamental gardeners (Appendix 6). One of the participants, an environmental specialist deeply involved in the ornamental industry, co-designed the questionnaires. I used these questionnaires for online and paper-based surveys and structured interviews (Table 6.1).

Informal conversations occurred online and in person, where people shared their opinions and experiences about any aspect of the topic in a safe and comfortable space. Many of them occurred unplanned, but we seized opportunities when they emerged. Participant observations occurred when there was no opportunity for a formal process of acquiring written/verbal consent and/or a comfortable conversation. I observed every day (that is, uninterrupted) daily practices in public spaces, including observing business places and/or gardens and/or participating in 'small talk' about topics of interest in public spaces (e.g., public transport, street markets, streets, and social media groups).

Although the abovementioned methods of interactions covered other various aspects of the human dimensions of plant invasions as part of my broader goal in this thesis, this chapter focuses on the awareness of plant invasions, perceptions of invasive plants used as ornamentals, and opinions about awareness of other stakeholder groups derived from interviews, workshops, informal conversations, and participant observations. The questionnaires focused on: i) stakeholders' understanding of the key categories within the introduction-naturalisation-invasion continuum framework (Richardson et al., 2000; Blackburn et al., 2011; IPBES, 2023); ii) familiar invasive plants; iii) perceptions of benefits and costs of familiar invasive plants; and iv) acknowledged sources of information about invasive plants and management.

When possible, I gathered demographic data, including age, gender, ethnicity, and level of attainment in the formal education system and profession. I did not explicitly solicit these in

semi-structured interviews, informal conversations, and observations. However, I could infer them from conversations and interactions (i.e., participants referred to such information directly or indirectly). I did not use pre-defined ethnicity categories in the questionnaires. Forcing categories on participants might be viewed as unethical and could have potentially disrupted engagement, given the colonial and apartheid histories (Funada-Classen, 2013; Ginsburgh, 2022; Hughes, 2010; Limb et al., 2010; Mgadla, 2014). I based each interaction on respect and written and/or verbal consent. However, as indicated above, the nature of some informal interactions did not allow for formal consent; thus, the derived information is considered additional experiential knowledge, acknowledging that it comes from other people.

6.2.3 Data analysis and interpretation

Verbal interactions were either recorded or later transcribed or journaled and later digitalised. I used inductive thematic analysis (TA) to analyse the textual data, adopting a hybrid between the codebook and reflexive TA (Braun & Clarke, 2022). Following my experiential qualitative and critical realist approach, I analysed the text at a semantic level, meaning that we assume that what participants say reflects their realities (Braun & Clarke, 2022). I interpreted the data through deductive and retroductive reasoning. I paid attention to the interactions between the coding categories and the complexity derived from these interactions by familiarising, analysing, interpreting, and reflecting on the data several times in the analytical process. Moreover, I focussed on the nuances in the perspectives of the different types of stakeholders, socio-cultural backgrounds, geographies, and individuals based on the hierarchical framework presented earlier (Figure 6.1).

In addition, I used quantitative content analysis (Sullivan & Forrester, 2019) to find out about the sources of information that non-specialist participants use to learn about invasive species and their management and familiar invasive plants. I counted the frequency of sources and familiar invasive plants that survey respondents (ornamental industry staff and gardeners) mentioned with the Nvivo 1.5's word frequency tool and complemented this approach with ethnographic data. I interpreted participants' perceptions of the three most frequent plants they mentioned. I also noted the invasive species other participants mentioned during the interviews, participant observations, and informal conversations.

6.3 Results

My thematic analysis generated the following themes: 1) the importance of the human agency, 2) the ambiguity and relevance of boundaries, 3) negative impact as a benchmark, 4) plant

recognition driven by perceived impact, and 5) awareness influenced by historically determined socio-economic factors and tacit knowledge. I unpack these five themes below, adding the quantitative content analysis of the survey. First, I describe participants' understandings of plant invasions by focusing on the first three themes that connect to their awareness. Second, I specify the invasive plants that participants were familiar with and describe their perceptions of the three most frequently mentioned invasive plants, which exemplifies the fourth theme. Third, I talk about the information, knowledge sources, and ways people become aware of invasive plants and biological invasions, which relates to the fifth theme.

6.3.1 Understanding of plant invasions

When asked in the survey to explain what the terms 'alien,' 'native,' and 'invasive' mean regarding species, more than half of the questionnaire respondents (45 out of 79) from Botswana, Namibia, and Zimbabwe were able to conceptualise those terms. Less than half of the ornamental gardeners responded (22 out of 49), compared to more than a third of ornamental industry staff (23 out of 30).

Respondents' definitions related 'alien' to plants originating from other geographical areas and/or countries that did not "naturally grow" in or that "do not belong" to the area where the plants are now. They contrasted them to 'native' plants occurring naturally in the area. Respondents often referred to 'alien' plants related to human spaces and/or actions, while 'native' plants occur independently of human agency. In that sense, two ornamental gardeners touched on a temporal reference point for 'native' plants in the country "long before people came here" (ornamental gardener Ben). Other participants (both survey respondents and others with whom there were interactions other than the survey) used socio-ecological characteristics to define species, such as "evergreen" or "for beautifying" for 'alien' plants and "wild" for 'native' plants. Interestingly, a survey respondent from the ornamental horticulture sector in Botswana defined native plants as combining the perception of wildness with increasing social values:

“Wild trees that we find in the wild, that you never used to buy then, but now we do.”
(nursery owner Gaone)

Respondents provided spatial boundaries for their definitions, be it at the scale of biome, country, continent, area, region, or even home, with country and region being the most common. In that sense, an interviewee of Zimbabwe's plant nursery highlighted the ambiguity of scales, questioning whether the extent of the boundary was appropriate for species to be

considered native or not, exemplifying the issue by contrasting Madagascar with continental Africa:

“[...] Are you a purist indigenous person, or do you bring things from where? So, this is sort of southern Africa, but does Madagascar come into it or not? [...]”
(nursery owner Vicky)

This ambiguity was also apparent when we asked survey respondents to share plant examples for each of the three terms. Their responses reflected the degree to which some considered boundaries and their position when referring to African island states in their conceptualisation. When asked about the definition of ‘alien,’ only four survey respondents incorporated judgment about the traits and impact of plants into the definition of ‘alien.’ In contrast, such judgments were recurrent for the term ‘invasive.’ Three of these respondents were Namibian ornamental gardeners, using connotations of threat to ‘native’ plants and uncontrollable growth. In contrast, the other respondent from Zimbabwe (landscaper Gladys) said that ‘aliens’ do not “threaten the environment.”

Respondents related the term ‘invasive’ to three main concepts: 1) fast and uncontrollable spread; 2) harm to the environment, wildlife, and humans; and 3) undesirability, usually used in a single definition. Five respondents referred to spread or “taking over” with no further connotations. In contrast, several others went beyond, mentioning displacement, harm, and undesirability, such as poisonous plants, breaking infrastructure, or killing other species. In this sense, a Batswana nursery owner added: “Overall, if the plant is invasive, it becomes a weed, so you remove it” (nursery owner Joy). Likewise, a nursery owner from Zimbabwe illustrated her view on ‘invasive’ species, highlighting the importance of the general environmental impact of plant species for her perception of this category:

“[...] those plants that eventually are not good for the environment. Either they choke other plants, or they choke river flows, or something like that. Therefore, as a nursery, we do not encourage such plants. We try not to distribute those plants, because we know that at the end of the day, it is not good for the environment.”
(nursery owner Angelica)

Amongst the survey respondents from the ornamental horticulture sector, only two specified the biogeographical origin of the species when defining ‘invasive’ as alien, while ornamental gardeners frequently mentioned this. A Namibian gardener defined ‘invasive’ and ‘alien’ with the same concept, while another said ‘invasive’ could be “exotic or indigenous” (ornamental gardener Roy). Additionally, an interviewee from Botswana explicitly said that there are “a couple of indigenous ones that are invasive as well” (landscaper Sofia). In that sense, a South

African specialist referred to ‘native’ species as being extra-limital in South Africa, which are weedy “but not very weedy” (environmental specialist Joshua). Overall, both stakeholder groups in Namibia and Zimbabwe connected non-nativeness to perceptions of negative impacts relatively more frequently. Within Botswana, participants with origins in South Africa or countries in the Global North and /or who have been educated in South Africa also showed that connection more frequently.

6.3.2 Familiar invasive plants and perceptions of them

Survey respondents from the industry mentioned 23 plants they recognise as invasive, while gardeners mentioned 31 (Appendix 17). Between the two stakeholder groups, the three most frequent plants were prosopis (*Neltuma* spp.), cacti (including prickly pears), and lantana (*Lantana camara*) (Table 6.2). Participants from all the stakeholder groups mentioned these species and others in the interviews and informal conversations (Table 6.3).

Table 6.2: Invasive plants mentioned by surveyed ornamental gardeners and ornamental industry staff. The relative frequency of plant names was calculated using the Nvivo 1.5 word frequency tool. We use Plants of the World from the Royal Botanical Gardens Kew for scientific names. Common names are used as the participants mentioned them.

Species	Weighted percentage (%) amongst ornamental industry staff	Weighted percentage (%) amongst gardeners
prosopis (<i>Neltuma</i> spp.)	6.82	16.22
lantana (<i>Lantana camara</i>)	6.82	5.41
prickly pears (<i>Opuntia</i> spp.)	2.27	9.46
water hyacinth (<i>Pontederia crassipes</i>)	9.09	not mentioned
tecoma (<i>Tecoma stans</i>)	2.27	6.76
jacaranda (<i>Jacaranda mimosifolia</i>)	6.82	1.35
cacti	not mentioned	8.11
thorn apples (<i>Datura</i> spp.)	not mentioned	8.11
syringa or Chinaberry (<i>Melia azedarach</i>)	2.27	4.05
rubber vine (<i>Cryptostegia grandiflora</i>)	2.27	4.05
<i>Eucalyptus</i> spp.	4.55	1.35
fountain grass (<i>Cenchrus setaceus</i>)	2.27	2.70
wonderboom or leucaena (<i>Leucaena leucocephala</i>)	2.27	2.70

Table 6.3: Invasive plants mentioned by participants from the three stakeholder groups involved in the interplay between the ornamental sector and invasion management in three countries of Southern Africa (environmental specialists, ornamental industry staff, and ornamental gardeners). The species order is alphabetical.

Species	Botswana	Namibia	Zimbabwe
Aquatic plants (<i>Pontederia crassipes</i> , <i>Salvinia molesta</i> , <i>Azolla</i> spp.)	x	x	x
Cacti (particularly <i>Opuntia</i> spp.)		x	
<i>Cryptostegia grandiflora</i>		x	
<i>Lantana camara</i>			x
<i>Melia azedarach</i>	x		
<i>Neltuma</i> spp. (named as <i>Prosopis</i>)	x	x	
<i>Tecoma stans</i>	x		

Moreover, the environmental specialists from Zambia mentioned two species that survey respondents: *Salvinia molesta* and *Tithonia diversifolia*. A gardener in Botswana mentioned two plants that the survey respondents had also mentioned: *Tithonia rotundifolia* and *Zinnia peruviana*. The ornamental industry staff in Zimbabwe also mentioned three plants that survey participants had brought up: avocado (*Persea americana*), privet (*Ligustrum lucidum*), and *Eucalyptus* spp, while industry staff in Botswana mentioned three: *Schinus molle*, *Ricinus communis* and thorn apples (*Datura* spp.). A Namibian specialist mentioned two that survey respondents brought up: castor oil bush (*Ricinus communis*) and thorn apples (*Datura* spp.). In addition, environmental specialists, ornamental industry staff, and gardeners referred to other species as being invasive in localised areas in Botswana, South Africa, Zambia, and Zimbabwe that survey respondents did not bring up (Table 6.4).

Table 6.4: Plants mentioned by participants as being invasive in localised areas in four countries of Southern Africa. The species order is alphabetical.

Species	Botswana	Zambia	Zimbabwe	South Africa
<i>Acacia</i> sp.	x			
<i>Acacia mearnsii</i>			x	
<i>Alianthus altissima</i>	x			
<i>Alternanthera</i> spp.	x			
<i>Asclepias latifolia</i>	x			
<i>Bauhinia variegata</i>			x	
<i>Cenchrus</i> sp.	x			
<i>Dolichandra unguis-cati</i>			x	
<i>Grevillea robusta</i>	x			
<i>Nephrolepis</i> spp.			x	

<i>Mimosa pigra</i>		x		
<i>Parkinsonia aculeata</i>	x			
<i>Phragmites australis</i>	x			
<i>Prunus</i> sp.			x	
<i>Psidium guajava</i>			x	
<i>Schinus terebinthifolia</i>	x			
<i>Solanum mauritianum</i>			x	
<i>Verbesina encelioides</i>	x			
<i>Vernonanthura polyanthes</i>			x	
<i>Tipuana tipu</i>				x
<i>Tribulus terrestris</i>	x			
<i>Vachellia xanthophloea</i>	x			
<i>Xanthium spinosum</i>	x			

Prosopis (*Neltuma* spp.)

Participants from Namibia and Botswana mentioned this taxon. However, only the Namibian participants elaborated on their perceptions. Notably, members of the Namibian Botanical Society strongly highlighted how ‘invasive’ and detrimental to ecosystems prosopis species (now *Neltuma* spp.) are in Namibia. One referred to the fact that one of the prosopis species is called *suidwesdoring* in Afrikaans—meaning Southwest (part of the colonial name for Namibia) thorn—to signify how widespread the species has become in Namibia.

Nine gardeners from Namibia gave their opinions about the benefits and costs of Prosopis. According to two of them, prosopis has no benefits. One of them said that trees are difficult to control, which a respondent from the industry also described. The other respondent referred to the fact that Prosopis is invasive as a cost, adding its effects on children’s asthma. The other seven respondents referred to its qualities as fodder (that another respondent from the industry also mentioned), as shade trees, timber, and firewood. According to two Namibian specialists, prosopis trees were introduced into the sub-region as fodder. Two of them added that pods are edible for humans, one specifying that kids eat them because of the pods’ sweetness, which two Namibian specialists also noted.

Regarding its qualities for shade, one respondent told of an instance where they tried to convince farmers to remove prosopis from farms in the Kalahari-Stamriet area but failed because “they were the only shade trees that grew quickly” (ornamental gardener Laila). Another respondent emphasised Prosopis’ growth and dispersal capacities as a cost by saying that Prosopis “grows where other trees do not/cannot” (ornamental gardener Roy). Referring to its hardiness, a Namibian specialist admitted that it provides the much-needed shade in

periods of severe drought where other trees do not have foliage, though acknowledging that prosopis species are “very problematic” (environmental specialist Katy).

The survey respondents also discussed prosopis’ effects on Namibia’s river dynamics. According to them, prosopis trees take too much water, drying riverbeds and “out-competing” or “killing” other species, two of them specifying camelthorn (*Vachellia erioloba*). A Namibian specialist provided a summary that resonates with the perceptions of survey respondents:

“[...] *Prosopis* was brought in for its edible pods, which are nutritious and fed to cattle and goats. That’s been in the country now for over 100 years, brought in originally for its host feed, and has sprayed down some of our rivers such as the Nossob, which is heavily, heavily infested with *Prosopis* trees that is successfully outcompeting the natural indigenous river and woodland of camel thorn [*Vachellia erioloba*] and ana trees [*Faidherbia albida*] [...]”

(environmental specialist Sandra)

Cacti (prickly pears, *Opuntia* spp.)

Participants from Namibia and Botswana and one environmental specialist from Zimbabwe referred to cacti (Figure 6.2) and *Opuntia* (prickly pears) as invasive. Ornamental gardeners from Namibia elaborated on their perceptions of cacti and prickly pears. Of 13 respondents, three said that cacti do not have any benefits, pointing out their invasiveness as a negative impact. In contrast, one respondent said that cacti have no negative impact, referring to their protective use as a replacement for barbed wire as a benefit. In that sense, another respondent said that cacti are used as protection to keep animals away. Likewise, two Namibian environmental specialists commented that cacti are used for privacy protection in the north of Namibia. However, a participant who leads a Cactus Clean-up initiative in Windhoek said that robbers use cacti thickets to hide themselves and their tools.

This initiative, led by one retired member of the Namibian Botanical Society, supported by Windhoek residents from wealthier areas and integrated by young Namibians, has been systematically working to clear Windhoek of cacti (Cactus Clean-Up, n.d.). The group collaborates with the Namibian University of Science and Technology to monitor biocontrol trials distributed throughout the city. The group's public statement summarises the perceptions of negative impacts related to cacti invasiveness and damage to animals that survey respondents shared:

“All sorts of invasive cacti and other damaging plants are taking over the habitat of our Namibian vegetation and they are spreading countrywide at an incredible rapid pace. These alien plants can hurt and kill wildlife and domestic animals. We will end with impenetrable cactus thickets that can be used as strongholds by robbers. If we want to

prevent an entire collapse of our own vegetation, we together have to handle this problem urgently.”

(Cactus Clean-Up Namibia, Cactus Clean-Up, n.d.)

Ten respondents also pointed out related costs to cacti’s invasiveness, difficulties controlling their spread, and effects on other species. The rest of the respondents talked about the benefits of cacti, such as food, fodder, and ornamental plants. In that sense, one industry staff respondent and four gardeners from Namibia pointed out that they have had trouble controlling the spread of cacti (including prickly pears). However, their fast-growing capacities and ease of maintenance benefited two respondents who also praised the beauty of cacti flowers and the deliciousness of the prickly pears’ fruits. On the other hand, one respondent says that cacti are ugly. A respondent over 60 mentioned that they used to make juice from the prickly pear juice, which the leader of the Cactus Clean-up initiative in Windhoek —also in their 60s— described. According to this participant, it was usual for the family to have delicious prickly pear jam and juice during childhood. Two survey respondents mentioned cacti’s capacities to attract birds and insects but also admitted that they spread profusely and form impenetrable thickets. One of them mentioned as a drawback is that most cacti species do not produce usable fruits.

Figure 6.2: Cacti near urban properties in Botswana and Namibia. (a), *Cylindropuntia imbricata* subsp. *rosea* within the limits of a private property in Windhoek, Namibia. (b), *Opuntia* cactus (probably *Opuntia microdasys*) within the limits of private property and near a main road in Selebi-Phikwe, Botswana. Photo (a) by Diana Rodríguez Cala on April 25, 2023. Photo (b) by Diana Rodríguez-Cala on 8 February 2023.

The Namibian Botanical Society, with which many respondents were associated, has worked intensively to raise awareness of cacti invasions ([Botanical Society of Namibia](#), n.d., Figure 6.3). The Cactus Clean-Up leader voluntarily monitors the sale and use of cacti in Windhoek. She has had regular arguments and tensions with some residents who oppose the removal of cacti from their properties (Figure 6.3a) and with road sellers who continue to sell these cacti despite the group leader’s continuous attempt to persuade them by offering alternatives to native plants. According to the group’s leader, landscapers in Namibia are also contributing to the spread of invasive cacti and other invasive plants. During this investigation, we perceived the tensions between the group leader—who is white—and the road sellers—who are black.

Figure 6.3: Entrance of the Namibian Research Botanic Institute, where the Namibian Botanical Society has its regular location in Windhoek, showing posters that are part of an awareness campaign encouraging the public to remove the featured species wherever they are found. (a), Posters of invasive species, such as cacti, are displayed in a ‘Wanted

sign' style. (b) and (c) a box representing a prison for the plant parts to be put there. Photos by Diana Rodríguez Cala on 28 April 2023.

In Botswana, the iNaturalist project that one of the participants coordinates reports at least three cacti species as garden escapes ([@botswanabugs](#), 2022): bunny-ear barrier cactus (*Opuntia microdasys*), tree cholla (*Cylindropuntia imbricata*), queen-of-the-night (*Cereus jamacaru*). One of them, the bunny-ear barrier cactus (*Opuntia microdasys*) (Figure 6.3b), is “taking over,” according to one of the Botswana environmental specialists (environmental specialist Seloapi). A landscape business owner based in Botswana said that many cacti are invasive in the country. However, people intentionally plant some of them, like the species of *Cereus*, because of the beauty of their flowers.

The environmental specialist from Zimbabwe referred to the multiple uses that survey respondents from Namibia mentioned as reasons why cacti, especially *Opuntia*, are so popular amongst rural areas in the sub-region. According to this participant, their succulence and, hence, ease of maintenance is the main reason, given that water is a limiting factor for rural dwellers:

“[...] So, in rural areas someone needs to walk a few kilometres carrying 20-litre bucket of water. And it is very very unlikely that they will then use some of that water to water an ornamental plant. What I can tell you is that in rural areas most of the ornamental plants you find are succulent. *Aloe vera* type and this other one—I can't remember the name—is it *Euphorbia*?... [...] I found the plant, it's called *Opuntia*.

[...] because they don't need watering, but they do bring some flowers... [...] they do bring some fruits [...] They can use to make a live fencing around homes. [...]”

(environmental specialist Tinotenda)

Furthermore, a Namibian environmental specialist pointed out the common confusion people have between typical succulent plants native to Southern Africa, like *Euphorbia* and cacti, which the previous quote denotes as a matter of awareness concern. According to this participant, there is a widespread perception that “cacti come from Africa because it is a dry and arid region” (environmental specialist Katy). We observed this while engaging in informal conversations and observations across Botswana, Namibia, and Zimbabwe.

***Lantana camara* (lantana, tickberry)**

Botswana, Zambia, and Zimbabwe participants shared their perceptions about lantana (Figure 6.4). An ornamental industry respondent from Zimbabwe considered it not worth selling and challenging to control, which two gardener respondents also mentioned. Another Zimbabwean ornamental-related business owner said in an informal conversation that it is “dreadful and her

biggest threat” (supplier Daniella). In that sense, another nursery owner from Zimbabwe described her feelings about lantana because of how its growth and spread capacities have affected a sacred place for her family:

“[...] We have a place where it is our cemetery for the family. We have this lantana bush there. Initially it was a small bush, but we went there after the last rainy season and we couldn't even access the graves. [...] So, it took us the whole day to try to clear up. [...] Well, we tried but we did not finish. [...] But ufffff, that lantana is terrible! It grows very quickly. Before you know it, it has taken over the place [...].”

(nursery owner Angelica)

Four ornamental gardeners from Namibia elaborated on lantana in the survey. Only one said that lantana has no benefit, referring to its behavior as "overtaking natural vegetation" (ornamental gardener Ruben). The rest praised its ornamental qualities as a hedge, which a survey respondent from the Namibian industry also mentioned. These respondents, however, noted its invasiveness as well. One respondent praised its qualities as an ornamental plant but removed it from the garden when they realised it was invasive. Another gardener said it is toxic, and the respondent from the industry said it has medicinal properties. In that sense, an environmental specialist and a nursery owner from Zimbabwe also referred to its toxicity to livestock. According to the specialist, this species is "allelopathic" and "a problem" in the rainforests, specifically Victoria Falls National Park (environmental specialist Tinotenda). According to the nursery owner, hybrid species are in high demand in the ornamental market. Hence, he hopes the new hybrid from Kenya —that sold out when we had the interview— is not toxic.

Another gardener respondent said it attracts fruit-eating birds, but this participant does not like it because it is invasive. Deeming it one of the worst invasive plants in Zambia, a Zambian environmental specialist said that the plant "was thought to be a very nice hedge," but "it escaped because the birds eat the seed, drop it somewhere else, and then it germinates" (environmental specialist Simon). According to this participant, its bird dispersal ability, added to its vegetative reproductive capacity, makes it "very difficult to control" (environmental specialist Simon).

According to a Batswana specialist, lantana "has taken over areas in villages and hillsides" (environmental specialist Seloapi). Interestingly, in an informal conversation with this interviewee and a colleague from the same institution, the interviewee's colleague challenged the opinion that lantana was a problem, arguing that it was good for the soil on farms.

Figure 6.4: *Lantana camara* in the Mukuvisi Forests nature reserve, Harare, Zimbabwe. Photo by Diana Rodríguez Cala on 21 September 2022.

6.4.3 Information and knowledge sources about invasive plants and management

Environmental specialists said that people usually become aware of invasive plants when the spread somehow affects their lives. Specialists from South Africa said that public awareness is usually biased toward tree species that suck water and promote fire. Participants from all countries in the sample often referred to tree species in all categories and survey or interview questions.

One of the South African specialists summarised that knowledge and training on the biological invasion framework are key to becoming aware of plant invasions. Environmental specialists also said that increasing awareness of plant invasions is complex and that environmental personnel are usually not trained to communicate such complex issues to “laymen” (environmental specialist Katy).

When asked about sources of information on invasive species and management, the most frequent sources across both stakeholder groups were community (e.g., societies, church), own experience, training, family, and friends (Figure 6.5). The community was the most frequent source of information for the ornamental industry staff for invasive species and their management. However, training also came out frequently when referring to invasive species (Figure 6.5a and b). Ornamental gardeners frequently mentioned their experiences, family, friends, and neighbours with invasive species and their management. However, newspapers were amongst the most frequent sources for discovering invasive species (Figure 6.5c and d). Both stakeholder groups referred to people from the environmental sector (academics, specialists) and formal education, but this source was less frequently mentioned than the abovementioned sources (Figure 6.5). In addition, participants from Zimbabwe, Namibia, and

Botswana mentioned South Africa as the place where they have been informed, trained, and/or influenced about biological invasions.

Figure 6.5: Sources of information about invasive species (a, c) and management (b, d) that ornamental industry staff (a,b) and ornamental gardeners (b,c) mentioned in the survey. Figure created using the word frequency tool of Nvivo 1.5.

Wealthier, urban, European descendants and foreign residents were perceived to have greater access to scientific information about the topic (as expressed by several of the environmental specialists from Zambia, South Africa, Namibia, and Zimbabwe; ornamental industry staff from Botswana, Namibia, and Zimbabwe; and participant observations across Botswana, Namibia, and Zimbabwe). I observed that people from these particular social groups publicly led most activities to raise awareness of biological invasions. For example, according to one of the members of the Executive Committee of the Namibia Botanical Society, “retired whites” dominate the membership. However, the committee is trying to incorporate “young blacks” (environmental specialist Judith). One of the South African professionals referred to exposure

to formal education as a strong reason to explain that urban and wealthier strata in South Africa are more aware of invasive plants and choose to use native species for their gardens. One of the Zambian specialists said that the more people are exposed to the “Western environmentalist mindset” (environmental specialist Ryan), the greater the awareness of topics such as biological invasions. In addition, some environmental specialists and owners of formal businesses in Botswana, Namibia, and Zimbabwe argued that informal businesses and/or road sellers lack awareness and care about plant invasions. It should be noted that most informal businesses and road sellers self-identify as black or part of a Southern African tribe.

6.5 Discussion

6.5.1 Understanding of plant invasions

The definitions of alien and native species used by participants broadly aligned with either the conceptual framework of biological invasions of Blackburn et al. (2011) or with the most recent global assessment of the topic (IPBES, 2023), which all the countries’ governments included in my sample have agreed to its findings. This finding is similar to what Jones et al. (2024) reported for gardeners in Britain. Ornamental gardeners and industry staff widely referred to core concepts in the invasion science of the human agency, biogeographical boundaries, and timeframe (Pyšek & Richardson, 2010), while also reflecting the ongoing debates in academic circles around those concepts (Courchamp et al., 2017; Kendle & Rose, 1999; Larson, 2007; Lidström et al., 2015; Rejmánek et al., 2002; Richardson et al., 2008; Richardson & Ricciardi, 2013; Simberloff, 2003; Warren, 2007; 2023; Wehi et al., 2023). For example, the debate around the boundaries to define ‘nativeness’ and ‘non-nativeness’ came up through the varying terms participants used to define these concepts and the plant examples they mentioned. Administrative units, shaped by geopolitical boundaries, are the most used scale for management purposes (see the glossary in Zengeya & Wilson, 2023). In that sense, researchers in South Africa are starting to use the term ‘native-alien population’ to describe species populations that result from human-mediated movement beyond a biogeographical barrier and the native range of the species, but that is still within the same country that is part of the native range of the species (Nelufule et al., 2022; 2023). The diversity of terms and scales that participants used to delimit boundaries is therefore understandable, given the geographical context of a vast continental sub-region, where the sizes of countries are relatively large, containing different socio-ecological units and political borders that cut through socio-ecological units that otherwise would have been part of the same whole.

A few participants from the industry in Botswana talked about socio-ecological roles and/or plant traits that do not quite align with the scientific concept. Interestingly, the roles and traits mentioned by these participants could reflect how alien and native plants have been historically perceived and used in Southern Africa. For example, alien species defined as “evergreen trees” or those used “to beautify the homes” could reflect a functional niche alien species have come to fill in people’s homes in a vast, often treeless arid part of the sub-region (van Sittert, 2003; Bennett, 2014; Bennett & van Sittert, 2019), where afforestation attempts spread beyond South Africa’s Cape Colony centuries ago (Bennett & Kruger, 2015). Several studies have highlighted how people develop tight relationships with alien plants in contexts where socio-ecological changes linked to societal ‘development’ have dramatically reduced native species populations and/or native species cannot fulfill the socio-ecological roles that the context and people require (Kachena & Shackleton, 2024; Semanya & Maroyi, 2013; Thondhlana & Shackleton, 2015; Wehi et al., 2023). Although not entirely aligned with the scientific concept, these definitions could represent popular perceptions of the plants tied in with the scientific concept.

Some of the definitions of ‘native’ by ornamental gardeners and industry staff based on wildness and/or better adaptation to “the local environment” also overlap with the scientific definition of established (or naturalised) alien species (Pyšek & Richardson, 2010). As these species have established viable and self-sustaining populations beyond cultivation (Pyšek & Richardson, 2010), they could also be perceived as being “wild” and “locally adapted” as native plants. This perception could be reflected in the fact that cacti are often thought to be from Southern Africa. People observe that cacti are remarkably similar to *Euphorbia* species, probably due to the convergent evolution of succulents (Males, 2017). As one of the environmental specialists recognised, people tacitly correlate the environment with the species’ adaptive characteristics to drylands and observe the species spread ‘in the wild’ (establishment). All that, combined with the relatively long time many of these succulent plants have been in the sub-region (Henderson, 2006; Maroyi, 2017), can reinforce the widespread belief that they are, indeed, typical and belong to Southern Africa (Novoa et al., 2016). Nonetheless, regardless of their knowledge about species distribution ranges and specific names, people from the non-environmental specialist groups can distinguish cacti from *Euphorbia*. I corroborated it by noting people’s reactions when inviting them to observe these plants, pointing out their differences. How relevant it is to differentiate these native succulents from established alien succulents depends on the stakeholders’ interests.

When it comes to the term ‘invasive,’ notions of spread, weediness, negative impacts, and, hence, the need for control were common, echoing the results in other regions (Schüttler et al., 2010; Selge et al., 2011; Junge et al., 2019; Nguyen et al., 2020; Jones et al., 2024). Overall, most of the participants from all stakeholder groups gave more weight to impacts and spread when defining ‘invasive’ than non-nativeness, as Jones et al. (2024) showed for gardeners in Britain. However, unlike gardeners in Britain, who considered invasive in the boundaries of their gardens (Jones et al., 2024), ornamental gardeners and industry staff participating in this research did not confine the meanings of this term to their immediate surroundings, which might reflect that my participants’ sense of place is in a higher socio-ecological scale (e.g., nation). The importance of non-nativeness attributed to the term ‘invasive’ varied between participants within and between stakeholder groups, but, as in other studies, environmental specialists tended to give more importance to it (Selge et al., 2011; Fischer et al., 2014; Junge et al., 2019; Kapitzka et al., 2019). Participants talked about the invasiveness of certain native plant species, which is increasingly becoming a research topic (Nelufule et al., 2022; 2023).

Some definitions from ornamental gardeners and industry staff strictly defined invasive species by generalising a negative impact they experienced with particular plant species (e.g., plants whose roots damage infrastructure, plants that choke other plants). Other studies report similar results, where attitudes towards invasive species and their management are generally informed by perceptions of harmfulness and impact between public and specialist stakeholder groups (Schüttler et al., 2011; Fischer et al., 2014; van der Wal et al., 2014). Similarly, Southern African media emphasise the negative impacts of invasive species (e.g., The Guardian Sun from Botswana [Thobega, 2019; The MidweekSun Admin, 2019]; The Herald from Zimbabwe [EMA, 2014; Gogo, 2015; 2017; Ngomani, 2016; Precious Manomano Herald Reporter, 2024]; Daily Nation from Zambia [Daily Nation, 2021; Nation Editor, 2023]). The negative impact, hence, is a commonly used distinctive benchmark for conceptualising invasive species. This frequent association with harm is a matter of concern and critique since some scholars argue that the most frequent interpretations of the terminology neglect the possibility of benefits coming from invasive species (Kendle & Rose, 1999; Warren, 2007; 2023; Lidström et al., 2015; Wehi et al., 2023).

6.5.2 Recognition of invasive plants and perceptions

It is not surprising that *Prosopis* spp. (now *Neltuma* spp.) and *Lantana camara* were amongst the most frequent invasive plants my participants named. These plants are well-known global invasive species (IPBES, 2023) that make headlines across the globe (e.g., Coghill, 2024; Dall,

2024; Mishra, 2024; Rahman, 2024). More importantly, these species are widespread across Southern Africa (Chikuni et al., 2004; Mosweu et al., 2013; Rejmánek et al., 2017; Shackleton et al., 2017; Vardien et al., 2012; Witt et al., 2017). Therefore, it is expected that their own experience and that of family, friends, and communities of influence were important sources of information. My participants' opinions of them show that perceptions of harmfulness and usefulness influence their judgments, as other studies have documented (Chikuni et al., 2004; Kachena & Shackleton, 2024; Mosweu et al., 2013; Makhorole, 2021; Novoa et al., 2024; Seboko et al., 2024; Shackleton et al., 2007; Shackleton & Shackleton, 2018; Zengeya et al., 2017). Most of the species that participants mentioned (Tables 6.2, 6.3, and 6.4) are typical in urban areas of the sub-region (Mafokate et al., 2013; Seboko et al., 2024) and rural homesteads (Chikuni et al., 2004; Semanya & Mayori, 2020), meaning that participants interact with their populations regularly. As Chikuni et al. (2004) documented for *Prosopis glandulosa*'s invasion in Swang'oma in Malawi and Kachena & Shackleton (2024) for *Vernonanthura polyanthes*' invasion in the Chimanimani mountains in Zimbabwe, invasion processes are subject to macro socio-ecological dynamics (i.e., land use change, climate change, inequalities) and so people's evolving interactions with these species. For example, in Swang'oma, Malawi, the community depends on the firewood that *P. glandulosa* provides; given that deforestation in the area is extensive, use restrictions exist on the native trees left. Most people cannot afford to buy firewood from Mozambican traders. They have learnt to co-habit and use these species in a bio-cultural co-evolution process (Luat-Hū'eu et al., 2021; Pfeiffer & Voeks, 2008). Moreover, plants mentioned by participants (Tables 6.2, 6.3, and 6.4) are considered invasive in at least one Southern African country (Chase & Pagad, 2020; Heath et al., 2020; Maroyi et al., 2020; Robinson et al., 2020; Witt & Pagad, 2020) or alien and are likely to be inconsequential or beneficial (Zengeya et al., 2017).

There were a few native species (*Adansonia digitata*, *Cenchrus ciliaris*, *Chloris gayana*, *Dichrostachys cinerea*, *Nymphaea* spp., *Senegalia mellifera*, *Vachellia nilotica* subsp. *kraussiana*, *Vachellia xanthophloea*, *Terminalia prunioides*, *Tribulus terrestris*) that participants mentioned as invasive, likely because of their high dispersal capacity and/or perceived adverse effects. For instance, *D. cinerea* and *S. mellifera* are well-known encroaching bushes (Nghikembua et al., 2023; Njagi, 2019), while *Adansonia digitata*'s roots can damage infrastructure in Gaborone (as one participant described). In addition, species like *Vernonanthura polyanthes* and *Verbesina encelioides* were mentioned, which have been recently subject of research (Kachena & Shackleton, 2024; Mompoti, 2017) because of their

relatively recent spread across Zimbabwe and Botswana, respectively. Others are considered conflict-generating species in South Africa: *Acacia* spp. (e.g., *A. mearnsii*), cacti (e.g., *Opuntia microdasys*), *Melia azedarach*, *Parkinsonia aculeata*, *Prosopis* spp., and *Psidium guajava* (Zengeya et al., 2017).

6.5.3 Awareness of plant invasions

In this investigation's specific geographical and sectorial contexts, the influence of South African public narratives and education about biological invasions on the participants' perceptions was noticeable. This influence was related to the participants' familiarity with South African education and training regardless of the stakeholder group. South Africa has a world-renowned tradition in the research and management of biological invasions with far-reaching public campaigns and management programs such as the Working for Water Program (van Wilgen & Wannenburg, 2016) and a prevalent history of regional hegemony (Gumede, 2014; Lenggenhager, 2015).

Through my analysis and interpretation, I noticed the underlying socio-historical issues of class and racial discrimination that translate into unequal access to education and scientific communication. Environmental and ornamental industry participants referred to the higher awareness of wealthier, urban, and white groups, and the observations noted the more frequent leadership of these groups in the topic. Research has shown that in South Africa, income, and hence, education and skin colour positively correlate with awareness (Seboko et al., 2024), with elite groups usually having higher awareness of biological invasions (Shackleton et al., 2020). My research shows similar scenarios in neighbouring countries, which are part of the colonial and Apartheid legacies in the sub-region (Biggs et al., 2022; Funada-Classen, 2013; Ginsburgh, 2022; Hughes, 2010; Johnston et al., 2023; Limb et al., 2010; Mgadla, 2014; Ramutsindela et al., 2016; Seboko et al., 2024; Shackleton & Gwedla, 2021; Venter et al., 2020).

However, in contrast to what some specialist participants assumed, non-specialist participants, some of them not necessarily "highly educated," are often aware of biogeographical and ecological processes like plant spread and growth, although they might not use scientific terms to describe their awareness of these natural processes. Tacit knowledge, expressed through people's own experiences, intuition, and those of their extended network, are significant sources of knowledge for our participants, as Rogers et al. (2013) highlight. Nonetheless, mainstream sources of usually unidirectional communication (e.g., media, academics, formal

education) should not be ruled out as they also indirectly and/or directly influence my participants. Notably, the situation described with cacti in Namibia reminds us that more efforts are needed for awareness campaigns and management initiatives to be mindful of the language used (Lidström et al., 2015; Selge, 2011) and not to reproduce social inequalities attached to the synergies between class and skin colour in Southern Africa.

6.6 Conclusions

The understanding of plant invasions did not differ substantially amongst stakeholder groups and individual participants, nor did the scientific conceptual framework. Qualitative differences primarily lie in their perceptions of specific invasive plants, directly determined by what matters to my participants. Their socioeconomic statuses, cultures, worldviews, professional roles, and personal trajectories influence what it is what matters, as many other studies have described (Fischer et al., 2014; García-Llorente et al., 2008; Henke et al., 2024; Kachena & Shackleton, 2024; Novoa et al., 2016, 2018; Pfeiffer & Voeks, 2008; Selge et al., 2011; Seboko et al., 2024; Shackleton, Richardson et al., 2019; Shackleton, Shackleton et al., 2019; van der Wal et al., 2014). As I set out previously (Figure 6.1), those factors are influenced by macro socio-ecological and geopolitical dynamics that are often beyond our empirical senses.

However, despite different interests, different stakeholder groups that could be impacted by managing invasive plants linked to the ornamental horticultural sector in several countries in Southern Africa could find common grounds for mutual engagement. As Zengeya et al. (2017) concluded, an ideal scenario would be a participatory, integrated, and flexible management approach that maximises benefits while reducing negative impacts. This ideal requires respectful, relational, and balanced processes of regular communication between the participants, as Novoa et al. (2016) and Kaplan et al. (2017) have demonstrated with cacti in South Africa. Crowley et al. (2017), McGeoch et al. (2023), and Zengeya et al. (2017) have suggested anticipating and managing conflicts. It is important that environmental specialists — as publicly perceived authorities in the matter— recognise the tacit knowledge that non-specialists have and the influence that segregation and classism inherited from colonial and Apartheid times have on the power dynamics and perceptions of each other amongst stakeholder groups and individuals, and hence, on the relations with invasive plants and landscape.

7. Ornamental horticulture in Southern Africa: strategic actions to address biological invasions

Abstract

Southern Africa has a well-documented history of intentional plant introductions for three ornamental purposes. However, some of these plants have become widespread damaging invaders, and conflicts can arise when stakeholders' attitudes differ towards ornamental plants, plant invasions, and the interplay between the two. I examined the views of stakeholders involved in the ornamental sector and environmental management across southern Africa in light of the strategic actions proposed by the Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services 2023 thematic assessment on Invasive Alien Species and their Control. My analysis is based on semi-structured interviews, informal conversations, and observations with 78 environmental specialists, 30 ornamental industry staff, and 24 plant enthusiasts from Botswana, Namibia, Zimbabwe, South Africa, Zambia, Democratic Republic of Congo, and Eswatini. My analysis shows that although significant efforts are ongoing in Southern Africa to address biological invasions from the ornamental sector, they need more integration and consideration of the broader geopolitical and socio-historical context. I reflected on these needs and recommended 1) improving cohesion and collaboration amongst stakeholders, 2) ensuring pluralism by recognising and valuing marginalised groups, 3) addressing power differences and superiority-inferiority complexes, and 4) seeking alliances with existing sub-regional groups working in the realm of nature-society interplay.

7.1 Introduction

Globally, the ornamental horticulture sector has a long history of human-plant movement and, thus, of plant invasions (van Kleunen et al., 2018). In Southern Africa, alien plants are still widely used and traded as ornamentals across the sub-region (Cronin et al., 2017; Mukubu Pika et al., 2024; Semanya & Maroyi, 2020), and introductions for that purpose might even be on the rise (Faulkner et al., 2023). Hence, several species introduced as ornamentals have become invasive (e.g., cacti). Furthermore, 57% of the alien species that have most expanded their range in South Africa from 2000 to 2016 were ornamental introductions, based on the Southern African Plant Invaders Atlas (Henderson & Wilson, 2017). This trend highlights the invasiveness of such plants and the ongoing and long-lasting effects that introductions for ornamental purposes might have in the sub-region.

The management of some invasive ornamental plants, like cacti, has stirred conflicts in South Africa due to opposing attitudes between, for example, nursery owners and land managers (Novoa et al., 2016; Novoa et al., 2018). Varying attitudes to invasive species management might primarily arise from stakeholders' divergent interests, beliefs, and values, which, in turn, broader socio-ecological (and geopolitical) contexts influence (Biggs et al., 2022; Crowley et al., 2017; Shackleton, Adriaens et al., 2019; Shackleton, Richardson et al., 2019; Shackleton et al., 2020). Invasive ornamental plants can be a livelihood, a hobby, and a liking for some people while damaging livelihoods, life, and the environment for others. Such perceptions can be highly dynamic over time and space (Shackleton, Adriaens et al., 2019; Shackleton, Richardson et al., 2019; Shackleton, Shackleton et al., 2019). Therefore, coordinated and systematic strategic actions that account for such dynamics need to be included to effectively manage invasive species linked to the ornamental sector in Southern Africa. Furthermore, such strategic actions would require closer collaboration across the ornamental sector and neighbouring countries due to the transboundary nature of plant trade and biological invasions.

The first global assessment on invasive alien species and their control by the Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services (IPBES, 2023) recommends an integrated governance approach to biological invasions that takes account of the above-mentioned factors. All the continental state members of the Southern African Development Community accepted this governance framework. However, for an integrated approach to managing invasive ornamental plants in Southern Africa, it is important to consider the differences between the countries.

Firstly, the extent to which each of the countries currently addresses biological invasions varies (which you can see in their reports to the Convention on Biological Diversity, CBD Secretariat, 2022), with South Africa standing out as a global hotspot in research and management (IPBES, 2023). Secondly, an integrated governance approach across Southern African countries would need to reflect and consider the impact of national and regional interventions on the stakeholders involved since their collective engagement determines the success of management strategies (Shackleton, Shackleton et al., 2019). Thirdly, matters of social-environmental ethics and justice would need to permeate the integrated governance approach to avoid entrenching and/or reproducing the colonial and apartheid legacies that persist (Bennett & van Sittert, 2019; Biggs et al., 2022; Johnston et al., 2023; Ramutsindela et al., 2016; Seboko et al., 2024; Shackleton et al., 2011; Shackleton et al., 2020; Shackleton & Gwedla, 2021; Venter et al., 2020).

Building on these premises, I analyse what an integrated governance approach to biological invasions implies for Southern Africa’s ornamental horticulture sector. Providing practical recommendations for more comprehensive management of biological invasions linked to the ornamental horticulture sector in Southern Africa, I reflect on the actions and recommendations that key stakeholders shared with us. I link these recommendations to six strategic action areas proposed by the IPBES’ governance framework (IPBES, 2023). These six actions of focus are the following:

1. Resource innovation, research, and technology
2. Support information systems, infrastructures, and data sharing
3. Engage broadly across all stakeholders and Indigenous Peoples and local communities
4. Share efforts and commitments; understand specific roles of actors
5. Enhance coordination and collaboration across international and regional mechanisms
6. Improve policy coherence

These six actions will be crucial components of the seventh action proposed in the IPBES report—the development of strategies at national and regional strategies.

7.2 Obtaining the views of the stakeholders involved

This research followed an experiential qualitative and critical realist approach (Braun & Clarke, 2022; Price & Lotz-Sistka, 2015) based on: 1) online and face-to-face interactions with 135 people across seven countries (Botswana, the Democratic Republic of the Congo, Eswatini, Namibia, South Africa, Zambia, and Zimbabwe); 2) visits to 59 ornamental related sites in Botswana, Namibia, and Zimbabwe; and 3) participation in five events in Botswana, Namibia, South Africa and Zimbabwe (see Table 7.1 for details). The views expressed by stakeholders on invasive management more broadly and the trade, use, and management of ornamental species more specifically were interpreted in light of the IPBES’s six actions for an integrated governance approach to biological invasions.

Table 7.1: Participants per country and method of interaction to explore actions around managing biological invasions from the ornamental sector in Southern Africa. Activities were conducted between August 2021 and May 2023.

Country	Semi-structured interviews	Informal conversations	Observations
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Botswana	2 environmental specialists	52 environmental specialists; 15 ornamental industry staff; 1 plant enthusiast	Visits to 29 sites; Annual Meeting of the Forestry and Range Resources Departments from Botswana March 2023
Democratic Republic of the Congo	None	2 environmental specialists	None
Eswatini	None	1 environmental specialist	None
Namibia	2 environmental specialists	2 environmental specialists; 7 ornamental industry staff; 23 plant enthusiasts	Illustrated Talk session at the Botanical Society of Namibia in April 2023; Visits to 10 sites
South Africa	3 environmental specialists	10 environmental specialists	Centre for Invasion Biology Meeting, April 2022; South Africa National Symposium on Biological Invasions, July 2022
Zambia	3 environmental specialists	None	None
Zimbabwe	2 environmental specialists	2 environmental specialists; 8 ornamental industry staff	Annual Garden Show September 2022; Visit to 20 sites

Using purposive sampling (Robinson, 2014), I consulted academic publications and conference proceedings. I conducted scoping conversations with existing contacts to identify and recruit researchers, academics, scientists, university students, government officials, managers, educators, and activists working on a wide range of environmental topics, including biological invasions, from the mainland countries of the Southern African Development Community (SADC). I complemented that with a snowballing technique to build on existing networks of research participants. I assigned these participants to a stakeholder group (environmental specialists hereafter) whose professional role has historically positioned them as key knowledge holders (Toomey et al., 2017; Turnhout, 2024). They conduct research, inform and make management decisions, educate, raise awareness, and inform and enforce policies.

I also approached people whose income is linked to the trade and distribution of ornamental plants (ornamental industry staff hereafter). Ornamental industry staff included those working

for landscaping businesses, plant nurseries, and government offices managing urban spaces. It, therefore, included representatives from the private (including informal and formal businesses), non-profit, and government sectors. Initially, I located potential participants from this group through Google Maps and social media groups. Later, I conducted a snowballing approach across the network of environmental specialists and industry participants. With this group, the focus was on Botswana, Namibia, and Zimbabwe.

I included a third group of plant enthusiasts from the same three countries. I defined them as those practicing ornamental gardening and/or interested in invasive plants who are neither environmental specialists nor ornamental industry staff. I used a recruitment and snowballing approach similar to that of the ornamental industry staff group. Occasionally, participants from other stakeholder groups facilitated the recruitment of plant enthusiasts. I defined these groups as non-mutually exclusive, meaning that a participant could be part of more than one group. However, depending on the context in which I recruited them, I assigned them to a specific group.

Using a patchwork ethnography as a methodological umbrella (Günel et al., 2020; Günel & Watanabe, 2024), I interacted with environmental specialists, ornamental industry staff, and plant enthusiasts in different ways. I conducted thirteen semi-structured online interviews with environmental specialists from Botswana, Namibia, South Africa, Zambia, and Zimbabwe through Zoom and WhatsApp. I visited ornamental-related businesses and institutions in Botswana, Namibia, and Zimbabwe, conducted semi-structured interviews and informal conversations, and made observations. I also carried out informal conversations and observations at the following events: Centre for Invasion Biology's meeting (Stellenbosch, South Africa, April 2022), South Africa National Symposium on Biological Invasions (Fort Hare University, Alice, South Africa, July 2022), Annual Garden Show (Harare, Zimbabwe in September 2022), the Annual Meeting of the Forestry and Range Resources Departments from Botswana (Gaborone, Botswana, March 2023) and an Illustrated Talk session at the Botanical Society of Namibia (Windhoek, Namibia, April 2023). In addition, I had informal meetings with staff members of the Department of Water Affairs, National Plant Health Unit, National Botanical Gardens, and Landscaping Departments of three city councils in Botswana. Other informal conversations occurred via email with environmental specialists, industry staff, and plant enthusiasts from the Democratic Republic of Congo, Eswatini, Namibia, Zambia, and Zimbabwe. I also consulted relevant documents that participants mentioned (e.g., websites,

social media, legislation, reports, and academic publications). I based each interaction on respect and written and/or verbal consent. However, the nature of some of the informal interactions did not always allow for formal consent. Nonetheless, the derived information becomes part of my analysis and interpretation as experiential knowledge.

The following central questions informed the above-mentioned interactions:

1. What kind of actions aimed at managing biological invasions from the ornamental horticulture sector have you been involved in or are you aware of? How have they been implemented?
2. What are your views about these actions, and how should they be implemented?

I recorded online interviews, face-to-face interviews, and informal conversations; otherwise, I took notes. I analysed and interpreted the data through thematic analysis. My approach to this analysis is deductive since it was informed by the six actions (overarching themes in this case) in the IPBES's framework (IPBES, 2023). I explicitly looked for coding categories that fit these six overarching themes. In coherence with my experiential qualitative and critical realist approach (see [Chapter 3](#) for further details), I coded at a semantic level, meaning that I take what participants said as a reflection of their realities (Braun & Clarke, 2022).

In the next section, this chapter briefly unpacks how the information shared by my participants aligns with the six strategic actions for the integrated governance of biological invasions (IPBES, 2023) and, thus, what the challenges are for implementing these actions. The participant names in the quotes are fictitious.

7.3 Views of stakeholders in relation to the seven IPBES recommendations for strategic action

7.3.1 Resource innovation, research and technology

Academic and non-governmental institutions in Botswana, as well as government agencies from all these countries, have worked on the documentation of the introduction history, distribution, and impacts, and the management of alien and invasive plants across Botswana, Namibia, Zambia, and Zimbabwe (Table 7.2). However, it was clear that alien ornamental plants and alien plants, in general, are not a primary research focus, for example:

“[...] I think there needs to be a push to find out the extent of some of the distributions of some of these [alien] species. For instance, at the national herbarium, when we used to go out and in the past as well, people very rarely collected alien species, because we know they are alien and we do not generally house it, and with ornamentals as well. We do not go around collecting an ornamental because we know it is an ornamental [...]”

(environmental specialist Katy, Namibia)

Table 7.2: Examples of work on the documentation of the introduction history, distribution and impacts and the management of alien and invasive plants in Southern Africa.

Country	Institution	Examples of outputs
Botswana	Okavango Research Institute Botswana University of Agriculture and Natural Resources National Botanical Garden	Kashe et al. (2020) Mafokate et al. (2013)
Namibia	Namibia Botanical Research Institute Namibia Nature Foundation University of Namibia Namibian University of Science and Technology Botanical Society of Namibia	Chase & Pagad (2020) Ipinge (2019) Mutota (2018) Ndelitunga (2022) Njunge et al. (2017)
Zambia	Copperbelt University	Siachoono et al. (2021)
South Africa (but about Zimbabwe)	University of Fort Hare	Maroyi (2012) Maroyi (2017)

Several participants from environmental specialists and industry groups said that additional research or “know-how” on domestication/cultivation would be necessary to offer native plants as alternatives to the current alien ornamental plants in the market. Specialists from Zambia, the Democratic Republic of the Congo, and Eswatini said there are not as many invasive species related to the ornamental sector as those related to the agricultural, livestock, and forestry sectors. By contrast, South African interviewees based in Garden Route and Kruger National Parks emphasised the extensive research on the spread of alien plants used as ornamentals compared to neighbouring countries and other areas of South Africa.

7.3.2 Support information systems, infrastructures and data sharing

Data sharing through public platforms, like iNaturalist, is not rare in South Africa, where there is particularly rich data on ornamental alien plants. Researchers from the Centre for Invasion Biology at Stellenbosch University and other South African institutions are increasingly using records from iNaturalist to document and monitor the spread of alien species (e.g., Potgieter et

al., 2024; Richardson & Potgieter, 2024). A few iNaturalist users in Botswana actively contribute to documenting invasive plants, specifically garden escapes (@botswanabugs, 2022). Academic institutions do not seem to be using this platform for such functions. In that context, an avid user of iNaturalist and creator of the iNaturalist project on Garden Escapes of Botswana mentioned how useful this platform could be for academic institutions in Botswana for their research and outreach activities.

The Namibian Chamber of Environment (NCE), a membership-based organisation acting as “an umbrella association that provides a forum and mouthpiece for the broader environment sector, that can lobby with government and other parties” (NCE, n.d.), funds and supports a citizen-science project that focuses on “recording biodiversity and cultural heritage in Namibia” (Atlasing in Namibia, n.d.). This project has a specific section for alien plants and connections to the work the Cactus Clean-up group (Cactus Clean-up, n.d.) carries out in Windhoek (Atlasing in Namibia, n.d.). An undergraduate project at the Namibian University of Science and Technology produced an identification guide of the 50 most important alien plants in Namibia based on this tool from NCE (Mutota, 2018). The organisation generally supports student projects (e.g., Iiping, 2019).

Social media gardening groups are valuable data-sharing platforms across Botswana (Gabs Gardener, n.d.) and Zimbabwe (Zimbabwe Gardening and Plant Lovers, n.d.). However, they are not widely used for topics like biological invasions but more for providing gardening tips, learning from each other in making businesses and gardens, and advertising plant offers by businesses.

7.3.3 Engage broadly across all stakeholders and Indigenous Peoples and local communities
Environmental specialists and people working in the sector, and, to a lesser extent, plant enthusiasts, see engagement across stakeholders and communities as a priority. They referred to engagement by mentioning education, awareness raising, knowledge sharing, and persuasion. For example, the Botanical Society of Namibia has a consistent program of awareness and education around invasive plants, which, amongst other things, organises educational activities, has an awareness campaign, and supports a citizen initiative that is currently managing cacti invasion across Windhoek, the capital of Namibia (<https://botsoc.org.na/about-us/our-projects/invasive-alien-plants-awareness>). However, the society mainly comprises “retired whites” (environmental specialist Judith, Namibia); hence,

it does not represent the wider Namibian society. Therefore, the society committee encourages “young blacks” (environmental specialist Judith, Namibia).

In Zimbabwe, every September, the Annual Garden Show in Harare focuses on using native plants, although each year has different themes. The co-organiser described how they have steadily persuaded businesses not to stock, use, or promote invasive plants in their business activities. Although, according to this interviewee, “our first three years, there was massive resistance from our exhibitors” (environmental specialist, Leyla), several businesses have followed and persuaded their customers to use native species alternatives to the usual alien ornamental plants. Furthermore, communication tools like the Zimbabwean Gardener Magazine have addressed the topic. However, most of the public attending the Annual Garden Show in September 2022 was white. In general, from across the region, participants suggested that wealthier and urban strata are more educated about the topic, being more mindful about what plants they use for gardening.

In Botswana, some businesses are conducting activities to address invasions (e.g., focusing on native plant species for gardening), especially those contributing to the SC Gardener Magazine. Botswana’s Department of Water Affairs has a consistent strategy where communication tools like TV, radio, and Facebook for the public and flyers and posters for government departments (e.g., landscaping units of the city council) are being used to raise awareness and tackle the spread of aquatic herbs (e.g., *Pontederia crassipes*, *Salvinia molesta*, *Pistia stratiotes*).

Regarding the formal education sector, a Zambian specialist said biological invasions are “a subject that is becoming popular in our curricula” (environmental specialist Michelo). Namibian and South African specialists said that the level of inclusion of this topic in formal education activities relates to the availability of resources and capacity that schools have, which translates into perceived differences between schools, dependent on their affluence status:

“[...] from an educational point of view, I know it is part of the curriculum to learn about indigenous trees, which is quite good. But I think it's also very dependent on the school. Some of the schools, which come from more affluent areas, they will then go to the National Botanical Research Institute, they'll go to the botanical gardens, and they'll be shown around. But the students that come from the less affluent areas don't have that sort of exposure. I am not 100% sure of what is taught, but I guess it also depends on the resources available for the government schools. The level of education is fine in Namibia in some respects, but they don't have the resources for a lot of things, and I do think it is what you are exposed to. [...] When you're more from the

rural areas, it's more about living in the moment and surviving and not always the sustainability [...]"

(environmental specialist Katy, Namibia)

Participants often mentioned the need for better and consistent environmental education action plans at national levels, where communication strategies to reach people are improved sensibly. Referring to how messages come across to the gardening community in Zimbabwe, a participant who edits a gardening magazine reflected on the need for changing the discourse from scolding to empowering people with options, having concise and compelling messages, and being consistent in the long-term:

"I think we don't talk about alien invasive plants in a manner that people are receptive to. Because we just heard naughty, naughty, naughty instead of going: "Hey, I see you've planted this. That's actually really not very good for our indigenous environment. It does this, this, and this; but these are the other options that you can plant that will look just as good. And they have all these extra benefits: less water, less this, grow faster, this and this. Let's say we just talk [making a gesture of scolding]. And people go: "I'm not listening to you". [...] And I think it's going to be years and years of putting this information out there continuously. [...] People are receptive to softer information in smaller bits. Then there are this massive information overload. I've noticed it as well in the magazine [...] Because people are otherwise being so bombarded with information that they stop reading [...]"

(ornamental industry staff Caroline)

Some participants noted that academics, scientists, and specialists are not usually trained to communicate complex issues to lay audiences. In that sense, the editor of the gardening magazine shared a related experience with staff from the agriculture department in Zimbabwe:

"[...] the agricultural people, for the nursery thing, they gave me a whole book a couple of months ago on invasive plants and nematodes. It is this [making a gesture with the hand] thick [...] And they were like: 'Oh, you should read it'. And I was like: 'I'm really not gonna read that, [...] so you're wasting your time giving me this info'. I wanted in a one piece of paper this, this, bomp! These are the top 10 invasive plants for Zimbabwe. Bomp!, bomp!,...pictures, so we know what they look like. These are the best things you can plant in their places. Puff, puff, puff, pictures because people don't know what plants names are [...]"

(ornamental industry staff Caroline)

7.3.4 Share efforts and commitments; understand specific roles of actors

During interactions with participants, it was clear how existing partnerships enable sharing efforts and commitments. For example, the Botanical Society of Namibia has a strong and

consistent relationship with a nursery specialising in native species. The society is a member of the Namibian Invasive Alien Species Working Group, a recently created partnership between government and non-governmental bodies to reach national biodiversity targets that complement international commitments (NCE, 2022). In Botswana, the National Botanic Garden, in conjunction with the Ministry of Environment, Natural Resources, Conservation and Tourism and academic institutions, has been running yearly workshops with nurseries to support each other and to promote knowledge sharing in plant growth, maintenance, and the use of native plants. There is a solid network of businesses across Zimbabwe. To a lesser extent, Botswana is committed to promoting native species and avoiding selling invasive species (see Box 1 for an example). Across such networks and groups, some degree of social accounting and reputation is linked to who sells or uses invasive plants and who does not. One of the Zambian specialists is working to create a similar network there.

Box 1: Nurseries focussed on native plants in Zimbabwe, Namibia and Botswana

Emerald Seedlings in Harare (Zimbabwe), Namib Trees in Windhoek (Namibia), and Mokolodi Indigenous Nursery in Gaborone (Botswana) are three examples of nurseries being well-known for promoting the use of native plants and/or for being well-connected with several stakeholders within the environmental, academic and gardening communities in Botswana, Namibia, and Zimbabwe. While Namib Trees and Emerald Seedlings are relatively large-scale, well-established, and renowned businesses with more than one branch in their respective countries, Mokolodi Indigenous Nursery’s owners said that their nursery is a small-scale social project for the community of Mokolodi. White Namibians and white Zimbabweans own Namib Trees and Emerald Seedlings, respectively, while white foreigners own Mokolodi Indigenous Nursery, employing black majorities.

---End of Box 1

One of the most palpable conflicts is between the formal and the informal businesses selling/using ornamental plants. Some formal businesses across Botswana, Namibia, and Zimbabwe perceive informal sellers as unfair competitors because they do not pay taxes, licenses, water bills, or rent, offering plants for cheaper prices. For a landscaper in Botswana, the problem is not “the little guys with little plants” (ornamental industry staff Petrus)—which his business supports—but the ones that “just come in, bringing a truckload of plants, drop it into the road and sell there, and there is no taxes” (ornamental industry staff Petrus). A small-scale backyard nursery owner in Botswana explained that people sometimes abuse the

perceived vulnerability of road sellers by bargaining for lower prices. However, they would not do that to a well-established business or a franchise. Moreover, a backyard nursery owner from Botswana explained that the process for getting licenses is bureaucratic and unclear, limiting the capacities of small-scale nurseries to be legalised and to tender for government and city council landscaping projects, on which several participants would have been keen. Several backyard nursery owners in Botswana were open for training and knowledge sharing. One nursery owner in Zimbabwe explained that informal sellers stocking invasive plants undermines her nursery's efforts to educate their clients:

“[...] I think it's the smaller roadside nurseries where they [clients] say: ‘Oh, but I saw it over that nursery’. And it's like, ‘yes, but they shouldn't have it’. So, you are sometimes fighting a losing battle, but we've tried our best to eradicate all of that [...]”

(ornamental industry staff Susan)

I observed that in Zimbabwe, for example, the conflict “becomes a racial thing sometimes” (ornamental industry staff Gerrit) since the road sellers are mostly “indigenous guys,” whereas, as one of the interviewees and organiser of the garden show in Harare said, “a lot of our [formal] nurseries are white-owned” (environmental specialist Leyla).

A nursery owner in Zimbabwe highlighted another type of conflict. According to this participant, a South African landscaper the nursery is working with on a large-scale project recommended plants that could not be legally used in South Africa under their Alien and Invasive Species Regulations (see Wilson and Kumschick [2024] for a review of the South African regulations). The participant criticised that people could go to Zimbabwe to do things they would not be allowed to do by law in South Africa, given the lack of legislation, law enforcement, and a higher level of corruption in Zimbabwe compared to South Africa. Other participants in Zimbabwe echoed the lack of legislation as a drawback. However, a nursery manager mentioned that legislation prohibited certain species (e.g., water hyacinth, jacaranda, lantana) from being sold in Zimbabwe.

Another visible conflict is between businesses and government offices. Some businesses across Botswana and Zimbabwe complained about governments' inability to enforce environmental laws and consistent programmes and the poor training of government staff. One South African nursery owner based in Botswana found that government landscaping projects often ask for alien plants. When I asked relevant Botswanan council officials about this, they responded that

they must ensure plants are water-wise, fast-growing, unpalatable for free-roaming cattle, and appealing. Their options are limited.

According to a Zimbabwean specialist, government officers in Zimbabwe and other Southern African countries are not as skilled in the topic as in South Africa:

“[...] I need to stress how different that country [South Africa] is in its operation from the rest of southern Africa. And where it's different is the government agencies actually function there. For example, when you speak to the environmental agency in South Africa, they will have people who are qualified, experienced, top of the field involved. When you talk to our Environmental Management Agency in Zimbabwe, you are talking to individuals who are kind of bottom of the professional pit. Because if somebody has a good qualification experience, or ability, they're not in government service [...]”

(environmental specialist Leyla)

Nurseries in Namibia and Zimbabwe complained about the legislative and bureaucratic obstacles to sourcing and selling native species while it is easy to source and sell alien plants. In Botswana, several nursery owners also said that importing plants is straightforward. A few nursery owners further explained that importing plants is usually more cost-effective for many small-scale businesses than growing many plants by themselves, given the high investment in infrastructure and resources such projects require.

In contrast, in South Africa, several local professionals said that some nurseries sell plants banned by legislation, hindering the effectiveness of environmental agencies' management actions and educational campaigns:

“[...] They [nurseries] are selling alien plants that they are not even supposed to be selling [...] this also causes implications when it comes to management. Because it just makes things so difficult for the implementing managers to be on top of this problem. If you gonna get people promoting and selling them, on the other hand, you are busy trying to raise awareness: ‘Ok, no, not this way!’ And then, there are other people on the other hand selling them. So, it just makes things so complicated! [...]”

(environmental specialist Nofoto, South Africa)

There are also disconnections and controversies across the different sectors and offices of government that deal with plant and natural resource use, conservation, and management. Namibian and Botswanan specialists mentioned the historical role that governmental forestry departments have had in promoting the use of alien plants. For instance, the landscaping units of a few city councils in Botswana described how they now have to manage plants that once were promoted by the forestry department. Nowadays, the forestry departments are shifting

towards native plants in both countries. Forestry nursery branches in Tlokweng (Botswana) and Okahandja (Namibia) exemplify this. When interacting with several government departments in Botswana, it was evident that communication processes between them are not as effective as they would be necessary for an integrated governance of biological invasions.

In addition, some department participants said they needed more support in training and funding. A common theme was that funding, and the state of countries' economies limit the prioritisation of invasion management by stakeholders, especially governments. For instance, a Zambian specialist recalled how government-funded management has changed over the years since the independence, influenced by economic hardship:

“[...] Many years ago after independence, there used to be more greater pushes by government to tackle certain noxious weed species like *Lantana camara*. And that, over the years, has gone by the wayside. At independence, they were quite good at still tackling those issues of invasive species. There were more agricultural extension officers that worked about going into the rural areas and helping in terms of best practices for cultivation, for soil conservation, as well as plant health and so forth. When Zambia hit economic hard times, those were things that disappeared, and they've never really returned [...]

(environmental specialist Ryan)

7.3.5 Enhance coordination and collaboration across international and regional mechanisms

Environmental specialists recurrently mentioned regional collaboration as a priority. According to one South African specialist, regional collaboration across countries exists, but it has to move beyond the academic world toward the implementation of clear management actions:

“[...] I think they [regional collaborations] are happening. But they are more happening [at] collaborative research level. They don't go down deeper into the implementation stage. There is the collaborations when it comes to scientific writing, and so on, the meetings and stuff; they are there! But, then, when it comes to the actual implementation, now it does not get there! So, it's very important to start with them. It's fine the collaborations, write the papers, the science and so on, that is fine, up until the end, up until like the implementation stage. So, it would be great if those collaborations actually could go down through the implementation stage [...]

(environmental specialist Nofoto)

Another South African specialist could not recall examples of regional collaboration in preventing and controlling plant invasions linked explicitly to the ornamental sector. Based on

this specialist's interpretation, the lack of examples relates to the fact that research on the topic is still in the early stages, not enabling translation into management actions:

“[...] For ornamentals, I am not aware of, on the research side, many programs, or many projects even that are looking at this. It might just be my ignorance, but with the groups that I have worked with, or they do not know of, or I do not know of huge amount of work on this topic, not nearly compared to what has been done on the other aspects of invasion. This is also then [related to] not being translated over into many management situations. A lot of it is still early stage, a lot of theories [...]”

(environmental specialist Owen)

My interactions and observations across South Africa, Botswana, Namibia, and Zimbabwe suggest that collaborations amongst the countries are less intense than collaborations between each country and countries like the United States, Britain, Germany, and Australia. However, participants recalled collaborations in managing water herbs and cacti introduced as ornamental between Botswana, Namibia, and South Africa. For instance, a Namibian specialist recalled when she participated in the joint (Namibian-Botswanan) management of *Salvinia molesta* in the Okavango Delta region. Moreover, the Botanical Society of Namibia hosted a South African specialist in biocontrol to tackle the spread of several species of cacti, supported by the Cactus Clean-up group, a citizen-based control and monitoring program (Cactus Clean-up, n.d.—mentioned earlier). This collaboration also involved a student project at the Namibian University of Science and Technology that assessed the effectiveness of those interventions (Ndelitunga, 2022).

Specialists highlighted the need for increased regional collaboration in border inspection and control, legislation enforcement, knowledge sharing, and training. Non-South African specialists emphasised the need to collaborate with South Africa regarding market adoption of native plants, public and sector outreach, training, and legislation design and enforcement. The shared perception amongst the non-South African participants is that South Africa has done these things better. Usually, the non-South African participants mentioned and considered South Africa as the provider of expertise. According to them, South Africa has been able to put its native plants into the market and take pride in its native flora for ornamental gardening and regulating plant sales like no other country in the sub-region. Likewise, this perceived superiority of South Africa was widely shared by the people working within the ornamental sector in Botswana, Namibia, and Zimbabwe. It was common to hear from businesses and

institutions that knowledge about plant invasion management and/or invasive plants came from training and education received in South Africa.

A Zimbabwean specialist mentioned essential challenges around the governance of regional collaborations when countries are in different developmental stages. Apart from the decisive influence of funding to sustain collaborations, this participant reflected on other factors. For him, the political-administrative infrastructure, the situation of Southern African countries, and the funders' perceptions of these infrastructures and situations influence the capacity for collaborative management. In the context of transboundary conservation areas (Transfrontier Parks), which can be relevant for collaborative invasion management, the specialist explained:

“[...] [Greater Limpopo Transfrontier Park Contribution area] is not as useful as people would have liked it to be, because it's a platform where people just talk, but then, for things to be done, I think, it all takes money. There is the Big Brother South Africa, which stocks more money than Zimbabwe and Mozambique. If you hear about the stories in Kruger, the South African section, their roads are better, water is good, communication is better. Then if you come to Zimbabwe or Mozambique, it is different. I think the platform is opening people's eyes, sharing ideas of what and how things can be done, but then for things to really happen, I think it takes more than just that. [...] South Africa has a better economy, so their operations are well funded by the national fiscus. Their national budget is better than Zimbabwe's. Because things work [in South Africa], it attracts more professionals to stay in the system and all that. [...] I think Zimbabwe, in first value would attract more funding, because of the economy and poverty, but then there are issues that come to play, the politics and all that, the accountability, that makes people not bringing the funding [...]

(environmental specialist Tinotenda)

Furthermore, this specialist added that having an alliance with an “international organisation” has proved to be a fit-to-purpose strategy to make the attraction of international funding smoother:

“[...] we are not government [only], but we are a national park in partnership between an international organization and the government. It makes people know that if I put my money into this organization, I'm not giving the Zimbabwean government, but I am giving an organization that is being managed by—from some angle—an international organization, which is world renowned, with a good track record of use of funds and all that [...]

(environmental specialist Tinotenda)

7.3.6 Improve policy coherence

Concerning policy, most non-South African specialists and some businesses have expressed that a specific legislative framework is needed. Most of them acknowledged that their

countries' biosecurity laws focused on the phytosanitary implications of plant imports, not specifically tackling biological invasions. Two specialists —from Namibia and Botswana— mentioned laws that, although not specific to biological invasions, include the management of functional groups of species like agricultural or aquatic weeds. Such legislation includes, for example, the Aquatic Weeds Act 1989 in Botswana and the Agricultural Pest Act 1973 in Namibia (see further examples in Table 7.3 and a case study from Namibia referred to wetland management [Bethune & Ruppel, 2007]). One participant from the National Plant Health Unit in Botswana said that a nursery bill to control the plants that nurseries can import had been drafted for approval at the moment of my interaction.

Table 7.3: Laws that relate to the management and prevention of biological invasions in Botswana, Namibia, the Democratic Republic of Congo, Zambia, and Zimbabwe.

Botswana	Namibia	Democratic Republic of Congo	Zambia	Zimbabwe
Aquatic Weeds (Control) Act 1971	Weeds Act No 42 of 1937	Loi n° 11/022 du 24 décembre 2011 portant principes fondamentaux relatifs a l'agriculture	Noxious Weed Act 1953	Environmental Management Act 2002
Noxious Weeds Act 1916	Weeds Ordinance 19 of 1957	Loi n° 11/009 du 09 juillet 2011 portant principes fondamentaux de gestion de l'environnement	Environmental Management Act 12 of 2011	Forest Act 1949
Noxious Weed Order 1968	Plant Quarantine Act 7 of 2008	Loi n° 14/003 du 11 février 2014 relative à la conservation de la nature	Forest Act 4 of 2015	Forest Amendment Act 2021
Plant Protection Act	Environmental Management Act 7 of 2007	Décret n° 14/019 du 02 août 2014 fixant les règles de fonctionnement des mécanismes procéduraux de la protection de l'environnement	The Zambia Wildlife	Plant Pest and Diseases Act 1958
Forest Act 1968	Forest Act 12 of 2001	Loi n° 15/026 du 31 décembre	Plant Pests and Diseases Act	Parks and Wildlife Act 1975

		2015 relative à l'eau		
Wildlife Conservation and National Parks Act 1992	Nature Conservation Amendment Act 3 of 2017		Water Resources Management Act 21 of 2011	Water Act 1958
Water Act 1968	Water Resources Management Act 11 of 2013			

A Namibian specialist summarised related laws—some of them from the times of the colonial Apartheid South African regime—and policies in place:

“[...] Our constitution in Namibia can be interpreted as asking us to deal with the issue. We have an environmental clause in the Constitution, Article 95 L [...], [which] we can interpret as saying that the maintenance of the overall ecosystem is a national obligation, and depending all actions of the legislature, and this includes the control of invasive alien species, where [they] pose a threat to an ecosystem or ecological process, or to biological diversity or the welfare of people or to sustainable utilization of natural resources. We have some more specific legislation as well in the policy of the Ministry of Environment and Tourism, so they are aware of the issue of alien invasive, and these are being thoroughly addressed in the new parks and wildlife management tool. There is also a Forestry Act, which looks at the introduction of alien invasive species, and that it was recently revised. The Ministry of the Department of Agriculture keeps a list of species not allowed into the country, where the five water weeds are specifically mentioned, and then cacti are just as a general concept [...] The Environmental Management bill provides some very good contingencies. It specifically states the application of a precautionary principle under the section on principles of environmental management [...] and it is a legal requirement to do EIA [environmental impact assessment] before any development. [...]”

(environmental specialist Sandra)

This participant added that despite these many laws, there are problems in their coordinated enforcement across societal sectors (e.g., forestry, tourism, environment, agriculture) and in the design and implementation of complementary policies. Interestingly, the specialist mentioned the counteraction that the Forestry Act might have in the management of a specific invasive plant in Namibia, denoting incoherencies between closely related sectors and institutions:

“There is a clause in the Forestry Act that provides the protection of the environment and makes it an offence ‘to harm, injure, remove any living tree bush or shrub within 100 metres of any river stream or watercourse’, but that is actually something counter

to what we need to do when removing riverside aliens such as *Prosopis* [*Neltuma* spp.]. It essentially makes it illegal, and therefore we need to have these excluded from that type of legislation. [...]"

(environmental specialist Sandra)

Moreover, as described earlier, in Zimbabwe, laws are not necessarily well-known amongst participants, even amongst environmental specialists. Overall, non-South African participants praised South Africa's legislative corpus on alien species, deeming it the model to follow in the sub-region. However, the South African participants recognised both strengths and weaknesses of the South African legislative framework. One specialist said the South African legislation was too general and extensive, limiting its operationalisation, especially when building capacity among the government staff that is supposed to enforce it. This participant further suggested that the species listing and derived management categories could adopt a local approach that allows stakeholders to assess which species are included and what management measures to take, considering the local context. A different South African informant said that the high levels of corruption across the South African governmental administration do not enable effective enforcement. Furthermore, another South African specialist commented that the South African legislation had not been designed to serve and protect non-privileged South Africans, hindering the capacity to effectively reach the economy's informal sector. In addition, some business owners complained about the lack of a long-term vision of policies and the general corruption and instability in Africa compared to "first world" countries.

7.4 Conclusions and recommendations

Building on six of the strategic action areas for an integrated governance approach to biological invasions proposed by IPBES (2023), this chapter—to my knowledge—constitutes the first attempt that examines how this framework applies to a specific area and sector since the launch of the IPBES report. The process, although straightforward in general, turned complex when distinguishing overarching themes between "Resource innovation, research and technology" and "Support information systems, infrastructures, and data sharing," and between "Engage broadly across all stakeholders and Indigenous People" and "Share efforts and commitments; understand specific roles." These strategic actions (or overarching themes) areas from the framework overlap, which is expected, given the integrated nature of governance and the multi-factorial and cross-sectorial nature of biological invasions.

My analysis appraised that significant efforts are ongoing in Southern Africa to address biological invasions from the ornamental sector. However, they need more integration and consideration of the broader geopolitical and socio-historical context (Table 7.3). If the existing limited funding for invasive species management were channelled to better coordination, such programs could integrate all the actions and actors described in this paper while facilitating policies and practices to manage biological invasions.

Table 7.3: Summary remarks of what the strategic action areas for an integrated governance approach to biological invasions proposed by IPBES (2023) look like in several Southern African countries.

Strategic action area	Summary
7.3.1 Resource innovation, research and technology	While research and innovation activities are taking place in several countries of Southern Africa, the attention to biological invasions linked to the ornamental sector varies substantially between countries, giving room for more integration and focus.
7.3.2 Support information systems, infrastructures and data sharing	Data and knowledge sharing are happening, but there are differences in scale and type of platforms and infrastructures across countries. There is great potential for more topic integration into such platforms across Southern Africa.
7.3.3 Engage broadly across all stakeholders and Indigenous Peoples and local communities	Although this action (overarching theme) is viewed as a priority for addressing invasive plants and various activities ranging from education and awareness to persuasion and knowledge sharing are happening in Namibia, Zimbabwe, and Botswana, challenges remain in ensuring inclusive participation and effective communication across stakeholders.
7.3.4 Share efforts and commitments; understand specific roles of actors	Although joint efforts and commitments occur between environmental organisations, governments, and businesses in several countries, conflicts arise between formal and informal plant businesses and amongst businesses and government agencies. Issues in regulations, bureaucratic hurdles, communication, and inequalities shape these conflicts. Furthermore, poor funding and resources and economic instability limit what government units can do, as well as communication issues.
7.3.5 Enhance coordination and collaboration across international and regional mechanisms	Regional collaboration is still scarce across Southern Africa, significantly beyond academic research and management actions. Challenges such as perceptions of superiority and inferiority,

	economic disparities, legislative inconsistencies, and the need for solid governance and funding hinder effective collaboration across the region.
7.3.6 Improve policy coherence	Policy coherence faces challenges across the sub-region, especially concerning cross-sectorial and societal coherence, legislation awareness, enforcement, and inclusivity. Despite its challenges, such as generality, corruption, and insufficient capacity building and inclusivity, South Africa's legislative model on alien species is praised amongst non-South African specialists.

I picked up and unpacked these needs in four practical recommendations (Figure 7.1) that I hope to contribute to the ongoing efforts to tackle biological invasions in Southern Africa.

- Improve cohesion and collaboration amongst stakeholders by using the framework for stakeholder engagement proposed by Novoa et al. (2018). Starting with Botswana, Namibia, and Zimbabwe—given the above-presented deeper understanding of the contexts therein—regular communication spaces (for example, Living Labs) could be used where environmental specialists, ornamental industry staff, and plant enthusiasts meet to debate the prevention and management of biological invasions. Such spaces for dialogue could happen in the form of workshops, meetings, and/or by using/amplifying already created spaces like, for instance, the Annual Garden Show in Harare, the Illustrated Talks by the Namibian Botanical Society, and forestry/environmental workshops like the one hosted by the National Botanic Garden and Forestry Departments in Botswana. However, such existing spaces might limit the reach of informal businesses, especially in Namibia and Zimbabwe. Hence, it is likely that new spaces would need to be mindfully organised so that informal businesses can join and feel safe enough to share their knowledge. Also, such spaces should include a mix of stakeholders: government, private businesses, academia, non-profit organisations, and people interested in plants.
- Ensure pluralism, where “non-scientific” and subaltern views and practices from historically marginalised social groups in Southern Africa are recognised and valued as significant knowledges and realities (Bandauko & Arku, 2024; Toomey et al., 2017; Turnhout, 2024; Zein-Elabdin, 2009). Designing suitable communication spaces requires carefully considering the segregation and marginalisation issues within the ornamental sector, their historical structural causes, and discussing the overall social

contexts and embedded power dynamics I aimed to show. For this to happen, there should be a paradigm shift in policy and governance that includes and considers the informal sector through inclusive and participatory urban planning (Bandauko & Arku, 2024) and in legislation that changes the colonial laws still in place (Mitullah, 2003; Wily, 2011). Zein-Elabdin's (2009) notions of profound economic, cultural, and institutional mixing (i.e., hybridity) into legislative and policy decision-making could benefit the movement towards fairer, more ethical, and more locally relevant legislations and policies. This incorporation means that the historical and geopolitical mechanisms that determine the inequalities and power dynamics in the sub-region should be recognised, even if this recognition produces discomfort.

- Address the power differences and superiority/inferiority complexes that the representatives from the different countries in the sub-region unconsciously might carry when taking the programme to a sub-regional level. For sub-regional cooperation to become more effective, collaborators need to pay attention to the nuances constructed along the history of the sub-region and the diversity of cultural and socio-geographical contexts. In particular, South African collaborators should be mindful of this power relation where South Africa acts as “the big brother” and the giver of expertise to avoid the naïve and good-intentioned imposition of strategies that might be counterproductive and unfair for the other partners. Moreover, such processes should be careful not to increase South Africa's perceived superiority in the topic disproportionately.
- Collaborate with existing sub-regional groups working in nature-society, like the Southern African Program on Ecosystem Change and Society (SAPECS, n.d) and the Environmental Education Association of Southern Africa (EESSA, n.d.). Both groups are actively working towards more sustainable, just, and equitable futures in the sub-region of socio-ecological research and practice in Southern Africa (Biggs et al., 2022; see EESSA's publications in EESSA, n.d.). Unsurprisingly, South Africans and/or people based in South African institutions lead EESSA as the majority in SAPECS. This fact, again, is an artefact of the power dynamics in the sub-region—where South Africa plays a dominant role—that should be considered when framing collaborative networks. Creating a Southern African Symposium on Biological Invasions could be a space to network and frame joint efforts between countries.

Figure 7.1: Recommendations for facilitating conflict management and decision-making in the management of ornamental-related biological invasions across Southern Africa, using Botswana, Namibia, and Zimbabwe as case examples. Illustration by Verónica Barrajon-Santos.

8. Conclusions and Reflections

8.1 Conclusions

This thesis has utilised a qualitative and critical realist approach (chapter 3) to examine the role of the ornamental horticulture sector in plant invasions across Southern Africa. To my knowledge, this is the first study that has examined the role of a specific economic sector in biological invasions using sub-regional and multistakeholder perspectives in Southern Africa. I considered three research questions that address its building blocks: the plants, the people, and the interactions between them, to examine the relationship between the sector and plant invasions. In addition, the fourth research question transformed the theoretical and empirical analyses into a pragmatic set of recommendations to improve the governance of ornamental-related plant invasions in the area.

Firstly, it documented what invasive species (and alien established species) are on sale within the ornamental sector of three Southern African countries, reporting that the sector in Botswana, Namibia, and Zimbabwe lists for sale 82 invasive plants and 289 plants that have already established alien populations in at least one continental SADC country. This estimate is a documentation of the high invasion debt that the sector is carrying in the area, with the potential for conflicts given the popularity and establishment of many of these plants within the global and regional market ([chapter 4](#)). This analysis constitutes a baseline for an invasion risk assessment of the ornamental sector at a sub-regional level that supports prevention, impact reduction, and mitigation while considering the sector's demands and characteristics.

Secondly, the thesis has described what supply chains and practices look like within the ornamental horticulture sector in Southern Africa, where South Africa (and Zimbabwe to a lesser extent) plays a hegemonic role tied to its ornamental horticulture industry's British and Dutch colonial legacy, its related economic dominance and its role as the region's leading supplier (of ornamental plants) and as a (governance, policy, and industry) model to follow in the sub-region ([chapter 5](#)). The sector increasingly provides 'formal' and 'informal' livelihoods in urban areas, the latter especially for women and those retired or unemployed in the formal sector. Moreover, the sector reflects a deep cultural mixing that, according to Zein-Elabdin (2009), typifies postcolonial African societies, where hegemonic (western) and subaltern (indigenous) practices coexist and intertwine. Alien plants and foreign styles usually symbolise higher social status, but modern trends towards more geographically contextualised gardening practices and native plants are in fashion too. The description of these scenarios constitutes an

assessment of the socio-ecological context in which the management of the invasive and alien established species currently traded, used (reported in [chapter 4](#)), and sought-after takes place. It, thus, forms the context to address question 3 of this thesis (see [chapter 1](#))

Thirdly, the thesis has documented how stakeholders involved in the interplay between the sector and environmental management understand biological invasions and if and how they recognise and perceive invasive ornamental plants ([chapter 6](#)). Unsurprisingly, my screening of the plants on sale (chapter 4) identified several species that participants mentioned in this chapter. The analysis in chapter 6 has shed light on the commonalities and differences in perceptions and understandings amongst those stakeholders that affect the management of ornamental-related invasions. It demonstrates that—although people’s perceptions of invasive species, and particular ornamental plants, vary because of different interests, socio-economic, cultural contexts, and personal experiences with the plants—the overall understanding of the key concepts of biological invasion does not differ substantially across environmental specialists, ornamental industry staff and ornamental gardeners or end users in Southern Africa. Better communication and engagement strategies could be implemented to reach out to non-specialist audiences and stakeholders more effectively, who have an important role in addressing the link between plant invasions and the ornamental horticulture sector.

Fourthly, the thesis interprets what an integrated governance approach to biological invasions looks like in Botswana, Namibia, and Zimbabwe based on the strategic actions the IPBES report on invasive alien species and their control suggests (IPBES, 2023). Building from my interpretation, I provide practical recommendations to foster such an approach for the ornamental-related plant invasions in Southern Africa. These recommendations could facilitate conflict management and decision-making, emphasising the need to consider the power imbalances reflected at the sub-region’s individual, group, societal and regional levels ([chapter 7](#)). Moreover, my recommendations could also be contextualised to sectors like the pet industry, whose significance in animal invasions is still under scrutiny in South Africa, for example (Martin & Coetze, 2011; Nelufule et al., 2020; Shivambu et al., 2020).

Future research could be extended to include more countries of the sub-region, a bigger sample, and higher coverage over time, building upon this thesis’ results. For instance, incorporating more nurseries, given that my sample did not saturate the species accumulation curve (chapter 4), and/or conveying the perceptions and impacts for one specific stakeholder group (ornamental gardeners or ornamental industry staff) in each of the mainland SADC countries

across urban and rural areas. These examples could contribute to understanding spatial, socio-ecological, and potentially temporal variability of perceptions of invasive ornamental plants and their impacts on people’s livelihoods and lives. Therefore, it could also potentially inform management at SADC’s level. Furthermore, a potential follow-up research could examine the social factors shaping the leadership, discourses, and success of the current gardening movements promoting indigenous plants. Likewise, the adequate implementation of the recommendations given in this thesis requires follow-ups and monitoring.

Integrating the results from the four article chapters through the critical realist framework I introduced in chapter 3 (Figure 3.1), I argue that my thesis presents the empirical domain of the topic, documenting the perceptions of alien and invasive ornamental species held by stakeholders involved in the interplay between the ornamental horticultural sector and environmental management. My research also engages with the actual domain, documenting the operation and dynamics of the ornamental sector that relate, influence, and get shaped by those perceptions (Figure 3.1). The real domain is made of complex processes (that I refer to as “products of history”) that influence the likelihood of plants becoming invasive through interactions with the ornamental sector and related practices that humans develop in line with the mainstream concepts of human development and modernity and humans’ co-evolution with plants (Figure 8.1). The consequences of certain “products of history” (e.g., colonial processes and Apartheid, mainstream concepts of human development) go beyond the topic of this thesis, as I believe they are the mainstay of the Western hegemony in global science (refer to sub-chapter 2.2 for deeper discussion) and further into modern societies and the environmental crisis that we are facing (IPBES, 2024).

Figure 8.1: Products of history influencing the interplay between the ornamental sector and plant invasions in Southern Africa.

Multiple synergies between these “products of history” shape the configuration of the sector in Southern Africa, where South Africa is hegemonic and considered superior in terms of the industry’s development and its management of plant invasions, reflecting the geopolitical

power relations in the sub-region that stems from colonial and Apartheid times. Alien plants are highly appreciated for ornamental purposes; hence, both the offer and the demand within the sector favour them, showcasing a likely high invasion debt. Plant and gardening preferences are entangled in the colonial legacies of social and racial hierarchies, modernity, and the mutualistic relations between humans and ornamental plants.

Furthermore, the relations between the ornamental sector and plant invasions in Southern Africa reflect that humans and plants acclimatise and adapt to a rapidly changing world and sub-region, where urbanisation and climate change are becoming stronger selective forces. Some alien plants that people generally use and prefer in the sub-region have thrived in urban ecosystems, benefiting from the human-facilitated spread and becoming established and invasive. However, while others might not likely establish in the wild due to several specific plant traits, they symbolise hegemonic ideas of what modern gardens should look like to be seen as pretty and publicly appreciated.

These “products of history” also influence how stakeholders in this thesis perceive each other. This context cannot be ignored when analysing the root causes of some conflicts presented in chapters 5, 6, and 7. These conflicts have noticeable nuances across the three central countries where I developed my research practice. For instance, conflicts between the formal and informal sectors felt more substantial and more problematic in Namibia and Zimbabwe than in Botswana (likely also linked to substantial differences in the regulation of informal spaces). Conflicts observed during this research stem from racial and classist underlining, reflecting the colonial and Apartheid legacies in both countries where racial segregation and white settlerism were higher than in Botswana (Mgadla, 2014). Botswana, on the other hand, seemed less confrontational, reflecting its typical strategic geopolitical role of peacemaker in between fighting neighbours and as a refuge for the black majorities in Apartheid times. However, the sector in Botswana does display the typical colonial legacies where significant businesses are still owned by white expats and South Africans, and ‘Western’ ideas of gardening symbolize higher social status to the detriment of traditional indigenous ideas. I argue, therefore, that the nuances within and between the countries’ sectors reflect the nuanced history of Botswana, Namibia, and Zimbabwe, as well as their historical positions in the geopolitical map of the sub-region.

These conflicts – alongside the high invasion debt from the sector – suggest that managing ornamental-related plant invasions in Southern Africa could entrench these conflicts if the

consequences of the “products of history” are not addressed with care and bearing justice in mind. My recommendations ([chapter 7](#)) attempt to do so by proposing transparent and participatory engagement, building on the commonalities in stakeholders’ understandings of biological invasions ([chapter 6](#) for further details). Such recommendations need to be developed so that, on the one hand, they allow for regional cross-country coordination and, on the other hand, enable each country to develop and implement its strategy. Likewise, an appropriate legal framework that serves nature and people as part of nature must be co-designed, shared, and adequately implemented to facilitate actions.

Environmental specialists are likely to be the facilitators of the abovementioned endeavours. Thus, as environmental specialists, we should acknowledge that our perceptions, attitudes, preferences, behaviours, and public discourse have the potential to influence significantly other stakeholder groups because we have been historically positioned as key knowledge holders (Pascual et al., 2021; Toomey et al., 2017; Turnhout, 2024). However, the scientific production of knowledge is a socioeconomic activity and livelihood subjected to power relations, cultural perceptions, social interactions, and political consequences (Bhaskar, 1975; Pascual et al., 2021; Price, 2015; Toomey et al., 2017), and it is currently being dominated by ‘western’ thinking and lifestyle. Using Pascual et al. (2021) and Turnhout’s (2024) calls for change, I argue that we—environmental specialists—need to work towards improving how our institutions are governed and our environmental practice is conducted to counteract power concentration and marginalisation within the sector and society. We also need to embrace open-mindedness, practicing a relational approach to environmental practice and communication, where our knowledge and opinions do not become hegemonic over others. This process would be the first step toward the transformative change necessary for tackling the current environmental crisis’s underlying political and economic causes (IPBES, 2024; Pascual et al., 2021).

My thesis demonstrates that research in Invasion Science worldwide could benefit from a) critical perspectives that acknowledge the systemic and long-term repercussions of the geographically contextualised “products of history” in the relations between people and invasive species; b) transboundary perspectives that acknowledge the movement, either through “natural” spread or trade of invasive plants across boundaries; c) the need for a more coordinated management framework that considers the former points a and b; and d) a greater awareness of the benefits of utilising qualitative and mixed methods approach to inform the management of invasive species. Overall, alien plants are an integral part of gardens in

Southern Africa—which participants (and I) tacitly accepted and embraced. However, this embracing process should not lead to a naïve and uncritical appraisal of the drivers, impacts, and modulating factors of alien plant spread and biological invasions. We should focus on the drivers analysed in this thesis while considering the impacts and plurality of positions amongst stakeholders to aim for a healthier relationship between species, ecosystems, and peoples.

8.2 Reflections on my positionality

My journey to write this thesis has been about resilience, fighting, and acceptance. The topic and Southern Africa captivated me; thus, I was always motivated to keep pushing. However, from my research to my life beyond, I have struggled to convey my messages in ways other people could understand and mainly accept. Nonetheless, other constructive critiques, fascination, and understanding moments have existed. For example, in conferences, I came across people who told me that they had never thought of some of the interpretations I presented in this thesis but that they would from that moment onwards. In the following lines, related to my introductory reflections in [sub-chapter 3.4](#), I will briefly reflect on some of those struggles since they have shaped how this thesis unfolded.

8.2.1 Reflections on critiques of my methodological approach

As I discussed in [chapter 2](#) and [chapter 3](#), science, particularly invasion science, is highly quantitative and positivist. My methodological choice was a somewhat unusual one in this context. For example, in my first presentation for PhD researchers focussed on agriculture and livestock sciences at the Botswana University of Agriculture and Natural Resources, part of the audience seemed confused and perturbed. I was told that my approach was not scientific enough. However, my methodological approach allowed me to acknowledge the research's interactive and co-constructive nature with human participants. I could embrace our humanness and account for the interrelation between contexts and our lives, paying attention to macro-socio-ecological processes that are complex and difficult to quantify.

8.2.2 My “subjective” interpretations

I use several concepts in this thesis that were not expected when the topic of the thesis was initially conceptualised, as I previously mentioned in [sub-chapter 3.4](#). These include terms like hegemony, products of history, and colonial and Apartheid legacies, to name but a few. I did not prove the relevance of colonial legacies and Apartheid in numbers, but others have come close (e.g., Shackleton & Gwedla, 2021; Venter et al., 2020). In a conversation with one of my supervisors, she wondered to what extent my focus on these historical aspects as predominating

explanatory causes for conflicts around invasive plant management was tied to my own specific experiences and was mainly triggered by a few intense, very opinionated and unpleasant interactions with participants in Namibia and Zimbabwe. I reflected and explained that I also had interactions and experiences in Botswana (and South Africa) that showed me the deeply engrained and sometimes subtle colours of colonial and Apartheid legacies there. She suggested that more nuances were needed between countries and factors exposed in this thesis to avoid binary interpretations and homogenisation of the realities interpreted. As a result of these conversations, I have attempted to do this throughout the thesis, especially in the previous section.

Regarding the seemingly less adversarial Botswana, I would like to reflect on one of my first interactions with a white nursery owner from a Global North country who is an expat in Botswana. This person hires Botswana black women with the condition that their kids must go to school. If it is found that the women do not send their kids to school, then they are likely fired. This measure seems well-intentioned against Botswana's supposedly high illiteracy and inequality, per this nursery owner's belief. After much self-learning and being exposed to passive-aggressive (sometimes naive), colonially rooted verbal violence, I can recognise coloniality, racism, and superiority complexes. This participant's behaviour is rooted in a colonial settler mindset that automatically justifies and grants the entitlement to coerce people to do what they think is better for others. The colonial legacies of racial and classist inequalities existing in Botswana provide the societal privileges to exercise this power. The experience described is a subtle memory of the colonial past and a present reminder of the colonial legacy that still permeates Botswana and beyond.

In addition, my supervisor highlighted the need for nuances between the various factors that I propose to influence the interplay between the ornamental sector and plant invasions in Southern Africa. She mentioned, for example, that in my empirical data, there appear to be descriptions of personal experiences with the plants themselves that are not necessarily related to geopolitics and coloniality and that, nonetheless, also shape the attitudes and perceptions towards plants. The example described in [chapter 6](#), where one of my participants said how *Lantana camara* completely took over a family graveyard, and thus –after this experience– emphasised how annoying the plant had become for them. Indeed, personal experiences with plants and personal preferences are related to our biological and ecological human identity and, hence, our co-evolution with plants, influencing this interplay between the sector and plant invasions in Southern Africa. However, I focus on the geopolitical and socio-historical sides

of the "products of history" due to their paramount role in the current environmental crisis, needing greater attention from decision-makers, policymakers, and society. In addition, I cannot deny that my socialist and highly political upbringing in a country like Cuba (see brief referral in [sub-chapter 3.4](#)), as well as my migratory experiences as a Cuban woman traveling between Europe, Africa, and the Americas, have made me hyper-aware of geopolitics and how it can influence every facet of individuals.

8.2.3 The ethical principles of my research

Before embarking on this doctoral research project, I worked in Cuba as a conservationist, interacting with local communities, government, researchers from all over Cuba, and international academics, especially from the Global North. I have lived through many experiences that made me aware of the damaging social repercussions that an extractive research practice has.

Reading the biocultural community protocol of Tswapong Hills in Botswana from the Women's Resources Enterprise Community Trust (Women's Resources Enterprise Community Trust in Tswapong, n.d.), I found this statement: "Researchers are our main stakeholders. Over the years, we have interacted with undergraduates, graduates, scholars, and academics from various institutions, locally and internationally. Despite this, we do not have the research results, which are critical to inform our growth as a Trust. Researchers are also not transparent about their intents concerning the information they get from us. We never know if the results have been used in accordance with our verbal agreements with researchers".

How do I give back to my participants? How do I avoid reproducing this usually extractive pattern even when my position as a working-class international PhD researcher at a British university is highly vulnerable? These have been critical questions in my research practice. In May 2024, after submitting my PhD thesis, I returned to Gaborone, Botswana, after obtaining a mobility grant under the Turin scheme at Coventry University. I reached out to participants to find out if they were willing to hear back from the research I had conducted thanks to their contributions once the writing process was finished (i.e., papers published, post-Viva corrections done). I have also drafted policy briefs that I sent to relevant participants in Botswana and Namibia.

Furthermore, I appeared on national TV in Botswana, discussing ornamental invasive plants in the sub-region (BWBotswana Television, 2024). Going forward, I will likely write articles summarising the project's results for the two gardening magazines from Botswana and

Zimbabwe and share the thesis, papers, and policy briefs with the interested participants. Moreover, I will likely share aspects of the research on relevant social media groups and relevant online blogs or magazines.

In summary, my thesis explored the interplay between the ornamental horticulture sector and plant invasions across Southern Africa through a qualitative and critical realist approach. I documented the invasive species on sale in Botswana, Namibia, and Zimbabwe, stressing the sector's high invasion debt. I noticed that Western colonial legacies shape the sector's structure and dynamics. Despite socioeconomic and cultural differences, I found commonalities in how stakeholders understand biological invasions. I provided recommendations to facilitate an integrated governance approach to biological invasions considering micro to macro-historical and geopolitical dynamics in the sub-region. My thesis highlights the relevance of socio-political contexts in the interplay between the ornamental sector and plant invasions. The importance of history implies that the management of ornamental-related plant invasions should operate with a sense of justice and care to avoid reproducing mechanisms of oppression. I reckon that my positionality as a researcher from a unique Global South context undoubtedly influenced my approach and interpretations. Following my positionality and ethical principles, I am committed to avoiding extractive research practices, giving back to the participants, and engaging beyond academia to contribute to a just and careful environmental practice.

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